

Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
Group Biomedical Sciences
Faculty of Medicine
Center for Molecular and Vascular Biology

Expanding *GNAS*-related pathology by genetic and epigenetic studies

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Doctoral thesis in Biomedical Sciences

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List of abbreviations

AHO	Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy
cAMP	cyclic adenosine monophosphate
CNS	central nervous system
CVD	cardiovascular disease
DAG	diacylglycerol
DMR	differentially methylated region
DNMT	DNA-methyltransferase
DNMT3A	DNA methyltransferase 3A
GDP	guanosine diphosphate
G α	G protein alpha subunit
GTP	guanosine triphosphate
GWAS	genome-wide association study
HDAC	histone deacetylases
ICR	imprinting control regions
IP ₃	inositol triphosphate
MAS	McCune Albright syndrome
MS-MLPA	methylation-sensitive multiplex ligation-dependent probe amplification
MS-PCR	methylation specific PCR
MTHFR	methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase
NTD	neural tube defect
PACAP	Pituitary adenylate cyclase-activating polypeptide
PCP	planar cell polarity

PGE ₂	prostaglandin E ₂
PHPIa	pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ia
PHPIb	pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ib
PKA	protein kinase A
PPHP	pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism
PTH	parathyroid hormone
RGS	regulator of G-protein signaling
SAM	S-adenosyl methionine
SB	spina bifida
SNP	single nucleotide polymorphism
TSH	thyroid stimulating hormone
TXA ₂	thromboxane A ₂
UPD	uniparental disomy
VPA	valproate

Introduction

This introduction includes the state-of-the-art literature on (epi)genetics in the field of GNAS pathology (**Chapter 1**) and neural tube defects (**Chapter 2**), being the major study subjects of my PhD thesis. **Chapter 3** describes my PhD project in the wider context of the current knowledge of epigenetics in relation to cardiovascular disease and platelet function and the position of 'epigenomics' against the other 'Omics' strategies.

Chapter 1

Regulation of the imprinted GNAS cluster in health and disease

Partially based on

Izzi B, Van Geet C, Freson K. Recent advances in GNAS epigenetic research of pseudohypoparathyroidism. Cur Mol Med. 2011. (In review)

General introduction to epigenetics

Epigenetics refers to functional changes in the genome that do not result in alterations of the nucleotide sequence. Epigenetic modifications are caused by a number of phenomena of which DNA methylation is certainly the most studied so far. Together with histone changes,¹ transcription of ncRNAs or siRNAs,²⁻⁴ and nuclear lamina protein interactions,⁵ DNA methylation plays a crucial role in determining transcript stability of imprinted genes, DNA folding, nucleosome positioning, chromatin compaction and nuclear organization, regulating in turn (tissue-specific) gene expression.

DNA methylation is a covalent modification that results from the activity of DNA-methyltransferases (DNMTs),⁶ which transfer a methyl group from the S-adenosyl methionine (SAM) to the cytosine ring. The resulting carbon-carbon bond is a stable epigenetic mark classically associated with gene silencing⁶⁻¹⁰ through direct interference of methylated CpG dinucleotides residing within a recognition element with the binding of a transcription factor. A second mechanism is indirect and links DNA methylation to inactive chromatin structures. Methylated DNA attracts methylated DNA binding proteins that recruit a repressor complex, which includes histone deacetylases (HDACs) that are able to deacetylate histones and favor an inactive chromatin state.^{6,8-11} Nevertheless, it is not really clear whether methyl marks are necessarily a cause or consequence of changes in chromatin structure and gene expression.¹² DNA methylation patterns are commonly established during early embryonic development¹³ and are maintained by the constant action of DNMTs.

Regulation of genomic imprinting by DNA methylation

Genomic imprinting refers to a special kind of epigenetic variation that involves heritable changes in the expression of a small number of autosomal genes. This result in a differential gene expression between the maternal and paternal allele.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Mutation or dysregulation of imprinted genes is associated with several human congenital diseases including Angelman, Prader-Willi, and Beckwith-Wiedemann as the most common imprinting syndromes. The first clue to the existence of imprinting was the observation that both androgenetic and parthenogenetic zygotes develop abnormally, demonstrating that normal development requires both a paternal and maternal contribution to the genome.^{17,18} Subsequently, specific chromosomal

regions in the mouse were identified as containing imprinted genes due to the fact that uniparental disomy (UPD) of these regions produced abnormal phenotypes.¹⁹ Often these imprinted regions contain several closely linked imprinted genes that are co-ordinately regulated. A specific mark placed on the gene in either the male or female gamete is thought to define its parental specific expression and is maintained in all somatic cells throughout development. This mark would have to be raised in the primordial germ cell so that the appropriate imprinting patterns could be re-established in the mature oocyte or spermatozoa, respectively (**Figure 1**). Virtually all the imprinted genes have one or more regions in which the cytosines within CpG dinucleotides are methylated on only one parental allele.^{14,16} In many instances, methylation within the differentially methylated regions (DMRs) is established in either the male or female gamete and maintained throughout pre- and postimplantation development. The deletion of these DMRs disrupts the imprinting of one or more genes in the imprinted region.²⁰⁻²⁴ As differential methylation of these regions is probably important for establishing imprinting, these regions have been referred to as methylation imprint marks or Imprinting Control Regions (ICRs).

Figure 1. From Reik W. et al.¹⁶ Genomic imprinting in mammals

Erasure, establishment and maintenance of methylation imprints at imprinting centres during germ cell and embryonic development. Imprinting control elements 1 (IC1) and IC2 are shown as examples (see chromosome 11p15.5 in FIG. 1). Grey

indicates modification and white indicates no modification at the corresponding alleles. Parental chromosomes are marked according to their sex in blue²⁵ or red (female). The reading (transcriptional interpretation of the primary imprints) in the developing embryo is indicated by arrows.

Structure of the imprinted *GNAS* cluster

The human gene for the stimulatory G protein alpha subunit ($G\alpha$) is located in the imprinted region *GNAS* (MIM 139320) on the distal portion of chromosome 20 (20q13.2-13.3)^{26,27} while its mouse ortholog is located in a syntenic region on chromosome 2.^{28,29} The overall structure of the mouse and human *GNAS* cluster is highly similar. The $G\alpha$ gene was originally defined by 13 exons. Due to alternative splicing involving exon 3 and with or without an extra codon, there exist four, functionally similar, $G\alpha$ isoforms (two of 45 and two of 52 kDa).^{30,31} The classical $G\alpha$ promoter and first exon are located within a CpG island that is unmethylated, resulting in $G\alpha$ expression from both alleles in most tissues³²⁻³⁴ and monoallelic maternal expression in a number of tissues such as proximal renal tubules, anterior pituitary and thyroid gland and the ovaries.³⁵⁻⁴¹ In addition, a recent study by Klemke et al.⁴² has reported higher maternal expression of $G\alpha$ in human lymphoblasts, peripheral blood mononuclear cells, mammary adipose tissue and heart.

The complex imprinted *GNAS* cluster contains at least three additional promoters and first exons located upstream of the $G\alpha$ promoter that all splice onto the common exon 2 of the classical $G\alpha$ gene and that are all imprinted (**Figure 2**). The most upstream *GNAS* promoter generates a transcript for the chromogranin-like protein NESP55.^{33,43} The entire NESP55 coding region is within the upstream exon while $G\alpha$ exon 2-13 contribute to the 3' untranslated region of the NESP55 transcripts.^{43,44} The NESP55 promoter region is methylated on the paternal allele and NESP55 is transcribed only from the maternal allele^{33,43,45} and primarily expressed in neuroendocrine tissues.^{46,47} An alternative promoter, located $\approx$ 11 kb downstream of the NESP55 promoter, generates a transcript for XL α s, a large isoform of $G\alpha$ with a long amino-terminal extension.^{32,33,44} The XL α s promoter region is methylated on the maternal allele and XL α s is expressed only from the paternal allele.^{32,33,45} XL α s has a more restricted tissue distribution in humans than $G\alpha$, being primarily expressed in neuroendocrine tissues including the brain, adrenal medulla, pars intermedia of the pituitary, stomach, heart, kidney and pancreatic islets.^{44,48-50} Paternally derived

antisense transcripts, which originate from a promoter upstream of the XL α s promoter and traverse the NESP55 promoter region, have also been identified.^{45,51} From a recent report it seems that these transcripts are involved in silencing of their sense NESP55 via a mechanism independent of DNA methylation.⁵² Finally, the alternative promoter and first exon (exon A/B also defined as exon 1A) located $\approx$ 2.5 kb upstream of Gs α exon 1 generates ubiquitously expressed transcripts that are presumed to be untranslated.^{34,53} The exon A/B region is methylated on the maternal allele, and exon A/B transcripts are expressed only from the paternal allele.^{34,54} Studies in mice suggest that this region is a primary imprinting mark, which regulates Gs α imprinting.^{54,55} In addition, it has been shown that PTH resistance in pseudohypoparathyroidism type 1b (PHPIb) is associated with loss of imprinting of exon A/B^{54,56} and tissue-specific loss of Gs α expression (in renal proximal tubules). The exon A/B region is therefore believed to contain a negative regulatory element for the classical Gs α promoter that is both methylation-sensitive and tissue-specific.

Figure 2. GNAS genomic organization and transcripts

Features of the paternal and the maternal allele are shown above and below the line, respectively. The arrows show initiation and direction of transcription. The first exons of the protein coding transcripts are shown as black boxes and the first exons of the noncoding transcripts (Nespas and exon A/B) are shown as gray boxes. Differentially methylated regions (DMRs) are shown by + symbols (indication of methylation). The figure is not to scale.

Gs α and XL α s in the Gs signaling cascade

Gs α is a member of the heterotrimeric G proteins that transmit signals from cell surface receptors to intracellular effectors, such as ion channels or enzymes (*e.g.*, adenylyl cyclase, Phospholipase C, ...), which generate second messengers (*e.g.*, cAMP, calcium, inositol triphosphate, ...). Classical G protein-coupled receptors have seven putative helical transmembrane domains with an extracellular amino terminus and an intracellular carboxyl terminus. **(Figure 3)** Each G protein is defined by its specific α -subunit, which binds guanine nucleotide and interacts with specific receptors and effectors. β - and γ -subunits form tightly but non-covalently bound dimers that are targeted to the plasma membrane through lipid modifications at the carboxyl terminus of γ -subunits. The three subunits are each the product of separate genes. The α -subunit of Gs is a protein found in all cell types except mature spermatozoa⁵⁷, which couples a wide variety of G protein-coupled receptors to the stimulation of adenylyl cyclase, the enzyme that catalyzes the synthesis of cAMP from ATP within cells. Many of the downstream effects of cAMP are mediated via activation of protein kinase A (PKA). Seven-transmembrane receptors for numerous extracellular signals, including many peptide hormones, catecholamines, and other biological amines and neurotransmitters, activate Gs α to raise intracellular cAMP in their target cells. However, Gs α activators may not be limited to the seven-transmembrane receptor family, as there is evidence that Gs α can also be activated by various tyrosine kinase receptors, including the epidermal growth factor^{58,59} and basic fibroblast growth factor receptors.⁶⁰ Nor is adenylyl cyclase the only effector activated by Gs α . Gs α has been shown to open specific Ca²⁺ channels in the heart^{61,62} and to interact (along with Gi1 α) directly with members of the src tyrosine kinase family.⁶³ Gs α undergoes palmitoylation at the amino terminus, which is required for membrane targeting.⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶ While most attention has been directed at the role of Gs α as a signal transducer at the plasma membrane, Gs α is also present in intracellular membrane compartments and has been implicated as a regulator of intracellular membrane trafficking.⁶⁷

Consistent with the high degree of homology between Gs α and XL α s, XL α s can couple to typical Gs α -coupled receptors and can stimulate intracellular cAMP generation in transfected cells.⁶⁸⁻⁷⁰ Very recently it has been shown that transgenic

XL α s expression in the proximal tubules enhanced G α -mediated responses, indicating that XL α s can mimic G α also in vivo.⁷¹

Figure 3. From Van Geet C. et al.⁷² The GTPase signaling cascade.

In basal state, a heterotrimeric G-protein exists as an inactive G α - β - γ heterotrimer with GDP bound to G α . Upon activation of the GPCR via interaction with its ligand, GDP is exchanged for GTP causing the G α -subunit to switch into an active conformation and to dissociate from the β - γ -dimer. Subsequently, the GTP-bound G α as well as the β - γ -dimer interact directly with their intra- cellular effectors. The hydrolysis of GTP by the intrinsic GTPase activity of the α -subunit is accelerated by regulator of G-protein signaling (RGS) proteins and this leads to the dissociation of the subunits from its effectors and terminates the signaling cascade. The inactivated G α -subunit then reassociates with the β - γ -dimer.

- *G α /XL α s signaling in platelets as studied by the platelet inhibition-aggregation test*

As in other cells, G proteins in platelets play a major role in signal transduction by mediating the interaction between agonist, receptor and enzymes, which produce second messengers (**Figure 4**). G α s plays the same role in the regulation of cAMP as it does in other cells, although the consequent elevation of cAMP is known to have an inhibitory function in platelets. Agents such as prostaglandin I₂, prostacyclin D₂, adenosin and adrenalin are G α s agonists and antagonists of platelet aggregation via stimulation of adenylyl cyclase and upregulation of intracellular levels of cAMP. In platelets and megakaryoblasts, G α s is present in a short (45 kDa) and a long (52 kDa) isoform, the G α -S and G α -L isoforms, respectively.⁷³ Several studies have been performed to assess the contribution of these isoforms in megakaryocyte synthesis

of cAMP. Megakaryocytic maturation has been shown to be accompanied by a downregulation of mRNA for $G_s\alpha$ and disappearance of iloprost-induced calcium mobilization, followed by upregulation of the $G_s\alpha$ -L stimulatory G protein and an increase in iloprost-induced cAMP formation.⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶ We have found that platelets also express the XL α_s variant.⁷⁷

The platelet $G_s\alpha$ /XL α_s activity can easily be studied by using the platelet inhibition-aggregation test^{78,79} (**Figure 4**). This test is based on the inhibition of platelet aggregation by cAMP produced by G_s agonists such as prostaglandin E1 or the stable prostacyclin analog Iloprost. This test was shown to be reliable in the identification of both $G_s\alpha$ hyper- and hypofunction.⁷⁸⁻⁸⁰

Figure 4. From Van Geet C. et al.⁷² GPCR signaling as basis for platelet aggregation-inhibition test.

Thromboxane A2 (TXA2), ADP, thrombin, PGE2, PGI2 and PACAP bind to GPCRs on the platelet surface. Different agonists for receptors coupled to G α_q or G α_i subunits stimulate platelet aggregation and shape change. G α_q activates PLC, which stimulates the production of IP3 and DAG, with the consequent stimulation of PKC and release of intracellular calcium. The presence of high levels of cytosolic Ca²⁺ is needed for integrin α IIb β 3 activation and stable platelet aggregation. G α_i inhibits the production of cAMP by adenylyl cyclase (AC) while $G_s\alpha$ and its isoform XL α_s stimulate cAMP production. High levels of cAMP inhibit platelet aggregation via multiple mechanisms.

Platelet pathology related to defects in the G_s signaling cascade

Both bleeding and thrombotic phenotypes have been described to be dependent on a defective $G_s\alpha$ function in platelets. Via the platelet aggregation-inhibition test a platelet G_s hyperfunction has been identified in a group of patients having a paternally inherited polymorphism (36bp insertion in combination with 2 substitutions) in the XL α_s .^{77,81} The mutated variant of XL α_s is associated with

elevated inducible platelet Gs activity and a high level of cAMP formation, and therefore leads to an increased trauma-related bleeding tendency.^{77,81} On the other hand, Gs hypofunction has been shown to be also relevant in platelet function since a first compound heterozygous Gs α deficient patient has been described to have a thrombotic phenotype due to absence of inhibition of platelet aggregation by Gs α stimulation and extreme platelet hyperreactivity.⁸² His platelets form almost no cAMP after Gs-coupled receptor activation. In both cases the thrombopathic phenotype is also associated with some AHO features which confirm the possible crucial role of a defective Gs α function also in other cell types and tissues.

Human diseases associated with defects in the Gs signaling pathway

As Gs α is ubiquitously expressed and is a necessary component for signaling pathways in many cells, genetic defects in the Gs α gene would be expected to lead to pleiotropic manifestations. Within the past decades it became obvious that Gs α signaling defects can result from gain-of-function, loss-of-function, or *GNAS* imprinting mutations.

Gsa gain-of-function mutations: McCune Albright syndrome (MAS; MIM 174800)

MAS is classically defined as the co-appearance of hyperpigmented (café-au-lait) skin lesions, sexual precocity, and fibrous dysplasia of bone.⁸³ However, MAS patients may present with only one or two of these manifestations or may also present with other endocrine or non-endocrine manifestations.^{84,85} MAS patients may develop hyperfunctional thyroid nodules, macronodular adrenal hyperplasia or adrenal adenomas associated with hypercortisolism, somatotroph adenomas, or hypophosphatemic rickets or osteomalacia.⁸⁶ In each case the peripheral endocrine organs (thyroid, adrenal cortex, gonads) appear to be activated despite low circulating levels of their respective stimulatory pituitary hormone (thyrotropin, adrenocorticotropin, gonadotropins).^{86,87} MAS patients may also develop one or more non-endocrine abnormalities affecting the liver, heart, thymus, spleen, bone marrow, gastrointestinal tract, or the brain.^{88,89}

MAS is likely to be caused by a dominant somatic Gs α mutation as the extent of clinical manifestations within each patient is determined by the specific distribution of mutant-bearing cells.⁹⁰ Presumably the mutation would be lethal in the germline, as MAS is never inherited. The endocrine and skin manifestations of MAS provided

the clue that activating Gs α mutations might be the underlying cause, as cAMP was known to stimulate endocrine gland proliferation, hormone secretion, and pigment granule formation. Many studies indeed showed that MAS is caused by somatic Gs α mutations affecting residue R201H/C.^{88,91-93} In a recent MAS report it has been shown that paternal inheritance of the same mutation involving the XL α s transcript lead to its constitutive activation and cAMP generation suggesting a role for XL α s in the pathogenesis of MAS.⁹⁴ It remains to be elucidated how activating Gs α /XL α s mutations lead to the non-endocrine manifestations of MAS.

- *Gs α loss-of-function mutations: Pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ia vs. Pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism*

Heterozygous Gs alpha loss-of-function mutations are often the leading cause of a complex phenotype termed Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy which is characterized by short stature, obesity, brachydactyly, subcutaneous ossifications, and mental deficits or developmental delay.⁹⁵ Brachydactyly refers to shortening and widening of long bones in the hands and feet, which may or may not be symmetric and most often involves the distal phalanx of the thumb and fourth and fifth metacarpals. The severity of the AHO phenotype varies widely between patients, with some patients having few, or no, features of the syndrome.^{95,96} Maternal inherited Gs α mutations cause pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ia (PHP-Ia),⁹⁷ a clinical condition where AHO features are accompanied by endocrine dysfunctions characterized by parathormone (PTH) resistance, hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia.⁹⁷⁻¹⁰¹ Some patients with PHP-Ia also present with multi-hormonal resistance in addition to PTH resistance.^{41,102-104}

Alternatively, paternal Gs α mutations are often present in pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism (PPHP) patients which present with multiple AHO features but no hormone resistance.¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁸ Those patients have normal levels of PTH and TSH and have normal urinary cAMP responses to administered PTH.¹⁰⁹ Because many clinical features of AHO are non-specific, the diagnosis of PPHP can only be made in patients within a well-documented AHO kindred or in whom a Gs functional defect is identified.

Biochemical reconstitution assays that measure the Gs pathway in erythrocyte cell membranes showed that the Gs activity is decreased by $\approx$ 50% in membranes

isolated from PHP-Ia patients.¹⁰⁹⁻¹¹¹ Decreased Gs activity is often associated with decreased Gs α mRNA and/or protein expression.^{112,113} A similar Gs α deficiency is also present in PPHP patients, suggesting that both disorders are caused by a common gene defect.¹⁰⁹

Consistent with 50% loss of Gs α function in PHP-Ia and PPHP, multiple heterozygous mutations have been identified in these patients and were reviewed in the last few years.¹¹⁴ Identical Gs α mutations are present in both PHP-Ia and PPHP patients and sometimes over the same family.^{95,105} Many studies now show that PHP-Ia results from maternal inheritance, while PPHP results from paternal inheritance of the same mutations, strongly suggesting that Gs α is an imprinted gene.¹⁰⁵ This model would predict that Gs α is normally expressed primarily from the maternal allele due to silencing (imprinting) of the paternal allele in hormone target tissues (e.g. renal proximal tubules). Inactivating mutations on the active maternal allele would lead to loss of Gs α expression and hormone signaling (PHP-Ia), while mutations on the inactive paternal allele would have no effect on Gs α expression or hormone signaling (PPHP). This explains why urinary cAMP response to administered PTH is reduced in PHP-Ia but not in PPHP patients.¹¹⁵ Support for this model comes from studies on Gs α knockout mice that confirm Gs α imprinting in renal proximal tubules.³⁵ The imprinting of Gs α would have to be tissue-specific, as Gs α is not imprinted in several human and mouse tissues^{32,35,43} and is supported by the fact that in several tissues Gs α expression is similarly reduced by 50 % in both PHP-Ia and PPHP patients.¹⁰⁹

GNAS imprinting defects: Pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ib (PHP-Ib)

Pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ib (PHP-Ib) patients predominantly have PTH and sometimes TSH resistance but do not present with AHO features.^{116,117} They do not show Gs α coding mutations^{56,97} but instead they show a loss of exon A/B methylation.^{54,118-120} Exon A/B hypomethylation in familial cases of PHP-Ib appears to be caused by maternally inherited deletions affecting either the STX16 gene (STX16del4-6 or STX16del2-4)^{121,122} or the NESP55/NESPAS region (delNESP55/delAS3-4 and delAS3-4).^{123,124} These two regions in *GNAS* are therefore considered as cis-acting elements, which are critical for both the establishment and the maintenance of the exon A/B maternal-specific methylation pattern.¹²³ Broad *GNAS* imprinting defects involving all differentially methylated *GNAS* regions are

mostly observed in the sporadic PHP-Ib cases with NESP55 hypermethylation versus XL and exon A/B hypomethylation.^{119,124-127} In only few of those patients paternal uniparental isodisomy of the long arm of chromosome 20 (patUPD20) has been detected.¹²⁸⁻¹³⁰ However, the imprinting control element that is disrupted and responsible for the overall loss of imprinting in most sporadic PHP-Ib cases still remains unknown and it was recently hypothesized that this would be a trans-acting element.¹³¹ In both familial and sporadic PHP-Ib cases, exon A/B hypomethylation is thought to interfere with the normal $Gs\alpha$ expression in the proximal renal tubules and therefore responsible for the PTH resistance in these patients.⁹⁷

Need for reclassification of GNAS pathology? Imprinting defects in PHP-Ia

Despite the original classification of PHP patients in type Ia versus type Ib due to the presence of having a heterozygous loss-of-function versus an imprinting *GNAS* mutation, respectively, recent studies have now demonstrated the presence of an overall *GNAS* methylation abnormality in PHP-Ia patients with PTH resistance but also having a mild to obvious AHO phenotype.^{126,132-134} These findings suggest that PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib can also be considered as extremes of a disease spectrum that includes PHP patients without coding *GNAS* mutations but having a *GNAS* epigenetic defect and still having a variable or no AHO phenotype. A recent study from Lecumberri et al.¹³⁵ further supported this epigenetic overlap between PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib by reporting two unrelated PHP families each of which included at least one patient with a $Gs\alpha$ coding mutation and another with *GNAS* loss of imprinting, which in only one case was due to a paternal uniparental isodisomy of chromosome 20q. Both genetic and epigenetic *GNAS* defects found in PHP patients are thought to decrease the function or expression of $Gs\alpha$ in renal proximal tubules where the classical *GNAS* gene is considered as a maternal-specific gene. As a consequence, both PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib patients develop hypocalcemia, hyperphosphatemia and low circulating 1.25-dihydroxyvitamin D levels. The latter in turn dramatically reduces PTH signaling in the cells via affecting the activation of the cAMP/Protein Kinase A (PKA) pathway. In the renal proximal tubules, $Gs\alpha$ is in fact responsible for the regulation of PTH action in reducing phosphate reabsorption, leading to increased renal phosphate wasting and conversion of 25-hydroxyvitamin D to 1.25-dihydroxyvitamin D.^{136,137}

Detection and diagnosis of PHP

PHP diagnosis can be made upon the combination of the analysis of clinical signs such as having AHO features or not, laboratory biochemical tests (including PTH, TSH, calcium and phosphate measurements), genetic and epigenetic screening of *GNAS* and some specific in vitro assays measuring Gs α protein activity in erythrocyte membranes^{138,139} or platelets^{79,80} from the patients (**Table 1**). Gs α activity testing using erythrocyte membranes was first believed to be only effective when a mutation in the *GNAS* coding region would lead to a significant decreased Gs α function in PHP-Ia or PPHP patients. This in vitro assay was not able to detect an abnormal Gs α function in erythrocytes from PHP-Ib patients.¹⁴⁰ A recent study by de Nanclares et al.¹³² first described five PHP-Ia patients with broad epigenetic *GNAS* abnormalities and still having slightly reduced levels of Gs α activity in their erythrocyte membranes. We could in addition describe a loss of platelet Gs α activity in patients with PHP-Ia or PPHP and in sporadic cases of PHP-Ib with an overall *GNAS* methylation defect.⁸⁰ Platelets from familial PHP-Ib cases have a normal Gs α activity. A recent study by Zazo et al.¹⁴¹ confirmed these data in a larger cohort of PHP-Ib patients with both *GNAS* overall or exon A/B-specific methylation abnormalities, however reporting no functional difference in the two subgroups of PHP-Ib patients.⁸⁰ These recent data obtained by functional Gs α testing also strengthen the evidence of the clinical and (epi)genetic overlapping of PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib syndromes, thus again indicating that a new classification of PHP patients should be made by studying more patients with novel more sensitive DNA methylation detection assays.

Table 1. Clinical classification of GNAS related pathology and genetic and epigenetic findings

	PHPIb		PHPIa	PPHP
	Sporadic	Familial (Autosomal Dominant)		
AHO	No	No	Yes	Yes
PTH resistance	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
GNAS defect	NESP hypermethylation XL hypomethylation Exon A/B hypomethylation	Exon A/B hypomethylation	Maternal loss-of-function mutation or NESP-XL-Exon A/B methylation defect	Paternal loss-of function mutation
Transmission	De novo	Maternal	Maternal	Paternal
Gs activity in erythrocytes ^{132,141}	Mild hypofunction*	Mild hypofunction*	Hypofunction**	Hypofunction**
Gs function in platelets ⁸⁰	Mild hypofunction ‡	Normal	Hypofunction ‡ ‡	Hypofunction ‡ ‡

* ≈ 50%; ** ≈ 80%; ‡ and ‡ ‡ see⁸⁰

GNAS DNA methylation studies via different techniques

Many studies are already published that focused on the detection of the methylation of the different DMRs of the *GNAS* cluster using various techniques but here we will specifically summarize the studies that involve the description of *GNAS* imprinting defects in PHP patients (**Table 2**). The first DNA methylation analysis techniques used to study *GNAS* imprinting allowed the characterization of only one or few CpG sites. These kind of methods include Southern blot analysis using methylation sensitive restriction analysis of total genomic DNA and PCR amplification of bisulfite treated DNA before performing a methylation sensitive restriction analysis.^{79,80,118,119,121,142}

These methods allow the study of only these CpGs that are part of a methylation-sensitive restriction site and defects will only be detected in samples having a relatively high percentage of altered DNA methylation. This could represent an important limitation when studying patients with intermediate *GNAS* imprinting defects having rather small alterations in DNA methylation below the detection limit of these methods or having defects in DNA methylation at other CpGs in the same imprinting region than the one or few CpGs that were actually studied.

Therefore, there was a need for methods that allow the simultaneous study of multiple CpGs within the same DMR. Most of these more recent techniques are also based upon a first step of bisulfite treatment of DNA. For the second step, these methods use a methylation specific PCR (MS-PCR),^{120,131,143-146} sequencing of subcloned PCR fragments and the direct sequencing of PCR fragments.^{80,117,132,133,147,148} MS-PCR has been applied in only a few studies and relies on the selective PCR amplification of either the unmethylated or methylated allele using primers that specifically anneal with either one of these alleles. The subcloning of PCR fragments before sequencing is considered as gold standard method to study DNA methylation and has been used in different studies to characterize *GNAS* methylation in PHP patients. This last method allows the detection of methylation at multiple CpG sites but it is also highly time-consuming, making the study of larger DNA sample sets very difficult.^{142,149,150}

All above methods do not allow a true quantitative of CpG methylation. The study of imprinting disorders recently improved since novel methodologies to quantify DNA methylation became available with high sensitivity to detect only small differences in

DNA methylation. Bisulfite pyrosequencing, used in some studies analyzing *GNAS* methylation,^{125,134,151} is based on the synthesis of complementary strands of bisulfite-treated DNA during which pyrophosphate¹⁵² is released and converted in enzyme-catalyzed reactions; the latter determines a certain light emission proportional to the number of incorporations, thus allowing the discrimination between unmethylated and methylated strands. Methylation-sensitive endonucleases are on the contrary required when using Multiplex Ligation-dependent Probe Amplification (MS-MLPA)¹⁵³ since it is performed directly on genomic DNA. Despite the increased sensitivity of these methods allowing the quantification of multiple CpG sites, one important limitation remains as only relatively short fragments of DNA of about 100-150 bp can be studied. The MassArray-based analysis used by the Sequenom EpiTYPER¹⁵⁴ overcomes this problem and allows the analysis of fragments up to 500 bp. We recently applied this methodology to study *GNAS* methylation and found a high sensitivity in detecting even small methylation differences with a high reproducibility.¹²⁶ Via this methodology, which also relies on initial bisulphite treatment of DNA, we could characterize different *GNAS* methylation patterns in PHP patients and further defined the differences in *GNAS* epigenotypes of sporadic and familial PHP-Ib patients.¹²⁶ Via methodologies such as the Sequenom EpiTYPER, low penetrance *GNAS* imprinting defects might be more easily detectable, since there has been evidence for such a phenomenon in at least some PHP patients.^{120,131}

Table 2. GNAS methylation studies in PHP patients

Method	Number and type of PHP patients studied	Results of GNAS methylation				Reference
		NESP	NESPAS	XL	Exon A/B	
Single/few CpGs non quantitative						
Southern Blot Bisulphite restriction analysis	1 PHP-Ib with patUPD20	↑	↓	↓	↓	128
	11 AD-PHP-Ib + 1 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	↓	↓	↓	118
	1 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	-	↓	↓	79
	17 AD-PHP-Ib + 1 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	↓	↓	↓	121
	5 AD-PHP-Ib + 15 sporadic PHP	↑	↓	↓	↓	119
	2 AD-PHP-Ib + 8 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	↓	↓	↓	117
	4 PHP-Ia	↑	↓	↓	↓	132
	3 AD-PHP-Ib + 6 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	-	↓	↓	80
2 AD-PHP-Ib + 2 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	-	-	↓	148	
Multiple CpGs non quantitative						
Direct bisulphite sequencing Bisulphite subcloning and sequencing MS-PCR	1 AD-PHP-Ib	NI	-	nl	↓	143
	17 AD-PHP-Ib + 6 sporadic PHP-Ib + 9 PHP-Ia	-	-	-	↓	120
	1 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	↓	↓	↓	133
Multiple CpGs quantitative						
Pyrosequencing Sequenom EpiTYPER MS-MLPA MethylQuant	1 sporadic PHP-Ib					153
	40 sporadic PHP-Ia	↑	↓	↓	↓	134
	4 AD-PHP-Ia + 8 sporadic PHP-Ib + 2 PHP-Ia + 2 low Ca/high PTH resistance	↑	-	↓ ↑	↓	126
	3 AD-PHP-Ib + 16 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	↓	↓	↓	125
	2 AD-PHP-Ib + 4 sporadic PHP-Ib	↑	↓	↓	↓	131
	6 AD-PHP-Ib + 11 sporadic PHP-Ib	-	↓	↓	↓	141

↑ Significant gain of methylation; ↓ significant loss of methylation; - not detected; nl normal methylation

Chapter 2

Neural Tube Defects

Clinical description

Neural Tube Defects (NTDs) are among the most common of human birth defects, with an overall prevalence of around 0.5–2/1,000 pregnancies and frequently result in infant mortality or major health problems in surviving children.¹⁵⁵ They result from perturbation in the neurulation process. Neurulation, through a coordinated series of events, gives rise to the neural plate, neural folds and the neural tube, which eventually differentiates and develops into the future brain and spinal cord. Most NTDs arise in anterior and posterior neuropores as they close last. NTDs can be open or closed depending upon exposed or closed neural tissue. Open NTDs are the result of primary neurulation and may involve any area of the central nervous system (CNS). Closed NTDs are due to defects in secondary neurulation and are mostly confined to the spine.

The nature and severity of NTDs is determined by the stage and axial level at which closure fails.¹⁵⁶ The most severe defects are the cranial manifestations of NTDs represented by craniorachischisis and anencephaly that are both not compatible with life after birth, owing to in utero neurodegeneration. Spinal presentations are instead the result of closure failure of the posterior neuropore. They include the open spina bifida forms such as myelomeningocele and meningocele, where the defects in the vertebral arches are associated with the presence of the open neural folds (**Figure 5**). In addition, myelomeningocele is often associated with other complications such as hydrocephalus and Arnold-Chiari type II malformation. A milder form of spinal malformations is represented by spina bifida occulta, where the outer part of some vertebrae is not completely closed, but the skin is often normal and in most cases this condition is asymptomatic. In general, the clinical severity of spina bifida is affected by the axial level at which closure fails but patients frequently suffer from paralysis of the legs, as well as from bowel and bladder dysfunction.

The underlying molecular defect(s) for NTDs

The underlying causes for NTDs remain poorly understood in humans as the precise biochemical and cellular factors involved are still elusive, partly due to the lack of large families with Mendelian inheritance and also because of the high degree of heterogeneity between unrelated sporadic cases. There are a number of evidences

that suggest an interaction between both genetic and environmental factors as possible etiology for NTDs.¹⁵⁷⁻¹⁵⁹

Figure 5 Lateral view of the spinal cord in three types of spina bifida. From Botto LD et al.¹⁶⁰

Spina bifida occulta occurs most often at S1, S2, or both and is a bony defect of the spine, usually covered by normal skin. A meningocele is a sacular herniation of meninges and cerebrospinal fluid through a bony defect of the spine. Menigoceles are usually covered by normal skin. A myelomeningocele is the most common type of spina bifida and is characterized by herniation of the spinal cord, nerves, or both through a bony defect of the spine. Myelomeningoceles are usually open defects in which either the meninges or neural tissue is exposed to the environment. Of these three types, only meningocele and myelomeningocele are typically included in studies of spina bifida and are often jointly referred to as spina bifida cystica. The spinal cord and nerves are depicted in yellow and the cerebrospinal fluid is black.

Environment

A number of factors have been described to elevate the risk for NTDs. These include medical conditions such as maternal diabetes¹⁶¹ or maternal obesity¹⁶² while environmental exposures such as cigarette smoke, mycotoxins or use of anti-epileptic drugs may have teratogenic effects.¹⁶³⁻¹⁶⁵ Maternal dietary factors leading to a high dietary glycemic index or a high glycemic load are associated with increased risk of a NTD-affected pregnancy,¹⁶⁶ as are sub-optimal levels of folate and vitamin B.^{167,168} Maternal supplementation with folic acid during the first trimester of pregnancy has been proved to reduce the risk of NTDs.^{167,169,170} Those studies were further supported by the finding that elevated homocysteine levels have been associated with sub-optimal levels of folate and/or vitamin B₁₂ in maternal blood.^{168,171-173}

Genetics

Based on this evidence, primary focuses of genetic studies in NTDs involved genes coding for proteins regulating the folate one-carbon metabolism^{159,174,175} (**Figure 2**).

The most robust genetic risk factor for NTDs is the 677C>T SNP in 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR)¹⁷⁶ which is associated with elevated homocysteine.¹⁷⁷ However, some NTD cases were shown to be not folate-preventable¹⁷⁸ and it has been shown that maternal folate levels in most affected pregnancies fall within the “normal” range.¹⁷⁹

However, there are more evidences suggesting the role of genetics as predisposing factor for NTDs. High recurrence risk for siblings of affected individuals and association of NTDs with specific chromosomal anomalies has been reported.¹⁸⁰⁻¹⁸²

In addition, more than 200 different mouse genetic models have been described to have NTDs.^{183,184} However, of those 200 genes only few have been confirmed to be involved in human NTDs.¹⁵⁹ Some studies have focused on the human orthologous of those genes that cause NTDs in mice as possible causative factors for human NTDs. However, very few consistent findings originated from this candidate gene approach, except for a potential role for the non-canonical Wnt pathway ‘Planar Cell Polarity’ (PCP).¹⁷⁵ Mutations in the PCP gene VANGL1 were identified in few patients with NTDs¹⁸⁵ and were next characterized as loss of function variants in VANGL2 depleted zebrafish.¹⁸⁶ A case-control study was performed to evaluate the role of several key Wnt signaling genes in NTDs but none of the 172 evaluated SNPs in these Wnt regulatory genes showed an association with SB.¹⁸⁷

Apart from candidate-gene studies, the conventional gene hunting strategies such as positional cloning and linkage mapping were not applicable to study NTDs because of the paucity of large families with multiple affected individuals. It has been suggested to focus on larger patient cohorts using high-throughput genomic technologies such as detection of CNVs or GWAS to identify novel regulatory genes for NTDs.^{159,175} However, despite the notable success of GWAS in revealing numerous new disease-associated genes and loci, all the GWAS-SNPs collectively only account for a small proportion of the heritability of complex diseases. The same GWAS finding is expected for NTDs. The post-GWAS era strongly suggests to functionally characterize those risk loci.¹⁸⁸ Since many of the GWAS SNPs are located

in non-coding regions that are expected to have an effect on gene expression such as by modifying transcription factor binding sites, DNA methylation or histone positioning, further studies are needed to gain more insight in the field.

Epigenetics

Some of the established risk factors may act mechanistically via an effect on epigenetic regulation thereby influencing susceptibility through altered gene expression. Evidence for a potential role for epigenetic effects on gene regulation is emerging both from the study of human NTDs and from analysis of mouse models. The role of epigenetics in NTDs has recently been suggested based on a theoretical hypothesis.¹⁸⁹ Some evidence for a role of histone positioning in NTDs comes from studies that showed that valproate (VPA) that is widely used as anticonvulsant agent is associated with 1-2% incidence of NTD and 10-20-fold increased risk for lumbosacral meningomyelocele when taken during the first trimester of pregnancy¹⁹⁰⁻¹⁹³ It is suggested that its potent histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitory activity could affect neurulation as also shown in zebrafish.¹⁹⁴ Some literature suggests in particular a specific role for DNA methylation in the neurulation process and in the development of NTDs. First of all, folates are internal to the intracellular one-carbon metabolism (**Figure 6**) that produces pyrimidines and purines for DNA synthesis and s-adenosyl methionine,¹⁹⁵ the universal methyl group donor for all macromolecules, including DNA. Therefore, cell proliferation that depends on DNA synthesis and stimulation of DNA methylation are likely effects of folate supplementation. Secondly, epidemiological studies are suggestive for a link between impaired methylation cycle and human NTDs, since an association was found with elevated homocysteine and sub-optimal levels of folate in maternal blood.^{168,171} Few small-scale studies focused on fetal DNA methylation demonstrated an inverse correlation between LINE-1 DNA methylation and homocysteine levels.^{196,197} In addition, experimental evidence from model systems also supports the hypothesis that abnormal methylation contributes to NTDs. Mice deficient for DNA methyltransferase 3A (DNMT3A) or treated with methyl cycle inhibitors have cranial NTDs.^{198,199}

Figure 2. The metabolic roles of folic acid. From Botto LD et al.¹⁶⁰

After entering the cell, folic acid is involved in the transfer of carbon atoms that are used to synthesize nucleotides or through the conversion of homocysteine to methionine, for the methylation of a variety of substrates. These processes are regulated by numerous molecules, including enzymes and vitamins other than folic acid (e.g. vitamins B₆ and B₁₂). The activity of some enzymes, such as methionine synthase, may be influenced by other enzymes, such as methionine synthase reductase. Enzymes and factors that may be important in neural-tube development are indicated by boxes.

Preceding study

The complete coding region of GNAS (including NESP, XL and GNAS) was Sanger sequenced for a NTD patient with pronounced brachydactyly (short metacarpals IV), short stature, mental retardation (**Table 3**) and platelet Gs hypofunction comparable to defects observed in PHP-1a patients.⁸⁰ A unique combination of nucleotide substitutions in exon 7 and exon 13 on the same allele of the GNAS gene that was previously shown to be associated with three GNAS splice variants and reduced Gs protein levels²⁰⁰ has been detected in this SB patient. The incidence of these combined substitutions in a series of sporadic SB patients is 6.09 % (5/82). The 4 other SB patients with these GNAS variants also had AHO features and platelet Gs hypofunction (**table 1**). We tested unrelated controls and found an incidence in 2/397 without evidence of spinal closure defects (0.5% versus 6,09%, p=0.0021).

We hypothesized that GNAS methylation abnormalities could account also for the Gs platelet abnormal function in SB patients and therefore possibly have a causative role in the pathogenesis of NTDs.

Type of spina bifida	Brachydactyly /brachytarsy	Short stature	Mental retardation	Obesity
1. SB oc / UMS	+	+	-	-
2. SB oc / UMS	+	+	+	-
3. SB ap / H	-	+	-	-
4. SB ap / H	ND	+	+	+
5. SB ap / H	ND	+	-	-

Table 3. Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO) features in 5 spina bifida (SB) patients.

SB oc, spina bifida occulta; SB ap, spina bifida aperta; UMS, upper motor neuron sign; H, hydrocephalus; ND, not determined via Xray

Chapter 3

From Genetics to Epigenetics in platelet research

Invited review

Freson K, Izzi B, Van Geet C. From genetics to epigenetics in platelet research. Thromb Research. 2011. (In review)

Introduction to epigenomics

Epigenomics (or often referred to as epigenetics) is one of the fastest growing research domains in biomedicine. Most studied epigenetic phenomena include studies on imprinting, on metabolic networks, on genetic hierarchies in embryonic development and on mechanisms of gene activation in cancer. However, more recently it became clear that the epigenome is also involved in the pathogenesis of other complex diseases such as immunological, cardiovascular, developmental and neurological diseases.²⁰¹ Epigenomics defines chromatin-based mechanisms that are important in the regulation of gene expression but does not involve changes to the DNA sequence per se. These mechanisms include three different but interrelated mechanisms: DNA methylation, histone modifications and RNA-based mechanisms.^{8,202} The first two mechanisms change DNA accessibility for the transcriptional machinery and chromatin structure, resulting in altered gene expression. These epigenetic tags are essential to normal development and differentiation of different cell lineages in the adult organism. They can however be modified by exogenous factors such as nutritional and environmental influences or pathogenic conditions. In general, DNA methylation is a long-term epigenomic modification while short-term histone modifications are more flexible to acetylation and methylation reactions. In this review, we will specifically focus on the epigenomic modifications that are only introduced by DNA methylation, concentrating on examples that relate to cardiovascular disease and platelet (dys)function.

Basic mechanisms of epigenetic modifications by DNA methylation

The best understood epigenetic mechanism is DNA methylation, a covalent modification that occurs predominantly at cytosines followed by guanines (referred to as a CpG site) to form 5-methylcytosines.⁸ This modification alters the affinity of methylation-sensitive binding proteins, chromatin structure and correlates with transcriptional gene silencing. Methylation within gene promoters and CpG-dense sequences (CpG islands) was always thought to have the highest functional relevance to control gene expression. More recently, regions with variable methylation and enriched with functional CpG sites were identified up to 2 kb from the CpG islands (islands shores).²⁰³ About 50 % of gene promoter regions have CpG

islands that consist of a high density of CpG's, are typically unmethylated and act as a regulatory switch.²⁰⁴ DNA methylation is mitotically stable and is transmitted through cell division and for some loci even transgenerationally. The early postconceptional period is a critical window for the establishment of DNA methylation tags. During the development of germ cells their genomes are demethylated and after fertilization the combined genome is remethylated again with the exception of the imprinted genes that are characterized by a parent-specific DNA methylation pattern (see further for the GNAS gene). However, the epigenome undergoes dynamic changes induced by environmental factors (nutrition, maternal stress and behavior) throughout life to contribute and maintain adaptive and deviant gene-expression states. It was estimated that the maintenance of methylation is 97 to 99.9% per mitosis while de novo methylation occurs in adult somatic cells in 3 to 5% of mitosis, generating additional epigenetic changes.

The first methods to detect DNA methylation were qualitative measurements that used bisulfite sequencing and methylation-specific polymerase chain reaction. More recently, quantitative technologies for large-scale parallel epigenomic analysis became available including high-throughput pyrosequencing of bisulfite-treated DNA, high density oligomer arrays for the detection of methylation signals, and DNA-mass spectrometry for precise measurements of the copies of methylated genes/loci in larger sets of DNA samples.^{201,205} Currently, relatively inexpensive chip arrays are available that quantify DNA methylation at about 27.580 (Illumina Human methylation 27K BeadChip) or 486.000 (450K BeadChip) 'individual' CpGs. The 27k Bead Chip was recently used to quantify DNA methylation differences in relation to smoking.²⁰⁶ The genome-wide scale methods for epigenomic analysis are still limited because they are prone to analytic artifacts and measurement errors. Therefore technical validation through more accurate techniques is warranted such as by pyrosequencing or mass spectrometry to validate the genome-scale findings. The mass spectrometry-based methylation detection method 'Sequenom EpiTYPER' was used in the smoking study to replicate the findings for candidate loci with differential methylation in larger sample sets.²⁰⁶ This methodology allows the quantitative assessment of methylation ratios simultaneously across 'multiple' CpG sites in a

specific DNA locus over many samples, increasing the scope and throughput of analysis.

The role changes in DNA methylation in cardiovascular disease

The first studies that assessed genetic predisposition to cardiovascular disease (CVD) used a 'candidate gene approach' through association studies in prospective analysis or case-control studies to identify a set of common SNPs at loci that are associated with CVD. These candidate genes were chosen because on their essential role in the different processes that predispose to atherosclerosis. This hypothesis-driven search for useful genetic markers provides the foundation of the genetic CVD risk factors. Next, genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have sought to identify genetic determinants of CVD.²⁰⁷ However, in general, despite the notable success of GWAS in revealing numerous new disease-associated genes and loci, all the GWAS identified SNPs that collectively only account for a small proportion of the heritability of complex diseases. Two major dilemmas with these genomic studies have emerged: they identified loci, which do not correspond to genes and the effects of environmental factors such as diet, exercise, socioeconomic status and developmental stresses are ignored. Therefore, the post-GWAS era strongly suggests to functionally characterising risk loci.¹⁸⁸ Since many of the GWAS SNPs are located in non-coding regions that are expected to have an effect on gene expression such as by modifying transcription factor binding sites, DNA methylation or histone positioning, further studies of these aspects are expected to gain more interest in the next coming years.

A review by Baccarelli et al.²⁰⁸ showed the exponential increase in epigenetic publications related to CVD with only 12 reports in 1995 compared to 525 reports in 2010. Some studies have shown that the fetal environment influences the susceptibility to chronic disorders as a low birth weight increases the CVD risk.^{209,210} This led to the hypothesis that fetal metabolic adjustments to adverse circumstances to restrict growth and thus brain development, may result in an increased risk for CVD later in life. Indeed, participants in the 'Dutch Hunger Winter Families study' who were exposed in utero to the 1944-1945 famine, developed a higher risk for overweight, impaired glucose homeostasis and increased CVD risk in adulthood.²¹¹ Interestingly, these subjects had hypomethylation of the imprinted IGF2 and INSIGF

genes and hypermethylation of the GNAS-AS, MEG3, IL10 and ABCA1 and LEP genes compared to the unexposed siblings.²¹²

Studies that used the above described genome-scale methylation detection approaches to unravel differentially methylated loci that are associated with CVD have not yet been reported. However, some studies used the average blood genomic DNA methylation of repetitive sequences, such as Alu or LINE-1, to study the effect of certain environmental factors on the overall DNA methylation and this in relation to pathology.²¹³ Recent findings from the Normative Aging study showed lower LINE-1 methylation in leukocytes as a predictor for incidence and mortality from ischemic heart disease and stroke.²¹⁴ This global methylation provides an average estimate of methylation across the entire genome or in wide portions of DNA but does not have the resolution to pinpoint individual genes or sequences responsible for CVD risk. Though the genome-scale DNA methylation screening methodology is ready to use, some questions remain open as whether leukocytes reflect the right epigenomic signatures, how to perform replicate studies, how to analyze the epigenomic data in terms of to what extent the epigenetic tag varies with age, sex, race and environmental factors.

Can modifications in DNA methylation have a role in platelet activity? GNAS as an example

The study of epigenetic processes such as DNA methylation and histone modification are a completely unexplored domain in platelet research, as the analysis of these processes requires DNA. However, since epigenetic marks are already set after zygote implantation, the epigenome of each mature cellular lineage carries the record of its developmental history. Therefore, we believe that alterations in DNA methylation for genes important for platelet function can also be studied using leukocyte DNA. Pubmed searches for 'DNA methylation and platelets' result only in 15 hits. For this part of the review, we therefore will only focus on the methylation study of the imprinted GNAS cluster in relation to platelet stimulatory G-protein function, as there are no other studies to our knowledge that showed an association between DNA methylation and platelets.

Platelet Gs activity is easily determined using the platelet aggregation-inhibition test which gives a value for the Gs α activity based on the inhibition of platelet

aggregation by the generation of cAMP after incubation with different G-protein coupled receptor agonists such as PGI₂ or PGE₂.^{78,215} Gs is not coded by a single gene but by the complex imprinted gene cluster GNAS, that gives rise to several transcripts, antisense transcripts and noncoding RNAs, including transcription of Gs (**Figure 2, chapter 1**).²¹⁵ The GNAS cluster includes three differentially methylated regions with a paternal-specific expression of XL and ExonA/B and a maternal-specific expression for NESP. The phenotypes resulting from both genetic and epigenetic abnormalities of the GNAS region include Albright Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO), pseudohypoparathyroidism types Ia (PHP-Ia) and Ib (PHP-Ib) and pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism (PPHP). PHP-Ia (maternally inherited Gs α mutation) and PPHP (paternally inherited Gs α mutation) patients have an AHO phenotype (short stature, round face, subcutaneous calcifications, mental retardation, obesity and brachydactyly) with or without parathyroid hormone (PTH) resistance respectively and show a platelet Gs hypofunction as a higher concentration of Gs α agonist is needed to inhibit their platelet aggregation compared to normal individuals.⁸⁰ The clinical importance for Gs hypofunction in platelets becomes clear in the first compound heterozygous Gs deficient patient with an extremely severe AHO and PTH resistance, no inhibition of platelet aggregation by Gs stimulation and hyperreactive platelets with a shortened PFA100.⁸² PHP-Ib patients with PTH resistance and no AHO have an imprinting GNAS defect with an abnormal GNAS methylation pattern with exon A/B and XL hypomethylation and NESP hypermethylation and subsequently a decreased Gs expression^{79,80}. Their platelets show mild Gs hypofunction. Recently, the mass spectrometry Sequenom EpiTYPER was used to quantify methylation of the three different differentially methylated regions in GNAS using leukocyte DNA from PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia patients with mild to pronounced Gs hypofunction, respectively. Significant differences in methylation were found in the NESP, XL and ExonA/B GNAS regions.¹²⁶ Finally the same method was used to study GNAS methylation in two patients with stroke at young age and some mild AHO features but normal Gs gene. These patients showed especially a NESP hypermethylation²¹⁶ but further studies in a larger patient group are needed to support the possible role of GNAS loss-of-imprinting in the pathogenesis of ischemic stroke at young age and its causal relation with platelet Gs

hypofunction. Interestingly, a recent GWAS showed evidence for an association of blood pressure and CVD with the GNAS locus.²¹⁷ The associated SNP was not located in a coding sequence but near the imprinted GNAS cluster and therefore this SNP could be a modifier of a regulatory element.

Conclusions

Epigenomics represents a critical link between genomic coding and phenotype expression that is influenced by both underlying genetic and environmental factors (**Figure 7**). Epigenetic modifications could contribute to subclinical and clinical CVD and platelet dysfunction. Epigenomics is of course inherently connected to genetics because epigenetic modifications such as DNA methylation (methylome) and histone modifications can alter gene expression (transcriptome). Integration of the transcriptome and proteome²¹⁸ of a specific cell type related to CVD (endothelial cell, vascular smooth muscle cell, cardiac myocyte or platelets) can eventually gain further insights in this complex disease. Computational techniques will be essential for the integrated analysis of all 'omics' findings to subtract the essential factors that are truly related to the disease.

Figure 7. Conceptual model to linking epigenomics and genomics to further transcriptomics and proteomics to predict risk factors for complex diseases such as cardiovascular disease.

Chapter 4

Aims of the study

My PhD project will mainly focus on the finding of new (epi)genetic causes associated with an AHO phenotype and/or having PTH resistance in combination with a defective platelet Gs signaling pathway. Patients will be studied that have this phenotype (clinically defined as PHP-Ia, PHP-Ib or PPHP) but do not have an inactivating mutation in the coding region of the classical GNAS gene. Our study group includes a total of 270 patients of which 256 have only AHO features (PPHP), 14 patients with PTH resistance (of which 2 patients only have profound hypocalcemia; PHP-Ib) and 2 patients with PHP-Ia. For 24 and 15% of the 256 patients, we could identify a Gs hypo- or hyperfunction, respectively. Since Gs hypofunction was further found in platelets from 5 spina bifida patients with Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy features having a GNAS splice mutation, 96 other spina bifida cases were included for further (epi-)genetic GNAS studies.

Because of the large study group, I designed and optimized some large-scale (epi)genetic screening methods to study locus-specific methylation (Sequenom EpiTYPER), genome-wide methylation (27K BeadChip) and the presence of copy number variations in GNAS (MAQ-array).

Therefore the specific aims for my PhD thesis were:

Aim 1. to optimize methods for screening of GNAS methylation defects in PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia cases (Chapter 5 and chapters 6 and 7 for Sequenom EpiTYPER);

Aim 2. to screen for CNVs in the GNAS region in PPHP patients with MAQarray (Chapter 8);

Aim 3. to screen for epigenetic defects (GNAS, IGF2, H19, SNURF, GRB10) in PPHP patients using the sequenom EpiTYPER (Chapter 9);

Aim 4. to screen for genome-wide (27K BeadChip) methylation defects in Spina Bifida cases, replicate the candidate loci by sequenom analysis and functionally characterize them for function in neurulation in zebrafish (Chapter 10).

Chapter 5

***GNAS* defects identified by stimulatory G protein α -subunit signalling studies in platelets**

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*My contribution to this work has led to the optimization of a new rapid *GNAS* methylation screening method which has been applied to characterize all PHP-1b patients here described.*

Abstract

Context: *GNAS* is an imprinted region that gives rise to several transcripts, antisense transcripts, and noncoding RNAs, including transcription of RNA encoding the α -subunit of the stimulatory G protein (Gs α). The complexity of the *GNAS* cluster results in ubiquitous genomic imprints, tissue-specific Gs α expression, and multiple genotype-phenotype relationships. Phenotypes resulting from genetic and epigenetic abnormalities of the *GNAS* region include Albright's hereditary osteodystrophy, pseudohypoparathyroidism types Ia (PHP-Ia) and Ib (PHP-Ib), and pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism (PPHP).

Objective: The aim was to study the complex *GNAS* pathology by a functional test as an alternative to the generally used but labor-intensive erythrocyte complementation assay.

Design and Patients: We report the first platelet-based diagnostic test for Gs α hypofunction, supported by clinical, biochemical, and molecular data for six patients with PHP-Ia or PPHP and nine patients with PHP-Ib. The platelet test is based on the inhibition of platelet aggregation by cAMP, produced after Gs α stimulation.

Results: Platelets are easily accessible, and platelet aggregation responses were found to reflect Gs α signaling defects in patients, in concordance with the patient's phenotype and genotype. Gs α hypofunction in PHP-Ia and PPHP patients with *GNAS* mutations was clearly detected by this method. Mildly decreased or normal Gs α function was detected in patients with PHP-Ib with either an overall or exon 1A-only epigenetic defect, respectively. Platelet Gs α expression was reduced in both PHP-Ib patient groups, whereas XL α s was up-regulated only in PHP-Ib patients with the broad epigenetic defect.

Conclusion: The platelet-based test is a novel tool for establishing the diagnosis of Gs α defects, which may otherwise be quite challenging.

Introduction

The *GNAS* imprinted cluster on chromosome 20q13 is characterized by many complex genetic and epigenetic regulatory aspects.^{1,2} It encodes multiple gene products through the use of alternative promoters and first exons that splice onto a common set of downstream exons (**Figure 1**). The most downstream “classical” first exon (exon 1) generates ubiquitous transcripts for Gs α , the G protein α -subunit that couples receptors to adenylyl cyclase and is therefore required for receptor-mediated cAMP generation. Two upstream exons generate overlapping transcripts encoding the chromogranin-like protein NESP55 and the extra large Gs α isoform XL α s, respectively.³ NESP55 and XL α s are primarily expressed in neuroendocrine tissues, but little is known about their biological function. Finally, the exon 1A-containing transcripts are presumably not translated into a functional protein.⁴ All these additional gene products are oppositely imprinted: NESP55 is only expressed from the maternal allele and its promoter is methylated only on the paternal allele, whereas XL α s and exon 1A are expressed from the paternal allele, and their promoters are methylated only on the maternal allele.^{5,6} Although the classical Gs α promoter is unmethylated on both alleles and mostly biallelically expressed in most human adult and fetal tissues,⁵⁻⁸ recent studies have reported prevalent maternal expression of the Gs α gene in some human postnatal tissues such as the pituitary,⁹ thyroid, and gonads.¹⁰ Studies in the mouse also revealed a predominant maternal Gs α expression in the renal proximal tubules,¹¹⁻¹³ although this has not yet been demonstrated in humans.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the human STX16 loci and *GNAS* gene cluster on chromosome 20q13

Chapter 5-Gs α signaling studies in platelets

Exons are depicted as boxes, and the arrows indicate the direction and allelic origin (red for paternal, green for maternal) of the different GNAS transcripts. Differential GNAS splicing is indicated with dotted lines. Paternal and maternal imprint settings are indicated as CH3 for the methylated allele and for the transcriptional active allele. The different GNAS-associated pathologies with their responsible genetic abnormalities are indicated. nl, Normal; Δ , chromosomal deletion.

Heterozygous inactivating Gs α mutations lead to Albright's hereditary osteodystrophy (AHO), an autosomal dominant disorder characterized by short stature, sc ossifications, brachydactyly, and, in many cases, mental retardation and/or developmental delay.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ In addition to AHO, maternal transmission of Gs α mutations can lead to end-organ resistance to several hormones that activate Gs α -coupled pathways, particularly resistance to PTH in the renal proximal tubule.^{12,13} The presence of AHO, obesity, and multihormonal resistance is termed pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ia (PHP-Ia).¹⁶⁻¹⁸ In contrast, paternal transmission of Gs α mutations leads to the AHO phenotype alone, a condition referred to as pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism (PPHP).¹⁶⁻¹⁹ This different phenotype is explained by the differential expression of Gs α in the proximal renal tubule from the maternal allele only. Similar to what is observed in humans, maternal, but not paternal, transmission of the Gs α knockout allele in mice resulted in renal PTH resistance and reduced PTH-stimulated cAMP production in renal proximal tubules.¹³ Mice with targeted disruption of Gs α exon 2 in both alleles die in early gestation, demonstrating that Gs α expression is necessary for development.^{13,20}

Patients with PHP-Ib present with renal PTH resistance, usually in the absence of the AHO phenotype.¹⁴ As in PHP-Ia, urinary cAMP responses to PTH are markedly reduced in patients with PHP-Ib, suggesting that Gs α expression is lost in renal proximal tubules. It was recently shown that PHP-Ib is caused by a *GNAS* imprinting defect that leads to a paternal-specific imprinting pattern (unmethylated, transcriptionally active) on both alleles in the exon 1A promoter region.^{21,22} The familial form of the disease has been shown to be associated with an exon 1A-only methylation defect and a heterozygous 3-kb deletion mutation within the closely linked *STX16* gene.²¹⁻²³ Similar methylation changes in the *NESP55* and *XL α s* promoter regions are only present in patients with a sporadic form of PHP-Ib.²³ The exon 1A region is believed to be critical for the tissue-specific imprinting of Gs α in the renal proximal tubules.

AHO is characterized by considerable genetic heterogeneity.²⁴⁻²⁶ In a recent study,

Gs α activity was determined in isolated erythrocyte membranes from 106 patients with AHO, including 93 subjects with endocrine abnormalities (PHP-Ia).²⁷ Significantly reduced Gs α activity was found in 78 PHP-Ia and 13 PPHP patients, but an inactivating *GNAS* mutation was found only in 64 and 23% of these patients, respectively. In contrast, *GNAS* mutations were also found in 26% of patients with AHO and endocrinopathies who had normal Gs α erythrocyte function. This clinical entity is often referred to as PHP type Ic, but actually might rather reflect limitations of the assay used for the detection of Gs α activity, and probably represents a variant of PHP-Ia. The low mutation detection rate in patients with abnormal erythrocyte Gs α activity and the fact that *GNAS* mutations exist in patients with normal Gs α activity could be due to either a clinical or biological misdiagnosis of Gs α loss of activity. In some cases, a firm clinical diagnosis of PHP-Ia and especially PPHP may be hard to make because the AHO features can be nonspecific. Also, patients with PHP-Ib have a normal erythrocyte Gs α activity.²⁶ The generally used quantitative determination of erythrocyte Gs α functional activity is based on an ex vivo complementation assay in which adenylyl cyclase of S49 cyc⁻ murine lymphoma cells, which genetically lack Gs α , is reconstituted with human erythrocyte membranes.^{27,28} This method relies on Gs α activation via ADP ribosylation or GTP γ S stimulation and is generally used but not readily applicable for screening purposes. In addition, a normal Gs α activity in the presence of an inactivating *GNAS* mutation can still be determined because direct Gs α -coupled receptor activation is not being measured by this method. There is a need for a robust and less cumbersome assay to study Gs α activity after Gs α -coupled receptor activation in children and adults, using routinely available cells such as platelets, which may subsequently also contribute to the identification of genetic defects.

We propose to use a platelet-based Gs α activity assay that we previously described in patients with a platelet Gs α hyperfunction due to an insertion in XLalphas and in a PHP-Ib patient with a mild platelet Gs α hypofunction.^{29,30} This test is based on the inhibition of platelet aggregation by cAMP produced by Gs α agonists and proved to be straightforward and reliable, requiring only 15 ml of blood. Platelet Gs α activity was studied in six patients with a clinical AHO phenotype and in nine patients with PHP-Ib having a broad or exon 1A-only epigenetic defect. We found that the platelet

Gs α function test reflects the patients' clinical and molecular defects. In addition to leukocyte genomic DNA (gDNA), we also used platelet reversed-transcribed RNA to screen the *GNAS* coding region for mutations and platelet protein extracts to unravel underlying Gs α signaling defects further.

Subjects and Methods

Blood sampling

Healthy donors and AHO and PHP-1b patients, not taking aspirin or other medication interfering with platelet function for at least 10 d, donated 15 ml of blood anticoagulated with 3.8% (wt/vol) trisodium citrate, as well as 10 ml of EDTA anticoagulated blood. Platelet-rich plasma (PRP) from these samples was prepared by centrifugation (15 min at 150 X g). Citrated PRP was adjusted by autologous plasma to 250 X 10⁹ platelets per liter for platelet aggregations; 2 ml PRP was pelleted by centrifugation to prepare platelet protein extracts. PRP from EDTA anticoagulated blood was used for platelet RNA extraction. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and/or their legal representatives. The Institutional Review Board approved this study.

Platelet aggregation-inhibition test

Platelet aggregation was performed within 3 h after blood collection on two dual-channel Chrono-Log Aggregometers (Chronolog Corp., Havertown, PA) as described.^{29,30} Aggregation inhibition studies involved dose-response curves upon platelet stimulation with Gs α agonists: prostaglandin E1 (Prostin, 0–1 μ g/ml; GE Healthcare Life Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden), or the stable prostacyclin analog iloprost (Ilomédine, 0–5 ng/ml; Schering-Plough, Kenilworth, NY). These were added to PRP 1 min before induction of aggregation by collagen (2 μ g/ml). The IC₅₀ with SD was calculated for each Gs α agonist from the patient's dose-response curve and compared with the IC₅₀ for the same Gs α agonist of a control person, performed simultaneously. The intra-assay and inter-assay coefficients of variation are, respectively, 12.5 and 13.9% for prostaglandin E1 (n = 5) and 7 and 9.3% for prostacyclin (n = 5).

GNAS mutation detection

Total RNA was extracted from platelets using the TRIzol (Invitrogen) reagent,

according to the manufacturer's protocol. The *GNAS* gene was amplified from platelet RNA to detect potential alternative splicing defects. Primers for the *GNAS* amplification were GSF3 (5'-GGCTGCCTCGGGAACAGTAAG-3') and GS6R (5'-TAATCATGCCCTATGGTGGGTG-3'). Exons 1 to 13 of *GNAS* including intron/exon boundaries were amplified from leukocyte gDNA in 13 PCR fragments. Part of the *GNAS* promoter and exon 1 were amplified using 7-deaza-dGTP (GE Healthcare) instead of dGTP during the PCR. Sequencing was performed using the BigDye terminator chemistry on an ABI310 sequencer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA). All primers and PCR conditions are available upon request.

STX16 and NESP deletion analysis

Leukocyte gDNA samples from PHPIb patients were screened for the presence of the 3-kb deletion mutation within *STX16* by PCR as previously described.³¹ PHP-Ib patients with an overall *GNAS* methylation defect and negative for the *STX16* deletion were screened for NESP deletions by Southern blot analysis and PCR.³²

Methylation analysis of the GNAS cluster by Southern blot analysis

Southern blot analysis was done after double digestion of gDNA (15 μ g) with different combinations of methylation-insensitive (*Pst*I, *Bgl*II, and *Sac*I) and methylation-sensitive (*Asc*I, *Ngom*IV, and *Not*I) enzymes as previously described.³⁰ Radioactive labeled exon 1A, exon XL, or exon NESP55-specific PCR fragments were used as genomic probes.

Methylation analysis of the GNAS cluster by bisulfite conversion of DNA

The bisulfite reaction was carried out on 500 ng of gDNA with the MethylDetector bisulfite modification kit (Active Motif, Carlsbad, CA). A conversion reaction was performed in a 140- μ L mixture containing 13 μ L of gDNA, 7 μ L of hydroquinone, and 120 μ L of conversion buffer, as described by the manufacturer. DNA was denatured with an initial melt at 94°C for 3 min, and then a conversion at 50° C for 9 h was performed in a PTC-200 Peltier Thermal Cycler (MJ Research, Reno, NV). An on-column desulfonation of converted DNA was performed, and DNA was eluted as indicated by the manufacturer. Control nested PCRs were performed on 40 ng of both unconverted and converted DNA to verify the DNA conversion using primers and reagents provided with the kit. Different nested PCRs were performed to amplify the NESP55, XL α s, and exon 1A regions using 5 μ L bisulfite-treated gDNA, 0.5 μ M

primers, 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 1X buffer (20 mM Tris (pH 8.4), 50 mM KCl), and 0.2 μ L (5 U/ μ L) Taq DNA polymerase (Invitrogen). All primer sequences and PCR conditions are available in **supplementary Table 1** (published as supplemental data on The Endocrine Society's Journals Online web site at <http://jcem.endojournals.org>). Amplified PCR products were further digested with restriction enzymes that only recognize the nonconverted (methylated) DNA sequence: SsiI (Fermentas, St. Leon-Rot, Germany) for NESP55, Sall (Fermentas) for XL, and HinfI (Fermentas) for exon 1A. Digested PCR fragments were separated on a 2% agarose gel.

Platelet immunoblot analysis

Platelets isolated from citrated blood were directly lysed in ice-cold PBS containing 1% igepal CA-630 (Sigma Chemical, St. Louis, MO), 2 mmol/L Na₃VO₄, 1 mmol/L EDTA, 1 mmol/L phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride, 2 mmol/L dithioerythritol, 1% aprotinin, and 2 mmol/L NaF, and incubated on ice for 60 min. Lysates were cleared of insoluble debris by centrifugation at 14,000 X g for 20 min at 4°C. Platelet soluble cytosol protein fractions (12.5 μ g for Gs α and β -tubulin and 25 μ g for XL α s) were mixed with Laemmli sample buffer (5% SDS reducing buffer), resolved by SDS/PAGE on 10% acrylamide gels, and transferred to Hybond ECL-nitro-cellulose membrane (GE Healthcare). Blots were blocked for 1 h at room temperature in Tris-buffered saline with Tween (0.1% Tween-20) supplemented with 5% nonfat dry milk. Incubation with primary (overnight at 4°C) and secondary (2 to 3 h at room temperature) antibody was performed in Tris-buffered saline with Tween with 5% nonfat milk. Blots were revealed with a polyclonal anti-Gs α antibody (Santa Cruz Biotechnology Inc., Santa Cruz, CA), a monoclonal anti-XL α s antibody (11F7)²⁸ or a monoclonal anti-beta-tubulin antibody (Santa Cruz). Bands were quantified using the Java image processing program ImageJ 1.34 g (NIH Image software).

Statistical analysis

We used GraphPad InStat 3.01 software (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA). Continuous variables with small to mild skewness were summarized as mean $\pm$ SD and compared by the Student t test for unpaired data. Two-sided P values <0.05 were considered significant.

Results

Patients

Table 1 summarizes the clinical data of 16 index cases, comprising six patients with multiple AHO features with or without endocrinopathies and nine unrelated patients with PHP-Ib.

Novel mutations in GNAS and imprinting analysis

We screened the classical *GNAS* gene for mutations using platelet RNA for RT-PCR with primers encompassing exons 1 to 13 and leukocyte gDNA for sequencing all exons, including exon/intron boundaries. Six different heterozygous mutations, scattered throughout the *GNAS* gene, were found in AHO patients 1 to 6; these are not listed in the Human Genome Mutation Database for *GNAS* mutations except for the R231C mutation (**Table 2**). The *GNAS* mutations in patients 1, 4, and 6 are de novo mutations, whereas patient 5 inherited the Q35X mutation from her mother. Parental DNA samples were not available for patients 2 and 3. The methylation status of the exon 1A, NESP, and XL region of the *GNAS* cluster was also studied in nine PHP-Ib patients with PTH resistance without an AHO phenotype (**Table 2**). We developed a novel, easy, and reliable method to study *GNAS* methylation, based on bisulfite treatment of leukocyte gDNA, followed by PCR and restriction digestion with enzymes that only recognize the nonconverted methylated allele. All data could be confirmed by Southern blot analysis (data not shown). PHP-Ib patients 7 to 12 have overall imprinting defects with the loss of the *HinfI* and *Sall* restriction digestion sites in the exon 1A and XL regions, respectively, and a gain of the *SsiI* digestion site in the NESP region (**Figure 2A**). As expected, the 3-kb STX16 deletion could not be detected in the PHP-Ib patients with a broad epigenetic *GNAS* defect (Fig. 2B). Recently, two unrelated PHP-Ib patients were described with an overall *GNAS* methylation defect, without a STX16 deletion, but having deletions involving NESP and two of the antisense exons.³² We could not detect a deletion by Southern blot and PCR in the NESP region in patients 7 to 12 (data not shown). In line with previous evidence,²³ patients 13, 14, and 15, with an autosomal dominant form of PHP-Ib, have an exon 1A-only epigenetic defect with only a loss of exon 1A methylation (**Figure 2A**) and have the 3-kb STX16 deletion (**Figure 2B**). The mother of patient 14 with normal PTH levels carried the STX16 deletion but had a normal exon 1A methylation, as studied by PCR and Southern blot analysis of leukocyte DNA. The parental origin of the STX16 deletion could not be determined in this subject.

Figure 2. GNAS methylation and STX16 deletion analysis in PHP1b patients

A, Methylation analysis of exon 1A, exon XL, and exon NESP55 by PCR and restriction digestion (*Hinf*I, *Sa*I, and *Ss*I, respectively) of bisulfite-treated DNA from the indicated individuals and unrelated normal controls (ctrl). The mother (M14) and sister (S14) of patient 14 and the mother of patient 15 (M15) were also studied. B, Patients 13 to 15, M14, and M15 are carriers of the STX16 deletion as detected by PCR using primers, flanking the deletion.

Platelet Gs α screening assay

We have previously used the platelet aggregation-inhibition test to demonstrate Gs α hyperactivity.²⁹ Now, we performed the platelet aggregation-inhibition test in 24 healthy controls and compared their mean IC50 values $\pm$ SD, determined for two different Gs α agonists, with the IC50 values for the PHP-Ia, PPHP, and PHP-Ib patients (Table 2). When platelet aggregation was induced with collagen in AHO patients 1 to 6, after preincubation with either prostaglandin E1 (Prostin) or a stable prostacyclin analog (Iloprost), significantly higher concentrations of both Gs α agonists were required to achieve 50% inhibition of platelet aggregation (IC50), compared with the healthy controls. **Figure 3** illustrates the platelet aggregation-inhibition test for patient 1, carrying *GNAS* missense mutation D173N, and patient 3, with a 21-bp insertion, vs. two unrelated normal controls. Further studies with increased patient numbers are needed to define whether there are differences in platelet functional Gs α activity between PHP-Ia and PPHP patients.

PHP-Ib patients 7 to 12 had mild Gs α hypofunction, in association with an overall *GNAS* imprinting defect, as we already described for patient 7.³⁰ Platelet Gs α activity

was normal in PHP-1b patients with an exon 1A-only methylation defect and a STX16 deletion (Table 2).

Figure 3. Platelet Gs α aggregation-inhibition test

Dose-dependent inhibition of collagen-induced platelet aggregation (2 μ g/ml) by the indicated concentrations of two Gs α -coupled receptor agonists: prostacyclin (Iloprost, ng/ml) (A) and prostaglandin E1 (ng/ml) (B) for patient 1 and a control and for patient 3 and a control.

Sporadic PHP-1b vs. autosomal dominant PHP-1b in platelets

To rationalize the differences in functional platelet Gs α activity in patients with an overall vs. an exon 1A-only methylation defect, platelet Gs α and XLas protein levels were quantified.

Both PHP-1b patient groups express lower levels of Gs α in the platelet soluble cytosol

fraction compared with unrelated normal controls, but remarkably, no differences were seen in Gs α expression between the two different PHP-Ib groups (**Figure 4**). Gs α expression was normal in patient 1 with the D173N *GNAS* missense mutation and was decreased about 60% in PHP-Ia patients 2 and 3, with an out-of-frame *GNAS* mutation (supplementary Fig. 1, published as supplemental data on The Endocrine Society's Journals Online web site at <http://jcem.endojournals.org>). As we described before,³⁰ platelet cytosol fractions from PHP-Ib patients with an overall methylation defect, including an XL loss of methylation, express higher levels of XL α s compared with control platelets. This difference in XL α s expression was not observed in platelets from PHP-Ib patients with an exon 1A-only methylation defect or in the PHP-Ia patients (Fig. 4). No differences were seen in the expression levels of the widely expressed β -tubulin between the PHP-Ib patients and the controls.

Figure 4. Gs α and XL α s expression in PHP-Ib platelets

Immunoblot analysis (A) and densitometric scanning (B) of Gs α , XL α s, and β -tubulin proteins in platelet lysates from PHP-Ib patients with an overall methylation defect (patients 9, 10, 11, and 13 or gray bars; n=4), PHP-Ib patients with an exon 1A-only methylation defect (patients 14 and 15 or black bars; n=2), and normal controls (white bars; n=3). The results are expressed as percentage of controls (taken as 100%). Values are means $\pm$ SD. *, P<0.05.

Discussion

Platelets are easily accessible cells and have been used to study the coupling between membrane receptors, heterotrimeric G proteins, and intracellular signaling events.³³ The role of different G proteins in platelet function is extensively studied in

mouse models for Gq α , G α 12, G α 13, G α z, Gi α 2, and G α i3 deficiencies,³⁴ but the role of Gs α in platelet signaling has not been studied in Gs α heterozygous knockout mice^{13,35} or in humans with either PHP-Ia or PPHP. We hypothesized that an individual's Gs α activity could easily be estimated by the platelet aggregation-inhibition test, based on the inhibition of platelet aggregation by cAMP, induced after preincubation with different specific Gs α agonists. In this study, platelet Gs α signaling was evaluated in patients with PHP-Ia, PPHP, or PHP-Ib.

When platelet aggregation from six patients with PHP-Ia or PPHP was induced with collagen, after preincubation with either prostaglandin E1 (Prostin) or a stable prostacyclin analog (Iloprost), significantly higher concentrations of both Gs α agonists were required to cause platelet aggregation inhibition, compared with simultaneously studied normal controls. This platelet-based Gs α test helps to confirm the clinical diagnosis of AHO, which can be difficult if it is simply based on the presence of nonspecific but common phenotypic features such as short stature, brachydactyly, mental retardation, and other less frequent symptoms such as cataract and deafness.²⁶ The severity of the AHO phenotype varies considerably among patients, and some patients with inactivating *GNAS* mutations have either few or no features of the syndrome.^{26,36,37} Moreover, some features of AHO are also present in other disorders, such as the AHO-like syndrome caused by small terminal deletions on chromosome 2.^{38,39} We have studied platelet Gs α signaling in two previously described patients⁴⁰ with a 2q37.3 deletion and found normal Gs α platelet activity (data not shown). This makes the diagnosis of PPHP, especially in families without endocrinopathies, extremely difficult. Here we showed that Gs α function in a platelet aggregation-inhibition test is an easy and reliable diagnostic test, not only for patients with PHP-Ia but also for patients with PPHP. Analysis of more patients is needed to compare the efficiency of the platelet-based assay with the more generally used erythrocyte test, especially because it was recently shown that PHP-Ia and PPHP patients with an abnormal erythrocyte Gs α activity do not carry a *GNAS* mutation in 36 and 77% of all cases, respectively, and also because *GNAS* mutations were found in patients with a normal Gs α activity.²⁷

Erythrocytes and platelets of patients with PHP-Ib have previously been shown to have normal Gs α activity using the membrane complementation assay.^{26,41} But it

was also shown that platelets from patients with PHP-Ib accumulate less cAMP in response to prostacyclin than do platelets from control subjects.⁴¹ Our platelet-based Gs α assay can be used to detect mild Gs α hypofunction in sporadic PHP-Ib patients with overall *GNAS* methylation defects, but platelet Gs α activity was normal in PHP-Ib patients with an exon 1A-only methylation defect and a *STX16* deletion. A recent study showed no clinical or laboratory differences in PHP-Ib patients with an overall or exon 1A-only methylation defect.⁴² Mild platelet Gs α hypofunction was previously described in PHP-Ib patient 7 with an overall *GNAS* imprinting defect.³⁰ In this paper, we studied the platelet Gs α activity in five additional PHP-Ib patients with an overall imprinting defect and could confirm the presence of a mild platelet Gs α hypofunction. Similar to the findings for PHP-Ib patient 8, platelets from four patients with an overall methylation defect showed decreased Gs α and increased XL α s protein levels, compared with control platelets. In contrast, three PHP-Ib patients with an exon 1A-only methylation defect presented with normal platelet Gs α activity. Platelets from two of these patients showed decreased Gs α but normal XL α s protein levels. The nine PHP-Ib patients share the exon 1A hypomethylation defect, suggesting that the disturbed transcriptional regulation between exon 1A and exon 1 of the *GNAS* gene could account for the decreased platelet Gs α expression in all PHP-Ib patients, but it could not be responsible for the altered platelet Gs α function in only a subgroup of the PHP-Ib patients. We have previously shown that patient 8 with an overall methylation defect also had an XL hypomethylation with increased XL α s platelet protein expression.³⁰ In agreement, platelets from four other PHP-Ib patients with overall methylation defects have increased XL α s protein levels, whereas XL α s was normally expressed in platelets from PHP-Ib patients with an exon 1A-only methylation defect. Further studies are needed to find out whether similar expression differences are seen in the insoluble platelet membrane fractions and whether XL α s upregulation in platelets is directly responsible for the Gs α hypofunction in the six PHP-Ib patients with the overall imprinting defects. Normally, XL α s can substitute for Gs α , but this has not yet been studied for platelets.⁴³ Compatible with this observation is the opposite phenotype that patients with a bleeding tendency and a 36-bp insertion in XL α s showed increased Gs α levels and platelet Gs α hyperactivity.^{29,44} The six PHP-Ib patients with

the overall imprinting defects did not have deletions in the NESP55 region, as recently described for two PHP-Ib patients,³² which is suggestive of the existence of a third not yet known imprinting control domain for *GNAS*. The six PHP-Ib patients with the overall imprinting defects have no family history of the disease, which also raises the possibility of an autosomal recessive form of PHP-Ib in these subjects.

Because platelets are anucleated cells, it is impossible to study their *GNAS* methylation status. Megakaryocytes or platelet progenitor cells have a polyploid DNA content. To our knowledge, there are no studies describing the imprinting of the *GNAS* cluster during megakaryopoiesis or platelet production or in mature platelets. In a previous study, we found that exon 1A was hypermethylated in a human megakaryocytic cell line MEG01.³⁰ Therefore, it would be interesting to study the *GNAS* imprinting during megakaryocyte development from hematopoietic stem cells of PHP-Ib patients and normal individuals.

In conclusion, the platelet aggregation-inhibition test can be rapidly performed and reflects the behavior of the Gs α pathway *in vivo*. Moreover, in contrast to the erythrocyte membrane complementation assay, this assay uses the complete signaling system of the patient, thereby providing the opportunity to study the Gs α defect in more functional detail. One blood sampling per patient was sufficient to study the platelet Gs α activity, the platelet *GNAS* gene sequence, leukocyte gDNA sequence, and *GNAS* methylation profile, and finally the platelet Gs α protein levels. Platelet studies can be used to unravel pathogenic mechanisms in patients having more than a platelet dysfunction.⁴⁵ By studying easily accessible cells such as platelets, we could detect defective Gs α signaling in PHP-Ia, PPHP, and PHP-Ib patients with broad epigenetic *GNAS* defects.

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Table 1. Clinical and biochemical features of the patient cohort

Patient, Gender, Age at diagnosis (years)	Family History	Clinical classification	AHO FEATURES ^a						PTH RESISTANCE			TSH RESISTANCE
			RF	BM	SCC	MR	SS	O	Calcium (8.9 – 10.5) mg/dl	Phosphat e (2.3 – 4.7) mg/dl	PTH (3 – 40) ng/L	TSH (0.15 – 4.6) mIU/L
1, F, 16	No	PHPIa	+	+	-	+	+	+	5.4	8.1	430	22.9
2, F, 18	No	PPHIa	+	+	+	+	+	+	*	*	*	*
3, F, 7	No	PHPIa	+	+	+	+	+	+	*	*	*	5.79
4, M, 13	No	PHPIa	+	+	+	+	+	+	5.2	11.2	206	8.7
5, M, 4	Yes	PHPIa	+	+	+	+	+	+	8.55	4.34	187	6.77
6, F, 5	No	PPHP	-	+	-	+	+	+	10.1	5.20	36.7	3,62
7, F, 20	No	PHPIb	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.8	9.3	210.4	2.4
8, F, 29	No	PHPIb	-	-	-	-	-	+	6.34	5.01	68.6	5.3
9, F, 25	No	PHPIb	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.73	4.40	239.8	2.8
10, M, 13	No	PHPIb	-	-	-	+	-	-	7.1	7	158	NA
11, F, 21	No	PHPIb	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.58	3.35	162	1.8
12, M, 9	No	PHPIb	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	*	*	
13, M, 14	NA	PHPIb	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.6	3.53	102	11.6
14, M, 9	Yes	PHPIb	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.31	6.05	100.6	3.10
	mother	normal	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.24	3.92	18.5	2.39
	sister	normal	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.4	4.5	33.1	NA
15, M, 32	Yes	PHPIb	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.8	3.2	201	normal

Presence or absence of a symptom is indicated by a + or -, * means that the biochemical values before treatment with 1-hydroxy vitamin D₃ are not known. The normal values for all biochemical parameters are indicated between brackets. ^aAHO features: RF, round face; BM, brachymetacarpus; SCC, subcutaneous calcifications; MR, mental retardation; SS, short stature; O, obesity; F, female; M, Male; NA, not available.

Table 2. Molecular findings and platelet Gs α functional data for all patients

Patient	Clinical Classification	GNAS MUTATION		FUNCTIONAL PLATELET Gs α TEST			
		Gs α function	IC ₅₀ Prostaglandin E1 ng/ml 59.20 $\pm$ 24.49 (n=24)	IC ₅₀ Prostacyclin ng/ml 1.06 $\pm$ 0.37 (n=24)			
1	PHP-Ia	D173N	Hypofunction	366*		2.1*	
2	PHP-Ia	Deletion of 1bp (codon 328)	Hypofunction	> 1000*		> 2.5*	
3	PHP-Ia	Insertion 21bp (codon110)	Hypofunction	> 1000*		> 2.5*	
4	PHP-Ia	codon 24 en 25 are replaced by 14 bp	Hypofunction	520*		2.4*	
5	PHP-Ia	Q35X	Hypofunction	> 1000*		> 2.5*	
mother	NA	Q35X	NA	NA		NA	
6	PPHP	R231C	Hypofunction	490*		1.63*	
7	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in Nesp, XL and 1A	Mild hypofunction	145		1.65	
8	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in Nesp, XL and 1A	Mild hypofunction	140		1.9	
9	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in Nesp, XL and 1A	Mild hypofunction	78	95.3 $\pm$ 41.9	1.85	1.68 $\pm$ 0.16*
10	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in Nesp, XL and 1A	Mild hypofunction	42	(n=6)	1.55	(n=6)
11	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in Nesp, XL and 1A	Mild hypofunction	62		1.6	
12	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in Nesp, XL and 1A	Mild hypofunction	105		1.52	
13	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in 1A, STX16 deletion	Normal	52		0.5	
14	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in 1A, STX16 deletion	Normal	35		0.85	
mother	Mild PHP-Ib	Normal methylation in 1A, STX16 deletion	Normal	34	40.6 $\pm$ 9.8	1.1	0.71 $\pm$ 0.19
sister	normal	Normal methylation, No STX16 deletion	Normal	85	(n=3)	0.9	(n=3)
15	PHP-Ib	Abnormal methylation in 1A, STX16 deletion	Normal	35		0.8	

The numbering of the mutations refers to the codon number as described by Kozasa et al.¹ The concentration of Gs α agonist to inhibit the collagen-induced platelet aggregation by 50 % (IC₅₀) is indicated between brackets for 24 normal controls. A Gs α hypofunction is defined as requiring a significantly higher IC₅₀ value. *P values <.05. NA, not available.

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Chapter 6

A new approach to imprinting mutation detection in *GNAS* by Sequenom EpiTYPER system

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Abstract

Background: Pseudohypoparathyroidism type 1b (PHP-1b) results from abnormal imprinting of *GNAS*. Familial and sporadic forms of PHP-1b have distinct *GNAS* imprinting patterns: familial PHP-1b patients have an exon A/B-only imprinting defect and an intragenic STX16 deletion, whereas sporadic PHP-1b cases have abnormal imprinting of the three differentially methylated regions (DMRs) in *GNAS* without the STX16 deletion. Overall *GNAS* methylation defects have recently been detected in some PHP-1a patients.

Methods: This study describes the first quantitative methylation analysis of multiple CpG sites for three different *GNAS* DMRs using the Sequenom EpiTYPER in 35 controls, 12 PHP-1b patients, 2 PHP-1a patients and 2 patients without parathormone (PTH) resistance but having only hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia.

Results: All patients have *GNAS* methylation defects typically with NESP hypermethylation versus XL and exon A/B hypomethylation while the imprinting of SNURF/SNRPN was normal. PHP-1a patients showed an abnormal methylation in the three DMRs of *GNAS*. For the first time, a marked abnormal *GNAS* methylation was also found in 2 patients without PTH resistance but having hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia.

Conclusions: The Sequenom EpiTYPER proves to be very sensitive in detecting DNA methylation changes. Our analysis also suggests that *GNAS* imprinting defects might be more frequent and diverse than previously thought.

Introduction

The imprinted gene cluster *GNAS* is located on chromosome 20q13 and gives rise to maternal, paternal and biallelic transcripts that all share a common set of downstream exons¹ (**Figure 1**). The classical *GNAS* promoter and first exon are located within a CpG island that is unmethylated with a biallelic expression in most tissues¹⁻⁴ but still with a predominant maternal expression in the renal proximal tubuli, thyroids, gonads and central nervous system.⁵⁻¹⁰ Along the *GNAS* cluster, there exist four alternative first exons. The most upstream one is the exon NESP55, leading to a maternally-derived NESP55 transcript.^{1,5} The exon XL generates a paternally-derived XL α s transcript^{1,5,11} and exon A/B gives rise to a non-coding paternally-derived exon A/B transcript.⁴ Finally, there is also the NESPAS exon 1, which gives rise to a paternally-derived non-coding antisense transcript.¹²⁻¹⁴ The promoters for NESP55, XL α s, exon A/B and NESPAS are all situated within one of three differentially methylated regions (DMRs) present in the *GNAS* cluster. The XL DMR, comprising the NESPAS and XL α s promoters, and the exon A/B DMR are established during gametogenesis and are maternally methylated.^{4,15,16} In contrast, the most upstream paternally methylated DMR that regulates NESP expression is somatic since it is established postfertilization^{15,16,17} and has recently been proposed as additional *GNAS* imprinting control region.¹⁸

Figure 1. *GNAS* structure and expression

Genomic organization of the *STX16* locus and *GNAS* cluster. Features of the paternal and the maternal allele are shown above and below the line, respectively. The arrows show initiation and direction of transcription. The first exons of the protein coding transcripts are shown as black boxes and the first exons of the noncoding transcripts (Nespas and exon A/B) are shown as gray boxes. Differentially methylated regions (DMRs) are shown by + symbols (indication of methylation). The figure is not to scale.

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Heterozygous inactivating mutations in the *GNAS* gene give rise to Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO).¹⁹⁻²¹ Patients carrying maternally inherited *GNAS* mutations develop pseudohypoparathyroidism Type Ia (PHP-Ia), characterized by resistance to multiple stimulatory G protein-coupled hormones (e.g. PTH, TSH, LH, FSH, GHRH)²²⁻²⁸ in addition to obesity and an AHO phenotype. Patients with paternally inherited *GNAS* mutations have an AHO phenotype without hormonal resistance (called pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism or PPHP).^{20-22,29} *GNAS* imprinting defects have been described in pseudohypoparathyroidism Type Ib (PHP-Ib) patients having hormone resistance but no AHO phenotype.^{21,30} PHP-Ib results from hypomethylation of the exon A/B DMR that is believed to be critical for tissue-specific imprinting of *GNAS* in the renal proximal tubules.^{29,30} Familial PHP-Ib is usually caused by deletions within the STX16 gene or overlapping NESPAS exons 3 and 4 and is associated with exon A/B-specific hypomethylation but normal methylation of the other *GNAS* DMRs.³¹⁻³⁷ A broad *GNAS* methylation defect including all DMRs has been reported in sporadic PHP-Ib patients.^{34,36,38} Recent studies have also demonstrated broad *GNAS* methylation defects in PHP-Ia patients with PTH resistance and an AHO phenotype.³⁹⁻⁴¹

GNAS imprinting studies comprise diverse non-quantitative techniques to detect the methylation of single or multiple CpG sites such as Southern analysis using methylation-sensitive restriction digestion^{31,34,36,38,42} and bisulfite DNA treatment followed either by sequencing⁴³⁻⁴⁸ or by methylation-sensitive restriction analysis.^{36,39,40,49,50} Other more recent techniques, such as Multiplex Ligation-dependent Probe Amplification (MS-MLPA),⁵¹ Luminescence Methylation Analysis (LUMA),⁴⁶ SNUPE with IP-RP- HPLC⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ and bisulfite pyrosequencing^{41,46} have also been used to study *GNAS* imprinting. In this study, we for the first time used the Sequenom EpiTYPER⁵²⁻⁵⁴ to quantify the methylation of different CpG sites within all three DMRs of *GNAS* and one DMR of the SNURF/SNRPN cluster in leukocyte DNA from 35 control subjects, 12 PHP-Ib patients, 2 PHP-Ia patients and 2 patients with hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia though normal PTH levels.

Materials and methods

Samples

DNA samples were available from 35 healthy subjects (19 women, 16 men), 14 patients with PTH resistance, 2 patients with hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia but no PTH resistance and 1 Prader-Willi syndrome patient with a proven imprinting methylation defect in the SNURF region. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and/or their legal representatives. The Ethics Committee of the University of Leuven approved the study.

Bisulfite treatment of DNA

Leukocyte DNA (1 µg) was subjected to bisulfite treatment using the MethylDetector™ bisulfite modification kit (Active Motif, Carlsbad CA). Briefly, the conversion reaction was performed in 140µL mixture containing 13 µL of genomic DNA, 7 µL of hydroquinone, 120 µL of conversion buffer. After conversion, DNA was eluted to obtain a final concentration of 20 ng/µL of bisulfite-treated DNA. Control nested PCR reactions were performed on 40 ng of both unconverted and converted DNA to verify the DNA conversion using primers provided with the kit.

Amplicon and primer selection

The CpG-rich sequences for the NESP, XL, exon A/B, SNURF and MKRN3 DMRs were selected using the USCS genome browser (<http://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgGateway>). Primers to amplify different amplicons in the DMRs were designed using the Sequenom EpiDesigner BETA software (<http://www.epidesigner.com>) taken into account amplicon coverage, number of CpGs, fragment size and number of nucleotide repeats in the primer sequence. The characteristics of all amplicons are reported in **Table 1**. Each reverse primer has a T7-promoter tag for in vitro transcription (5'-cagtaatacagactcacta- tagggagaaggct-3') and each forward primer is tagged with a 10mer (5'-aggaagagag-3') to balance melting temperature differences. In order to maximize the coverage of each promoter region, a total of 4 couples of primers were designed along the 3 alternative *GNAS* promoter regions (NESP, XL, exon A/B). Primers sequences are reported in **Table 1 of the supplementary data**.

PCR amplification of amplicons

PCR amplification reactions for each amplicon consisted of 20 ng of bisulfite-treated DNA, 1X of Hot StarBuffer (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany), 25 mM dNTPs (Illustra™

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dNTP Set, GE Healthcare, Little Chalfont, Buckinghamshire, UK), 0.2 U of 5 U/ μ L Hot Star Taq (QIAGEN) and 0.2 μ M of primers (Life Technologies, Carlsbad, CA). Additional MgCl₂ (0.35 μ M, QIAGEN) was added in the reaction to amplify amplicon XL_44. For the NESP and exon A/B amplicons, cycling consisted of preactivation at 94 °C for 15 min and 45 cycles of 94 °C denaturation for 20 s, 56 °C annealing for 30 s, and 72 °C extension for 1 min, finishing with a 72 °C incubation for 3 min. For the XL, SNURF and MKRN3 amplicons cycling consisted of preactivation at 94 °C for 15 min and 45 cycles of 94 °C denaturation for 20 s, 52 °C annealing for 30 s, and 72 °C extension for 1 min, final incubation at 72 °C for 3 min. All PCR amplification products were checked on agarose gels prior to the Sequenom analysis.

Sequenom EpiTYPER MassARRAY methylation and spectra analysis

Sequenom MassARRAY methylation analysis was performed using the MassARRAY Compact System (Sequenom, San Diego, CA). This system is based on mass spectrometry (MS) analysis for qualitative and quantitative detection of DNA methylation using homogeneous MassCLEAVE (hMC) base-specific cleavage and matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight (MALDI-TOF) MS.⁵²⁻⁵⁴ After DNA amplification, a shrimp alkaline phosphatase treatment was performed. PCR products (2 μ l) were used as template for in vitro transcription and RNaseA cleavage for the T-reverse reaction as described in the manufacturer's instructions (Sequenom hMC). Samples were desalted and spotted on a 384-alternatively patch SpectroCHIP (Sequenom) using the MassARRAY nanodispenser (Samsung, Seoul, South Korea), and spectra were analyzed by the MassARRAY Analyzer Compact MALDI-TOF MS (Sequenom).

To achieve optimal quantification within the limitations of the technology, all samples were amplified and analyzed in triplicate as suggested.⁵³ If the triplicate measurements had a standard deviation equal to or greater than 0.10, all data for the sample involved were discarded (removing 8% of measurements).

Spectra were elaborated by the EpiTYPER software v1.0.5 (Sequenom), which provides methylation values for each CpG unit as percentage. Each CpG unit is determined by the EpiTYPER software and can be represented by one or more than one CpG site. Methylation percentages for each CpG unit result from the elaboration of the fragments' masses generated during the RNaseA-specific cleavage and

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calculated as mass signals ratio between the methylated and non-methylated DNA. Peaks with a reference intensity above 2 and overlapping or duplicate CpG units were excluded from the analysis.

Methylation-sensitive restriction analysis

Nested PCRs were performed to amplify the NESP, XL and exon A/B regions using bisulfite-treated DNA as described.³⁶ Amplified PCR products were digested with restriction enzymes that only recognize the non-converted (methylated) DNA sequence: SsiI for NESP, Sall for XL and HinfI for exon A/B (Fermentas, Burlington, Canada). The XL_44 amplicon was digested with SsiI (Fermentas).

Bisulfite sequencing

The XL_44 amplicon was amplified for 5 normal individuals. Amplified fragments were either directly sequenced or subcloned using the TOPO TA Cloning Kit (Life Technologies) to sequence 20 clones. Sequencing was performed using the ABI Prism 310 Genetic Analyzer (Life Technologies).

GNAS molecular analysis

Mutation analysis of the classical *GNAS* gene and the detection of the STX16 and NESP deletion were performed as described.^{31,33,36,38}

Statistical analysis

Intra-assay and interindividual variability were assessed by standard deviation⁵⁵ calculation. Sequenom CpG units with a SD above 10% in the control population were excluded from the analysis. The average of methylation for each amplicon was calculated for all control and patient samples. Shapiro–Wilk test was assessed with the SPSS 12.5 software to study the distributions of methylation among the healthy controls. Statistical analysis was performed comparing each patient's amplicon mean with the distribution of values of the same variable measured in the group of the 35 healthy controls (Z- test, P < 0.05). Values with a Z-score ≤ -2 and $\geq + 2$ were considered hypo- or hypermethylated, respectively.

Results

Mass spectrometric analysis of GNAS methylation in control subjects

We have studied the methylation of multiple CpG sites in different DMRs located in the *GNAS* and SNURF/SNRPN imprinting clusters from 35 normal subjects. PCR

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amplicons used to study the methylation of these DMRs include 33 CpGs for NESP, 24 CpGs for XL, 25 CpGs for exon A/B, 20 CpGs for SNURF and 15 CpGs for MKRN3 (**Table 1**). To date, this is one of the largest quantitative and qualitative *GNAS* methylation studies in normal subjects. Methylation percentages for single CpG units are reported in **Table 2 of Supplementary data**. The overall degree (mean in %) and the variability⁵⁵ of methylation for all CpG units of each amplicon among 35 control subjects are shown in first row of **Table 2**. Healthy controls values were normally distributed (Shapiro–Wilk test, $P < 0.05$). We also compared *GNAS* and SNURF/SNRPN methylation between 19 female and 16 male healthy subjects. No significant quantitative or qualitative differences in methylation were observed between these groups (t-test, $P < 0.05$).

The PCR step was performed in triplicate for each individual sample (both for controls and patients) and for all the amplicons studied as suggested by Coolen et al.⁵³ In general, we found that the standard deviation between replicates fell below 10%. Controversial data have been reported regarding bisulfite treatment influence on DNA methylation analysis,⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ we thus performed a second DNA bisulfite treatment for one control DNA sample followed by Sequenom methylation analysis for amplicon XL_44. The average methylation values of the two independent measurements were however comparable (27% and 24%, respectively).

The mean methylation percentage for all CpG sites of all amplicons does not reach the theoretical 50% value in control subjects (**Table 2**). All the amplicons seem to be hypomethylated with mean values of less than 40%, except the MKNR3 amplicon with hypermethylation and a mean of about 80%. To confirm this observation, we studied the overall methylation of one amplicon via another methylation detection method. The overall methylation of amplicon XL_44 was therefore studied via bisulfite treatment and sequencing of subcloned PCR fragments for 5 normal subjects (**Figure 2**). For each control up to 20 clones were sequenced (**Figure 2**). A mean methylation of 31% was found for the XL_44 amplicon, highly comparable to the 30% detected by the Sequenom EpiTYPER.

Figure 2. Bisulfite subcloning and sequencing of XL₄₄ amplicon in 5 normal individuals

XL₄₄ nucleotide sequence starting from CpG group 6 (U6) of the Sequenom analysis. DNA bisulfite treatment followed by subcloning and sequencing of XL₄₄ PCR fragment in 5 normal controls (crl). Each individual clone is represented by a row; methylated and unmethylated CpG sites are represented by black and white squares, respectively. Up to 20 clones were picked up and sequenced for each sample and the overall methylation percentages for each control are reported at the bottom.

*Mass spectrometric analysis of *GNAS* methylation in PHP patients*

We next studied the methylation pattern of the *GNAS* DMRs in 12 PHP-Ib patients, 2 PHP-Ia patients and 2 patients with hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia but no PTH resistance or AHO features (**Table 2**). Some of these PHP-Ib patients (patients 1-4, 7 and 9-11) were previously described with *GNAS* epigenetic defects after detection with both Southern Blot analysis and methylation-specific restriction analysis following DNA bisulfite treatment.^{36,38} Sequenom EpiTYPER analysis revealed a pronounced methylation defect for all *GNAS* DMRs in PHP-Ib patients 1 to 7, with highly significant NESP hypermethylation and XL and exon A/B hypomethylation. Patients 9 to 12 carried the previously described³² STX16 intragenic deletion and exon A/B hypomethylation (**Table 2**). Using the Sequenom method, very mild methylation defects could also be detected in the NESP and XL DMRs from patients 9 and 12, in contrast to the normal methylation observed when using Southern blot or methylation-sensitive restriction analysis.^{36,38} PHP-Ia patients 13 and 14 with PTH resistance and an AHO phenotype were included in the study because of the absence of mutations in the coding region of *GNAS*. An overall *GNAS* methylation

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defect with NESP hypermethylation and XL and exon A/B hypomethylation could be detected in these PHP-Ia patients (**Table 2**).

Finally, patients 15 and 16 were included in the study because they presented with pronounced hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia though they never showed overt PTH resistance (**Table 2**). Patient 15 was previously found negative for mutations in the calcium sensing receptor (CaSR) gene that could have explained the pronounced low calcium levels. Thyroid hormone (TSH) resistance detected in this patient is probably due to an autoimmune hypothyroidism, a diagnosis further supported by the presence of blood circulating TPO-antibodies. Both patients also had epilepsy. Quantitative methylation studies in these patients revealed some interesting findings. Patient 15 showed a marked overall *GNAS* methylation defect similar to the one observed for PHP-Ib patients. Patient 16 presented with NESP hypermethylation, XL hypomethylation and only a trend for exon A/B hypomethylation.

*Specificity of the *GNAS* methylation defect in PHP patients*

We studied the methylation of the SNURF_3 amplicon located in the SNURF/SNRPN imprinting region on chromosome 15 to confirm the specificity of the methylation defect in the *GNAS* cluster for all PHP patients. A Prader-Willi syndrome patient with a previously proven epigenetic defect in SNURF was used as positive control and showed indeed hypermethylation in this DMR (81% vs $38 \pm 7\%$ in controls, data reported as mean $\pm$ SD). Methylation percentages of the SNURF/ SNRPN DMR were not significantly different between any of the PHP patients and the normal controls (data not shown).

**GNAS* molecular analysis*

Sequencing analysis of the coding *GNAS* region excluded the presence of inactivating mutations in all 16 PHP patients. In addition, to exclude the presence of large chromosomal deletions comprising the *GNAS* gene, we screened all the patients for a known *GNAS* exon 5 SNP (rs7121) at codon 131 and for a known polymorphic pentanucleotide repeat within the exon A/B region⁵⁹. 12 out of 16 patients were heterozygous for at least one of the two polymorphisms studied (**Table 3 of supplementary data**).

Discussion

Over the last decades different techniques have been applied to study DNA methylation. The first methods consist of Southern blot using methylation-sensitive restriction enzymes starting from normal DNA and methylation-sensitive restriction analysis of bisulfite-treated DNA.⁶⁰ These two techniques enable only CpG methylation monitoring in the sequences containing methylation-sensitive restriction sites and detect methylation defects in samples with a considerable percentage of altered methylated DNA. Other methodologies, such as bisulfite subcloning and sequencing techniques, considered gold standard methods to study DNA methylation, allow the methylation detection of multiple CpG sites but are highly time-consuming and may be not representative for the total pool of DNA strands present.^{53,54,60} Lacking sensitivity, those techniques might not be sufficient to study DNA methylation in imprinted genes for which the balance between a methylated and non-methylated allele could be relevant in terms of gene expression regulation and disease development. The Sequenom EpiTYPER methodology combines candidate gene amplification with base-specific cleavage and MALDI-TOF mass spectrometric analysis.⁵²⁻⁵⁴ This methodology is based on the assessment of methylation ratios, between methylated and non-methylated DNA strands, simultaneously across multiple CpG sites, thus providing the necessary quantitative information potentially crucial in the analysis of an imprinted gene or cluster of genes. In this study, we have shown that the Sequenom EpiTYPER indeed provides both qualitative and quantitative methylation information in one single experiment on PCR fragments up to 500 bp.

We first evaluated the Sequenom EpiTYPER technology to study *GNAS* and *SNURF/SNRPN* methylation in a group of normal subjects. The methylation of all studied DMRs in these imprinting clusters did not reach on average the theoretical 50%, as most were hypomethylated ($\pm 30\%$) while only *MKRN3* showed hypermethylation (79%). This was not related to the Sequenom technique as we could confirm the *XL_44* hypomethylation in healthy subjects using bisulfite-treated DNA and methylation-sensitive restriction analysis of PCA amplified fragments (similar for other amplicons; data not shown). DNA methylation detection methods using bisulfite-treated DNA start with a PCR amplification step for which the choice

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of good primer combinations are needed to equally amplify both methylated and non-methylated DNA templates. Primers used in this study and designed with the EpiDesigner software, which is recommended by Sequenom, do not contain any CpG sites in their sequences (**Table 1 of supplementary data**). However, more recent reports^{61,62} have shown that primers with a limited number of CpG sites show a higher sensitivity in the detection of methylated templates than CpG free primers. Despite the latter limitation, the aim of the study was to validate the Sequenom EpiTYPER system as a good method to relatively assess imprinted genes methylation values and allow the clear identification of pathological epigenotypes, such as for *GNAS* methylation abnormalities in PHP-Ib as described in the present report. Also other published quantitative *GNAS* imprinting studies based upon bisulfite-treated DNA with restriction-sensitive digestion showed in normal subjects variability along the cluster but never reaching the expected correspondent 50% methylation.^{63,64} In contrast, Southern blot analysis starting from normal DNA showed a more or less 50% methylated versus non-methylated allele though this is more difficult to quantify. This probably means that the PCR amplification of bisulfite-treated DNA accounts of the observed trend in less than 50% methylation for the *GNAS* DMRs in normal subjects.

The Sequenom EpiTYPER methodology has been used to study DNA methylation in cancer⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷ but this study was the first to quantitatively study a true imprinting disease such as PHP-Ib. PHP-Ib cases have imprinting defects involving the *GNAS* cluster, with the sporadic form characterized by NESP hypermethylation versus XL and exon A/B hypomethylation and the familial form of PHP-Ib with an exon A/B-only hypomethylation in combination with an intragenic deletion in the STX16 locus.^{31,32,35,36} Indeed, our sporadic PHP-Ib patients also showed significant NESP hypermethylation and XL and exon A/B hypomethylation, while the PHP-Ib patients with the STX16 deletion had a clear exon A/B-only methylation defect. But in 2 out of 4 familial PHP-Ib cases, we also observed a very mild NESP hypo- and XL hypermethylation. More familial PHP-Ib cases must be studied to evaluate this further.

PHP-Ia patients have recently also been reported to have *GNAS* methylation defects instead of heterozygous loss of function mutations in *GNAS*³⁹⁻⁴¹. We were able to

identify two additional PHPIa cases with overall epigenetic alterations affecting the *GNAS* cluster (patients 13 and 14). These data, in combination with the cases reported by others,^{39-41,68-70} suggest the need of a less stringent classification of PHP patients, since PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib seem to be more heterogeneous and overlapping than previously thought. In fact, we also detected a rather profound *GNAS* methylation defect in 2 other non-classical PHP-Ib patients having hypocalcemia, hyperphosphatemia but never developing PTH resistance. Clinical heterogeneity of PHP has recently been described in a long-term follow-up study on 8 children.⁷¹ Although we are currently not able to explain the phenotype of patients 15 and 16 by the presence of *GNAS* epigenetic alterations, it might be of utter importance to extend *GNAS* methylation screening to patients having hypocalcemia and/or hyperphosphatemia without multi-hormone resistance.

In conclusion, in this study we performed the first quantitative *GNAS* methylation analysis on multiple CpGs in 35 normal and 16 PHP subjects. We showed that the Sequenom EpiTYPER is a useful technique enabling the accurate methylation screening of imprinted genes. We could show that *GNAS* imprinting defects are more frequent than previously foreseen and not only associated to PTH resistance. Further quantitative DNA methylation studies of normal populations are needed to better characterize imprinting in humans.

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Table 1. Description of all studied amplicons in the imprinted *GNAS* and *SNURF/SNRPM* clusters

name amplicon	chromosome	Start*	End*	Size (bp)	theoretical number of CpGs per amplicon	effective number of CpGs studied with the Sequenom EpiTYPER
NESP_4	20	57415104	57415451	347	32	13
NESP_28	20	57415380	57415837	457	40	20
XL_44	20	57430892	57431270	378	30	24
ExA/B_13	20	57464928	57465295	367	34	25
SNURF_3	15	25199949	25200380	432	25	20
MKRN3_6	15	21362169	21361719	451	19	15

*Nucleotide positions according to the February 2009 human reference sequence (NCBI Build 37.1) produced by the International Human Genome Sequencing Consortium.

Table 2. Methylation profiles and clinical findings in PHP patients

Case	GNAS methylation				STX16 del ^{31,36}	NESP del ^{33,36}	Biochemical values				AHO						Extra features/info
	NESP_4	NESP_28	XL_44	ExA/B_13			PTH (3-40) ng/L	Calcium (8.9-10.5) mg/dl	Phosphate (2.3-4.7) mg/dl	TSH (0.15-4.6) mIU/L	RF	BR	SC	MR	SS	Ob	
1, F	89*	92*	10*	9*	-	-	210.4	4.8	9.3	2.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	patient 7 ³⁶
2, F	89*	92*	6*	8*	-	-	68.6	6.34	5.01	5.3	-	-	-	-	-	+	patient 8 ³⁶
3, F	72*	91*	21*	15*	-	-	239.8	8.73	4.4	2.79	-	-	-	-	-	-	patient 9 ³⁶
4, M	78*	90*	18*	8*	-	-	158	7.1	7	NA	-	-	-	+	-	-	patient 10 ³⁶
5, F	89*	92*	8*	9*	-	ND	435°	7.6	5.5	7.78	-	-	-	-	-	-	
6, M	82*	92*	8*	7*	-	ND	444	7	4.83	3.33	-	-	-	-	-	-	
7 F	68*	65*	12*	12*	-	-	162	9.58	3.35	1.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	patient 11 ³⁶
8, M	78*	88*	20*	19*	-	ND	108	5.5	5.9	3.81 [#]	-	-	-	-	-	-	CVA at young age
9, M	14	38*	39*	10*	+	-	100.6	6.31	6.05	3.10	-	-	-	-	-	-	patient 14 ³⁶
10, M	31	29	38	14*	+	-	201	7.8	3.2	NL	-	-	-	-	-	-	patient 15 ³⁶
11, M	40	34	31	9*	+	-	102	6.6	3.53	11.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	patient 13 ³⁶
12, F	46*	33	28	13*	+	ND	194	5.44	7.3	2.93	-	-	-	-	-	-	
13, M	80*	93*	35	18*	-	ND	482	7.1	5.6	3.73	+	+	-	-	-	-	
14, F	74*	73*	15*	16*	-	ND	90.4	8.9	3.3	NA	+	+	+	+	-	-	epilepsy, ectopic calcifications
15, M	87*	93*	8*	10*	-	ND	11	5.7	4.98	11.2	-	-	-	-	-	+	epilepsy, Casr mutation negative, thyroid auto Ab positive
16, M	63*	49*	17*	21	-	ND	24.7	6.68	5.43	0.85	-	-	-	-	-	-	epilepsy, ectopic calcifications, vit-D deficiency

*: statistical significant vs crls, Z-test, P<0.05. °: reference range of 12-65 pg/ml, #: values obtained under thyroid hormone replacement, ND: Not Determined, NA: Not Available, NL: Normal. RF: round face, BR: brachydactyly, SC: subcutaneous calcifications, MR: mental retardation, SS: short stature, Ob: obesity, CVA: Cerebro-Vascular Accident.

Supplementary Table 1. Primers' sequences used in the Sequenom EpiTYPER study

name	nucleotide sequence
NESP_4_F	5'-AGGAAGAGAGGGAGTTATTTTTGTAGAGTTAGAGGG-3'
NESP_4_R	5'-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTAAAACAACTCAAATCTACCTCCTC-3'
NESP_28_F	5'-AGGAAGAGAGGGTGGGTTTTTTTTGGTTTGTAG-3'
NESP_28_R	5'-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTCCAAATATCCCTAAATCCCC-3'
XL_44_F	5'-AGGAAGAGAGTTTGTGTGTTTGGTTTTTAATTGT-3'
XL_44_R	5'-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTCTAAAATATCCCCTATTCCTATCCC-3'
ExA/B_13_F	5'-AGGAAGAGAGGGGTTATTATGTTGAAGATGGTTAT-3'
ExA/B_13_R	5'-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTACCTCCTCTAACTTCTAACACCT-3'
SNURF_3_F	5'-AGGAAGAGAGGTAATAGTGTGTTGGGGTTTTAGGG-3'
SNURF_3_R	5'-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTACACAACAACAACTCTAAACATTC-3'
MKRN3_6_F	5'-AGGAAGAGAGTGGTAGGGTTGAATTTGGAGTAGTA-3'
MKRN3_6_R	5'-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTCAAACAAAAAACTAAATTAATCCCC-3'

Supplementary Table 2. Sequenom EpiTYPER methylation analysis-CpGunits values in crls and PHP subjects

NESP_4								
	CpG_3	CpG_5.6	CpG_7	CpG_18.19	CpG_23.24	CpG_25	CpG_26.27.28	CpG_29
Crls mean	36	17	20	22	14	27	31	23
SD	10	7	10	9	9	9	9	7
Patients								
1	77	96	85	95	95	91	95	80
2	73	96	93	99	99	79	95	76
3	71	87	76	97	73	36	86	49
4	86	80	78	87	76	72	79	63
5	88	95	94	99	95	79	89	70
6	100	87	87	99	98	53	79	56
7	72	69	68	74	62	70	76	50
8	83	93	83	100	96	55	81	33
9	NA	11	8	17	12	12	23	16
10	51	42	22	24	16	29	38	25
11	47	39	35	40	28	48	46	39
12	52	45	40	45	30	55	52	46
13	92	93	85	100	76	74	84	33
14	80	81	73	82	72	71	81	53
15	83	89	93	99	91	87	89	68
16	79	70	62	56	55	63	65	51

NA: not analyzed

Data reported as average (%) and Standard Deviation (SD) of three replicates for each patient; CpG units with a SD>10% between replicates are excluded from the analysis

Supplementary Table 2. Sequenom EpiTYPER methylation analysis-CpGunits values in crls and PHP subjects

NESP_28														
	CpG_5	CpG_6	CpG_7.8.9.10	CpG_14	CpG_15	CpG_16	CpG_21.22	CpG_23	CpG_24.25	CpG_26.27	CpG_29	CpG_35	CpG_39	CpG_40
Crls mean	13	17	59	16	19	19	16	16	15	17	44	18	47	27
SD	8	7	5	8	9	9	8	4	9	10	10	9	10	7
Patients														
1	97	77	76	92	100	75	98	100	98	99	94	100	95	86
2	100	87	78	99	90	77	100	100	100	99	86	100	82	93
3	96	88	73	98	96	73	99	93	100	100	96	99	87	82
4	98	85	77	95	99	73	99	100	100	98	85	79	80	90
5	100	82	78	98	99	82	98	100	99	95	88	76	96	96
6	100	89	77	100	100	89	96	100	100	91	86	100	88	75
7	74	54	73	NA	75	60	63	45	66	69	69	66	70	62
8	100	85	78	79	100	75	90	100	100	100	91	70	77	84
9	39	38	65	41	24	27	18	22	29	62	58	38	24	40
10	30	28	53	30	21	22	24	13	34	21	40	NA	37	24
11	34	26	53	28	30	26	31	19	32	30	40	43	43	37
12	17	24	57	29	25	19	22	20	27	24	52	26	83	30
13	NA	92	79	98	98	67	100	100	96	99	96	61	97	97
14	78	64	69	76	79	66	77	57	78	74	71	65	86	73
15	100	75	78	100	93	78	100	100	100	100	92	100	100	88
16	42	40	64	38	48	46	46	32	46	40	65	39	82	60

NA: not analyzed

Data reported as average (%) and Standard Deviation (SD) of three replicates for each patient; CpG units with a SD>10% between replicates are excluded from the analysis

Supplementary Table 2. Sequenom EpiTYPER methylation analysis-CpGunits values in crls and PHP subjects

XL_44																	
	CpG_1	CpG_2	CpG_4	CpG_5	CpG_6.7	CpG_8.9	CpG_11	CpG_12	CpG_13	CpG_18.19	CpG_20-22	CpG_23	CpG_25	CpG_26	CpG_27	CpG_28.29	CpG_30
Crls																	
mean	35	21	26	44	42	23	37	16	24	27	20	45	21	22	21	60	26
SD	8	4	5	10	10	4	4	4	4	4	7	9	5	6	6	6	4
Patients																	
1	6	9	5	19	6	3	35	1	6	12	6	11	7	2	1	24	10
2	10	6	6	14	4	2	19	0	6	9	3	3	3	2	2	13	5
3	25	17	18	43	33	10	27	5	14	18	10	35	12	17	14	47	13
4	23	19	12	35	25	12	24	4	11	19	5	31	10	16	5	52	9
5	11	11	16	4	2	5	18	3	8	10	3	9	3	0	2	24	8
6	9	10	9	13	7	3	21	1	6	13	1	8	3	3	3	18	5
7	15	9	13	22	12	7	27	5	13	14	8	10	8	7	6	24	11
8	21	15	22	40	34	12	29	5	12	19	11	37	11	13	8	45	9
9	53	38	39	37	75	43	45	24	28	24	5	64	30	33	29	71	25
10	47	26	NA	33	35	39	39	25	34	34	33	46	33	36	36	67	37
11	30	17	27	41	35	26	39	20	30	28	29	31	26	27	29	54	34
12	34	24	30	17	34	23	34	15	25	27	22	46	24	21	28	58	27
13	31	30	57	16	63	40	50	1	23	38	40	51	38	34	9	48	48
14	14	13	24	10	17	10	23	7	16	16	11	16	9	10	13	31	16
15	10	7	11	23	6	2	22	0	6	13	3	4	3	0	3	15	6
16	18	17	23	8	29	10	26	8	15	18	8	28	11	11	8	47	13

NA: not analyzed

Data reported as average (%) and Standard Deviation (SD) of three replicates for each patient; CpG units with a SD>10% between replicates are excluded from the analysis

Supplementary Table 2. Sequenom EpiTYPER methylation analysis-CpGunits values in crls and PHP subjects

ExA/B_13										
	CpG_1.2.3	CpG_5.6.7.8.9	CpG_10	CpG_17	CpG_18.19.20.21.22	CpG_23	CpG_24	CpG_25.26	CpG_27.28.29	CpG_30.31
Crls mean	27	25	15	37	24	35	34	27	55	20
SD	7	7	5	8	6	7	8	8	4	6
Patients										
1	4	9	2	7	7	8	8	4	32	4
2	2	6	2	11	5	7	6	1	30	3
3	12	9	5	26	10	15	15	1	46	1
4	3	6	3	5	5	7	8	1	36	6
5	3	7	3		5	14	20	3	26	4
6	2	11	5	0	5	5	1	11	31	0
7	5	9	3	17	6	11	12	9	35	7
8	11	11	4	22	16	22	20	9	59	8
9	7	12	3	17	5	9	12	1	27	2
10	6	14	6	14	10	18	9	9	52	4
11	3	8	3	10	5	9	10	2	38	4
12	9	17	3	9	7	20	15	7	42	7
13	7	22	4	18	6	41	8	10	58	5
14	10	12	4	21	11	21	21	8	42	7
15	4	9	3	11	7	12	7	4	38	5
16	11	14	10	25	13	36	23	9	59	6

NA: not analyzed

Data reported as average (%) and Standard Deviation (SD) of three replicates for each patient; CpG units with a SD>10% between replicates are excluded from the analysis

Supplementary Table 3. Exon A/B pentanucleotide repeat pattern and Gs exon 5 single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) rs7121 identified in PHP patients

Case	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
ExA/B	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-
Ex5	C/T	C/T	T/T	C/T	C/T	C/T	C/T	C/T	C/C	C/C	C/T	T/T	T/T	C/T	C/C	T/T

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Chapter 7

***GNAS* imprinting defect in three unrelated patients
with hypoparathyroidism,
characterized by low calcium, high phosphate and
low intact PTH(1-84) levels**

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Submitted

Abstract

CONTEXT. Hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia are commonly observed in hypoparathyroidism and pseudohypoparathyroidism (PHP) as caused by low circulating levels of parathyroid hormone (PTH) or insensitivity to its action in the proximal renal tubules, respectively. The genetic bases for isolated hypoparathyroidism was characterized by mutations in the *CaSR*, *PTH* or *GCM2* genes. Two well established forms of PHP, PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib, are caused by maternally inherited mutations or epigenetic mutations within the *GNAS* locus.

OBJECTIVE. To study *GNAS* methylation in three unrelated patients with hypoparathyroidism.

DESIGN and PATIENTS. Patients had profound hypocalcemia, hyperphosphatemia and low serum PTH levels without a history of surgery, radiation or infiltrative disease in the neck region and negative for *CaSR* mutations. Two patients had severe calcifications of basal ganglia and the third suffered from an epileptic insult and had mild mental retardation. Quantification of methylation in different *GNAS* imprinting regions (NESP, XL and exonA/B) was performed with Sequenom EpiTYPER.

RESULTS. All patients displayed a highly significant NESP hypermethylation versus XL and exonA/B hypomethylation compared to control samples. Their epigenetic defect resembles that of sporadic PHP-Ib patients. The methylation of an imprinting region on another chromosome (SNURF) was normal.

CONCLUSION. This is the first report of *GNAS* imprinting defects in patients with profound hypocalcemia but normal to low PTH levels. This study is important since *GNAS* methylation screening is usually only considered in hypocalcemia cases when PTH levels are increased. Further studies are needed to understand why PTH levels are not elevated in these hypoparathyroidism patients in contrast to PHP-Ib cases with similar epigenetic defects.

Introduction

Parathormone (PTH) is a key regulator of calcium and phosphate levels in both blood and extracellular fluids via activation of the parathormone receptor (PTHR).¹ PTH is also involved in both anabolic and catabolic reactions that control bone formation and reabsorption. Hypocalcemia is a common feature in genetic disorders as hypoparathyroidism and pseudohypoparathyroidism (PHP) (recently reviewed by Bilezikian et al.²).

Isolated hypoparathyroidism is an uncommon endocrine disorder characterized by hypocalcemia, hyperphosphatemia and absent or inappropriately low levels of parathyroid hormone (PTH) in circulation. Sporadic and familial forms of this disease can be caused by mutation in the genes that code for PTH, *GCMB* (glial cells missing homologue B) or *CaSR* (calcium-sensing receptor) but for most patients the genetic factor still remains unknown.³⁻¹¹ In general, the above mentioned gene defects lead to abnormalities of PTH biosynthesis, secretion or are involved in parathyroid gland development or destruction.

In contrast, PHP patients have, high circulating levels of PTH in combination with hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia. These patients present with PTH resistance in the proximal renal tubules. Consistent with end-organ resistance to PTH, rather than deficiency, infusion of biologically active PTH is unable to increase urinary cAMP.¹² PHP is represented in two clinical forms. PHP type Ib (PHP-Ib) include patients with hormone resistance while PHP type Ia (PHP-Ia) is the subtype that comprises patients with hormone resistance and phenotypic features of Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO) such as short stature, brachydactyly, round face, obesity, subcutaneous calcifications and mental problems.¹³ PHP-Ib is caused by epigenetic defects in the *GNAS* cluster with an exon A/B-only methylation defect in autosomal dominant PHP-Ib and an overall methylation defect in sporadic PHP-Ib cases with NESP hypermethylation versus XL and ExonA/B hypomethylation.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ PHP-Ia is generally caused by maternally inherited loss of function mutations in the coding region of *GNAS*.¹⁷ Recent publications however suggest that PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia may be considered as 'extreme variants of the same disease' since some PHP-Ib cases were described having also some mild AHO features.^{18,19} In addition few PHP-

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la patients were recently depicted without *GNAS* coding mutations but having instead an epigenetic defect.^{15,20,21}

The recent reports also underlined the complexity of an imprinted gene such as *GNAS* and its related phenotypes thus far all characterized by hypocalcemia due to PTH resistance. This raised the question whether *GNAS* epigenetic defects could also account for other types of hypocalcemia such as in patients suffering from hypoparathyroidism. We here describe three patients with profound hypocalcemia, hyperphosphatemia and low serum PTH levels without a history of surgery, radiation or infiltrative disease in the neck region, and for which *CaSR* mutations were excluded. *GNAS* methylation was studied using the Sequenom EpiTyper that we have previously shown to be a highly sensitive technique for the quantification of methylation changes in PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia cases.¹⁵

Materials and Methods

*Quantification of *GNAS* methylation*

GNAS methylation status was assessed via Sequenom EpiTYPER analysis of leukocyte DNA as described.¹⁵ We studied a total of 33 CpGs in the NESP, 24 CpGs in the XL, 25 CpGs in the ExonA/B and 20 CpGs in the *SNURF/SNRPN* DMRs. Statistical analysis was performed as described.¹⁵ All Sequenom amplicons were in addition amplified and further digested with *Ssi I* (*Aci I*) enzyme (Fermentas).

Platelet aggregation-inhibition test

The platelet aggregation-inhibition test was performed on platelet rich plasma (PRP) as described.¹⁴

**GNAS* genetic screening*

Mutation analysis of the classical *GNAS* gene and the detection of the STX16 deletion were performed as described.^{14,22,23} To rule out the presence of other deletions in the upstream *GNAS* region we performed genotyping by PCR and direct sequencing of six polymorphic sites within the NESP55 region (rs 1800900-1800905) and of a known polymorphic pentanucleotide repeat within the ExonA/B region.²⁴ Primer pairs and conditions used for the specific amplification of these regions are available on request.

Results

Clinical description of hypoparathyroidism patients

The biochemical analysis for three patients with hypocalcemia is shown in **Table 1**. For the three patients, there was no familial history of calcium problems or epilepsy, and other causes of hypocalcemia were excluded (such as hypoparathyroidism caused by previous neck surgery or radiation or infiltrative parathyroid diseases, hypercalciuric hypocalcemia, magnesium deficiency, hypoalbuminemia and pancreatitis). However, two of the three patients (patients 2 and 3) were also vitamin D deficient at diagnosis. None of the three patients presented with a clinical phenotype of AHO and had normal TSH levels. Kidney function was normal in all three cases, as was bone densitometric analysis. All serum PTH measurements were performed with the full PTH (1-84) in house assay as described.²⁵

The first patient (patient 1) was diagnosed at age 24. He had no relevant medical history. He presented with muscle weakness without paresthesia or muscle spasms, and had no other clinical abnormalities. Biochemistry revealed hypoparathyroidism (**Table 1**). At CT scan of the brain symmetrical calcifications of the basal ganglia and thalamus were observed, as well as subcortical calcifications in the brain and the cerebellum (**Figure 1a**). He was treated with alfacalcidol and calcium supplements. Under this therapy the symptoms resolved and the calcium/phosphate balance normalized.

The second patient (patient 2) presented at age 29 with symptoms of fatigue and diffuse muscle weakness without paresthesia. He has been known with mild mental retardation, and at the age of 10 years he suffered an epileptic insult. Clinical examination revealed no abnormal signs, but biochemical analysis showed hypoparathyroidism (**table 1**) and autoimmune hypothyroidism. He also had a mild vitamin D deficiency, but as hyperphosphatemia and inadequately low PTH levels were present, hypoparathyroidism was considered the major cause of the hypocalcemia. Biochemical screening for other autoimmune diseases, including Addison's disease, was negative. After treatment with alfacalcidol, calcium supplements and levothyroxin, calcium/phosphate and thyroid hormone levels normalized, and he became free of symptoms.

The last patient (patient 3) was diagnosed at age 66 with severe hypocalcemia,

hyperphosphatemia, low vitamin D levels and inadequately low PTH levels when he was referred to the emergency department due to an episode of unconsciousness and urine loss. He had a history of arterial hypertension and hypercholesterolemia. CT and MRI scan of the brain excluded recent ischemia or bleeding, but revealed pronounced calcifications in the basal ganglia and cerebellum (**Figure 1b**). The diagnosis of hypocalcemia due to combined vitamin D deficiency and partial hypoparathyroidism (based on the absence of high PTH levels) was made. Upon treatment with colecalciferol and calcium supplements, calcium and phosphate levels normalized.

*Methylation and genetic analysis of the *GNAS* cluster*

DNA methylation in the three DMRs of *GNAS* (NESP, XL and ExonA/B) and the DMR of the imprinted gene SNURF on chromosome 15 was studied by the Sequenom EpiTYPER as done before for PHP1b patients.¹⁵ The Sequenom analysis for the different *GNAS* DMRs was performed in duplicate for the hypoparathyroidism patients and their methylation values were compared to the previously described sporadic (n=8) and familial (n=4) PHP-1b patients (**Table 1**). For the familial PHP-1b cases, one novel patient (patient 4) was included in the present data as this patient had hypocalcemia with PTH resistance and inherited the STX16 deletion from his phenotypically normal mother (patient clinical data are presented in the **supplementary Table 1**). The three hypoparathyroidism patients displayed highly significant NESP hypermethylation in both NESP amplicons (NESP_4 and NESP_28). A significant XL and ExonA/B hypomethylation could also be observed for the three cases compared to the group of normal control subjects. The methylation values were also compared to PHP-1b cases and were in the same range as described for sporadic PHP-1b cases. No abnormalities were found for the SNURF DMR indicating a *GNAS*-specific imprinting defect. The hypoparathyroidism patients were negative for the STX16 deletion. The epigenetic defect could also be confirmed via PCR amplification of the same regions on bisulphite-treated DNA and subsequent enzymatic restriction with the methylation-specific enzyme *SsiI* (*Acil*) (**supplementary Figure 1**).

The platelet aggregation-inhibition test showed a normal Gs activity for patients 2 and 3 while platelets from patient 1 were not tested (data not shown). The *GNAS*

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gene was also screened for coding mutation but except for known intronic SNPs (rs 3730170 detected for patients 1 and rs 234628 for patients 2 and 3) no abnormalities were found. In addition NESP rs 1800904 was detected in patients 1 and 3 while patient 2 presented with the penta ExonA/B SNP. These data excluded the presence of *GNAS* uniparental disomy in the three patients.

Discussion

PHP patients with hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia as a consequence of resistance to PTH action, can be subclassified into PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib depending on the presence or absence of AHO features and multihormone resistance. PHP-Ia is mainly caused by heterozygous inactivating *GNAS* mutations on the maternal allele while PHP-Ib results from an epigenetic *GNAS* defect. Recent reports point to an overlap between these PHP forms as some PHP-Ia patients were described with a similar methylation defect including all *GNAS* DMRs as found for sporadic PHP-Ib cases.^{15,20,21} This study now expands this overall *GNAS* epigenetic disease spectrum with at least three unrelated patients that obtained a clinical diagnosis of hypoparathyroidism instead of PHP as they have hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia but inappropriate low instead of elevated levels of PTH. No differences in the overall quantification of DNA methylation for each amplicon in the NESP, XL or ExonA/B DMRs could be observed between 8 sporadic PHP-Ib cases and these three hypoparathyroidism patients. Differences could also not be detected for separate CpGs within each amplicon between these groups. The same holds true between PHP-Ia cases with an epigenetic defect and sporadic PHP-Ib cases. Probably larger groups of patients need to be studied to unravel differences between the degree of DNA methylation and the clinical phenotype. At this moment it is also not clear what the underlying genetic defect is for these methylation abnormalities in any of the patients having an overall epigenetic *GNAS* defect but this might be different in sporadic PHP-Ib, PHP-Ia and hypoparathyroidism. It is only known at this moment that deletions in STX16 or NESP/Nespas region are causative for an ExonA/B-only methylation defect in familial PHP-Ib when present on the maternal allele.^{23,26-28}

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It is not clear why PTH levels remains normal in these hypoparathyroidism patients. In hypoparathyroidism and PHP, cAMP excretion by the kidney is low and renal reabsorption of phosphate is high. But patients with hypoparathyroidism show a vigorous increase of urinary cAMP excretion when given PTH parenterally (referred to as the Ellsworth-Howard test), while PHP patients present with ablated or absent response to exogenous PTH, consistent with their PTH resistance in the renal proximal tubules. Also in PHP, urinary excretion of calcium is lower than in hypoparathyroidism because renal resistance to PTH action is restricted to the proximal tubule while the elevated PTH remains active in the distal renal tubules, where it promotes calcium reabsorption. Therefore, bone alkaline phosphatase activity is normal and bone reabsorption is diminished in hypoparathyroidism, while PHP cases are usually characterized by an increased bone turnover and thus an increased alkaline phosphatase activity. Further studies are needed to understand the biochemical differences in PTH levels between sporadic PHP-Ib cases and hypoparathyroidism cases with a similar *GNAS* epigenetic defect.

In conclusion, we here expand the *GNAS* phenotypic spectrum that is caused by an overall epigenetic *GNAS* defects with hypoparathyroidism in addition to sporadic PHP-Ib and some PHP-Ia cases. Patients with idiopathic hypoparathyroidism that don't have mutations in the *CaSR*, *PTH* or *GCM2* genes should be screened for *GNAS* methylation defects.

Acknowledgments

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Figure 1. Brain CT scans of patients 1 (a) and 3 (b)

Table 1. Biochemistry of hypocalcemia and Sequenom *GNAS* and SNURF methylation values in hypoparathyroidism patients

Case	Biochemistry of hypocalcemia					Methylation values (%)				
	Ca (mg/dl)	P (mg/dl)	PTH 1-84 (ng/L)★	25-OHD3 (µg/L)	Ur Ca (mg/g creat)	NESP_4	NESP_28	XL_44	ExonA/B_13	SNURF
	nl range	nl range	nl range	nl range		23±7 (mean±SD)	27±5 (mean±SD)	29±4 (mean±SD)	32±7 (mean±SD)	38±7 (mean±SD)
	8.6-10.3	2.3-4.7	3.0-40.0	>20		n=48	n=41	n=48	n=47	n=35
1	6.03	6.34	16.9	37.2	11.5	78*	79*	19±2* ‡	10±4* ‡	31
	9.41w	4.71w	11.1w	35.3w	79.9w					
2	5.7	4.98	11.3	17.7	12.4	81±9* ‡	80±8* ‡	8±0* ‡	11±1* ‡	31
	8.17w	4.12w	16.0w	13.0w	NDw					
3	6.68	5.43	34.0	10.0	23	63±0* ‡	53±10* ‡	20±4* ‡	17±6* ‡	39
	8.88°	2.99°	39.0°	42.0°	ND°					
PHPIb sporadic n=8						81±8*	88±9*	13±6*	11±4*	32±4
PHPIb familial n=5						31±13	32±5	34±5	11±2*	31±3

* vs. Crls, Z-test, p<0.05

‡ mean±SD of 2 independent replicates

w values after treatment with R/alfacalcidol+Ca

° values after treatment with R/colecalciferol+Ca

★ measured by an in house assay as described²⁵

Supplementary Figure 1. NESP, XL and exon A/B imprinting in hypoparathyroidism patients via bisulfite DNA amplification and digestion with *Ssi I* (*Aci I*)

NESP_4 (a), NESP_28 (b), XL_44 (c) and exon A/B_13 (d) digestion with *Ssi I* (*Aci I*) of bisulfite-treated DNA from patients 1 (1) and 2 (2), from a classical sporadic PHP-Ib patient (Ib) and three normal controls (crI).

Supplementary Table 1. Biochemistry of hypocalcemia and PTH resistance in a classical autosomal dominant PHP-1b case

Case	Biochemistry of hypocalcemia				
	Ca (mg/dl)	P (mg/dl)	PTH 1-84 (ng/L)	25-OHD3 (µg/L)	Ur Ca (mg/g creat)
	nl range	nl range	nl range	nl range	
	8.6-10.3	2.3-4.7	3.0-40.0	>20	
4 at diagnosis	6.78	5.63	413	22.1	7.5
after treatment with R/alfacalcidol+Ca	8.53	4.26	404	ND	ND

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Chapter 8

No evidence for *GNAS* Copy Number Variants in patients with features of Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy and abnormal platelet Gs activity

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Submitted

Abstract

Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO) is characterized by short stature, round face, calcifications, obesity, brachydactyly and mental problems. AHO without hormone resistance is called pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism (PPHP), a rare clinical condition difficult to diagnose since most features are common and highly variable. PPHP can be caused by paternally inherited loss of function mutations in the *GNAS* coding region. We here hypothesized that copy number variants (CNVs) in *GNAS* could also cause PPHP. We have studied 256 patients with AHO features but no other clinical diagnosis. Their platelet Gs activity was determined via the aggregation-inhibition test showing Gs hypo- or hyperfunction in 24 and 15 % of the patients, respectively. Multiplex Amplicon Quantification (MAQ) for CNVs screening was developed for the 20q13.3 region including *GNAS* and potential long-range imprinting control elements such as STX16 to rapidly screen all patients. This is the first large-scale *GNAS* CNV study in patients with common AHO features but no CNVs were detected. In conclusion, CNVs in the *GNAS* region are not likely to cause an AHO phenotype with or without abnormal platelet Gs activity. Future studies will be undertaken to find out whether AHO patients with abnormal Gs function are characterized by *GNAS* coding or methylation defects.

GNAS is an imprinted region that gives rise to several transcripts, antisense transcripts and noncoding RNAs, including transcription of the alpha subunit of the stimulatory G protein ($G\alpha$), which interacts with adenylyl cyclase to generate cAMP.¹ Several phenotypes resulting from genetic and epigenetic abnormalities of the *GNAS* region have been described so far. $G\alpha$ loss of function mutations cause Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO), a spectrum of phenotypic features including short stature, obesity, round face, brachydactyly, subcutaneous ossifications and mental/behavioral abnormalities.¹ Patients with maternal inheritance of $G\alpha$ mutations often develop multi-hormone resistance, and are therefore referred to pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ia (PHP-Ia), while pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ib (PHP-Ib) patients, despite presenting also with hormone resistance, do not show overt AHO features. PHP-Ib patients display methylation abnormalities in the *GNAS* differentially methylated regions (DMRs) such as NESP hypermethylation versus XL/Nespas and Exon A/B hypomethylation¹. Familial cases of PHP-Ib present with Exon A/B-only hypomethylation^{2,3} that appears to be caused by maternally inherited deletions affecting imprinting control centers in either the STX16 gene^{4,5} or the NESP55/NESPAS region.^{6,7} Paternal $G\alpha$ inactivating mutations lead to pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism (PPHP).^{1,8,9} This clinical condition is characterized by highly variable AHO features but no hormone resistance.^{1,9,10} Clinical diagnosis of those patients is particularly difficult because of their phenotypic heterogeneity and the absence of a biochemical marker that could be used such as PTH and calcium levels that are determined to diagnose PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib. A firm clinical diagnosis of PPHP may therefore be hard to make since AHO features can also be nonspecific. Additional diagnostic support for PPHP comes from Gs functional assays. Such tests typically involve the use of the patients' erythrocytes or platelets and have been shown to be able to support the diagnosis of PHP-Ia, some cases of PHP-Ib and also PPHP.¹¹⁻¹³ However, the genotype-Gs function correlation is not always respected since a number of patients have been found to have an AHO phenotype, a Gs loss of function though $G\alpha$ coding mutations could not be detected.¹² To our knowledge, chromosomal or copy number variants (CNVs) in the *GNAS* cluster were not studied in detail in PPHP patients as cause of their AHO phenotype. Chromosome 20q paternal uniparental isodisomy (UPD) has also been

described as possible cause of PHP-Ib¹⁴⁻¹⁶ but maternal uniparental isodisomy has never been described for PPHP patients.

We here hypothesize that CNVs in the *GNAS* locus could account for an AHO phenotype in PPHP patients. To test this hypothesis, we have selected 256 patients with AHO features, no hormone resistance and no other clinical diagnosis. In all patients we have studied platelet Gs activity as described earlier using the platelet aggregation-inhibition test.¹⁷ All functional platelet and genetic studies were approved by our institutional Ethics Committee. This test is based on the inhibition of platelet aggregation by cAMP produced by Gs agonists such as prostaglandin E1 or the stable prostacyclin analog Iloprost and proved to be reliable in the identification of both Gs α hypo- or hyperfunction.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ For 24 and 15% of the 256 patients, we could identify a Gs hypo- or hyperfunction, respectively (**Table 1**).

To be able to rapidly screen for CNVs in a large sample set of 256 patients, we have developed and optimized a Multiplex Amplicon Quantification (MAQ) assay²⁰ for the assessment of CNVs in the 20q13.3 region including the complete *GNAS* locus with all alternative transcripts and the STX16 region that comprises a *GNAS* imprinting control region. The MAQ methodology consists of a multiplex PCR amplification of eighteen *GNAS* target amplicons and nine reference amplicons (randomly located on different chromosomes) (references of amplicons are in **supplementary Table 1**) (**Figure 1**), followed by fragment analysis on an ABI 3730 DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems).²⁰ The reaction was carried on 50ng genomic DNA by using optimized reaction conditions. The comparison of normalized peak areas between a patient and control individuals results in a dosage quotient (DQ) of the target amplicon. DQs were calculated using the MAQ-S software package (www.multiplicom.com). The complete *GNAS* MAQ array was performed in duplicate. No statistical differences were observed in *GNAS* CNVs in all the 256 patients studied, irrespectively of their loss, gain or normal platelet Gs function. The latter suggests that CNVs are not the cause in the present subset of patients neither for the AHO phenotype nor for the Gs abnormal function in their platelets.

In conclusion, we here have optimized the first rapid large-scale screening method for *GNAS* CNVs and have applied it to a population of 256 patients with AHO features but no endocrinopathy with or without abnormal platelet Gs function. Future studies

will include the *GNAS* sequencing and methylation analysis of all PPHP patients with abnormal platelet Gs function.

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Figure 1. MAQ Amplicons distribution along the *GNAS* chromosomal region

Chromosome 20q13 region selected for the MAQ assay. The region comprises the STX16 locus, the *GNAS* cluster and downstream genes TH1L and TUBB1. Amplicons designed for the MAQ assay are depicted as small vertical black bars (NCBI36/hg18).

Table 1. The aggregation-inhibition test to study platelet Gs activity

	Prostin 250 ng/mL			Prostin 1000 ng/mL			Iloprost 2,5 ng/mL		
	Amplitude of aggregation (%) **			Amplitude of aggregation (%) **			Amplitude of aggregation (%) **		
	average	SD	p-value	average	SD	p-value	average	SD	p-value
Unrelated control subjects (n = 70)	22,94	16,94		12,71	9,81		18,09	19,84	
AHO patients with Gs hypofunction (n = 63)	40,25	24,9	< 0,001*	17,74	10,92	0,006*	29,67	23,5	< 0,003*
AHO patients with Gs hyperfunction (n = 40)	14,80	9,7	< 0,001*	9,44	5,17	0,025*	9,7	4,3	0,001*

* vs. controls, 2-tailed unpaired t-test

**Platelets are stimulated with 2 microg/ml Horm collagen 1 minute after preincubation with Gs agonists prostaglandin E1 (Prostin) or prostacyclin (Iloprost) for the indicated concentration. The aggregation-inhibition test is fully described in ¹⁸ and ¹⁷.

Supplementary Table 1. MAQ amplicons localization in the *GNAS* region (NCBI36/hg18)

name	genomic localization	
amp001	56654061	56654337
amp002	56674372	56674458
amp003	56676467	56676604
amp004	56699604	56699801
amp005	56750957	56751064
amp006	56767315	56767693
amp007	56792450	56792572
amp008	56814785	56814938
amp009	56841881	56842088
amp010	56865673	56865911
amp011	56881450	56881565
amp012	56886940	56887258
amp013	56909006	56909226
amp014	56930371	56930620
amp015	56956524	56956616
amp016	56976695	56976871
amp017	57000817	57001003
amp018	57022775	57022874

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Chapter 9

Imprinting defect in patients with Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy and platelet Gs hypofunction

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In prepara

Abstract

Endocrinopathies in patients with hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia that share resistance to parathyroid hormone (PTH) are named pseudohypoparathyroidism (PHP). Most PHP types are caused by defects in *GNAS*, an imprinted gene locus consisting of maternal, paternal and biallelic transcripts. PHP-Ib patients have isolated PTH resistance and *GNAS* epigenetic defects while PHP-Ia cases presents with hormonal resistance and characteristic physical features such as mental problems, brachydactyly, shortness, round face and subcutaneous ossifications, jointly termed as having Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO) due to maternally inherited *GNAS* mutations or similar epigenetic defects as for PHP-Ib. PPHP patients have AHO without hormone resistance and paternally inherited *GNAS* mutations. We here describe 16 PPHP patients and 1 patient with Progressive Osseous Heteroplasia (POH) with platelet hypofunction but having a normal *GNAS* coding region. The methylation for the three differentially methylated *GNAS* regions was quantified with the Sequenome EpiTYPER. These patients showed significant hypermethylation of XL (36 ± 3 vs. $29\pm 3\%$; T-test, $p<0.001$). Since some AHO features are often present in other imprinting disorders, the of IGF2, H19, SNURF and GRB10 was also quantified. Surprisingly, significant IGF2 hypermethylation (20 ± 10 vs. $14\pm 7\%$; T-test, $p<0.05$) and SNURF hypomethylation (23 ± 6 vs. $32\pm 6\%$; T-test, $p<0.001$) was found in PPHP cases versus controls, while H19 and GRB10 were normally methylated. This is the first report of an epigenetic defect in PPHP and POH but additional studies in more patients are needed to make a correlation between the epigenotype en their clinical phenotype.

Introduction

Heterozygous inactivating mutations affecting the *GNAS* gene have been reported to cause Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO, MIM 300800), a complex and broad phenotype mostly characterized by short stature, obesity, round face, subcutaneous calcifications, brachydactyly and cognitive impairment.²⁻⁵ Patients carrying *GNAS* loss-of-function mutations on maternally inherited alleles have pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ia (PHP-Ia, MIM 103580) that is characterized by AHO and resistance to multiple stimulatory G protein-coupled hormones (e.g. PTH, TSH, LH, FSH, GHRH),⁶⁻¹¹ while patients with paternally inherited *GNAS* mutations are reported as having only AHO features or pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism (PPHP).^{3-5,12} Progressive Osseous Heteroplasia (POH, MIM 166350) describes a severe disease characterized by ectopic bone formation that affects not only the subcutis, but also the skeletal muscle and the deep connective tissue. POH is considered as an extreme variant of PPHP and is also caused by paternally inherited *GNAS* inactivating mutations.¹³ *GNAS* imprinting defects have extensively been described in pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ib (PHP-Ib, MIM 623233) patients^{4,14} with hormone resistance to PTH and TSH only and having no AHO. However, recent studies have shown the presence of epigenetic *GNAS* defects in PHP-Ia patients without mutations in the *GNAS* coding region.¹⁵⁻¹⁹ These findings suggest a reclassification of PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib patients as extreme ends of one heterogeneous group of *GNAS* (epi)genetic defects. Both PHP-Ia and PPHP patients are referred in the literature as having Gs loss of function as mostly determined in isolated erythrocyte membranes or in platelets.²⁰⁻²² Despite the fact that large-scale studies showed an association between AHO phenotype and loss of Gs activity,^{20,23-25} only a small number of PPHP subjects have inactivating *GNAS* mutations. The severity of the AHO phenotype varies greatly between patients, and some patients have only few features of the syndrome.

Some clinical characteristics of AHO are also reported in other imprinting syndromes (Silver-Russell/Beckwith-Wiedemann and Prader-Willi/Angelman syndromes). To support the common soil of imprinting disorders, an 'imprinting gene' network that regulates embryonic growth and differentiation dependent on Zac-1 regulation has been identified.²⁶ A subset of imprinting genes have been found to influence growth

progression via coordination of the glucose-regulated metabolism.²⁷ Among those genes, together with *GNAS* also *IGF2* and *H19* have been described to play a causative role on embryonic growth defects. DNA methylation defects involving imprinting control region 1 (ICR1) of the *IGF2/H19* locus for which methylation abnormalities result in two growth disorders with opposite phenotypes: the overgrowth disorder Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome²⁸ with maternal *H19-ICR1* hypermethylation and the growth retardation disorder Silver–Russell syndrome²⁹ with paternal *H19-ICR1* loss of methylation. Prader-Willi and Angelman syndromes³⁰ are distinct neurodevelopmental disorders that are associated with the deletion of the chromosomal 15q11-13 region, loss of imprinting or uniparental disomy of chromosome 15. The *SNURF/SNRPN* region is hypermethylated in some Prader-Willi syndrome patients.

We here study the methylation of *GNAS* (*NESP/XL* and *ExonA/B*), *IGF2/H19*, *SNURF* and *GRB10* in 17 patients with some typical AHO features (mainly growth retardation and brachydactyly) and loss of platelet Gs function but no *GNAS* coding mutations.

Materials and Methods

Patients description

Patients were selected based on having AHO features, mostly with severe short stature, mental retardation or behavioural problems, clinodactily or short metacarpals. Few patients also showed obesity and none of them presented with subcutaneous calcifications. One patient (patient 5) showed heterotopic calcifications, and was diagnosed with Progressive Osseous Heteroplasia.¹³ Other clinical (mainly bone) characteristics were also present and are reported in **Table 1**. None of the patients had abnormal PTH, TSH or calcium values.

Table 1. Clinical characteristics and platelet Gs test in PPHP patients

Case	Birth weight	Height Z-score	Brachydactily		other bone diseases	Mental/ behavioral problems	SC	Ob	RF	others	Ca, PTH and TSH levels	GS test	
			MC IV, V	MT II, V								Prostin IC50 (ng/mL) (n=24)	Iloprost IC50 (ng/mL) (n=24)
1	3,1	-1,56	MC IV	MT V	enchondroma	YES [^]	NO	NO	NO	café-au-lait spots	Normal	ND	ND
2	3,1	-1,5	MC IV, V	MT II, V	No	NO	NO	YES		/	Normal	ND	ND
3	NA	-0,73	MC V	-	clinodactily	YES	NO	NO	YES	epilepsy, cryptorchidism, spastic paraparesis, strabism, café-au-lait spots, macrocephalie	Normal	ND	ND
4	2,45	-2,59	MC II, IV	MT I	broad thumbs, clinodactily	YES [^]	NO	NO	YES	strabism, coarctatio aortae	Normal	ND	ND
5	adopted	-2,89	MC III, IV	MT III	synostosis, heterotopic calcifications	YES	NO	NO	YES	migraine, praecox pubertas	Normal	330**	>3**
6	2,03*	-3.6	MC IV	-	scoliosis	YES	NO	NO	NO	/	Normal	150**	2.5**
7	3,24	-2.6	-	-	short fingers clinodactily, broad thumbs, red bone age	YES	NO	NO	NO	prepubertas	Normal	122**	1.94**
8	2,96	-3.3	-	-	Retarded bone age, Frontal bossing Tooth agenesis	NO	NO	NO	NO	/	Normal	367**	>3**
9	3,35	-3.2	-	-	broad hands	NO	NO	NO	NO	/	Normal	144**	2.06**
10	3,4	-2.3	-	-	non fusion of sacral vertebrae S1/S2, broad thumbs	NO	YES	NO	NO	/	Normal	433**	1.25
11	1,96*	-2.6	-	-	clinodactily, retarded bone age	NO	NO	NO	NO	/	Normal	322**	>3**
12	3,64	-2.8	MC I, IV, V	MT I	osteochondroma	NO	NO	NO	NO	/	Normal	410**	1.95**
13	2,63*	-3.4	MC III uni, IV, V	MT I	exostose, osteochondroma, broad thumbs	YES	NO	NO	NO	synophris	Normal	250**	>2,5**
14	3,16	-3.2	MC IV, V	-	broad thumbs	YES	NO	NO	YES	synophris	Normal	>1000**	2.45**
15		-3.4	-	-	retarded bone age, broad hands	NO	NO	NO	NO	/	Normal	100**	1.94**
16	3,05	-1,16	MC IV, V	normal	no	NO	NO	YES	YES	orchidopexy, coarctatio	Normal	125**	1.55**
17	3,95	0.52	normal	normal	Small and broad hands	YES	NO	YES	YES	eccchymoses, hirsutism, macrocephalie, praecox pubertas	Normal	305**	>2.5**

*IUGR; [^]Gilles de la Tourette; [°]ADHD; SC: subcutaneous calcifications; Ob: obesity; RF: round face; NA: not available

** vs. crls, p<0.05 The concentration of Gs α agonist to inhibit the collagen-induced platelet aggregation by 50 % (IC₅₀) is indicated between brackets for 24 normal controls. A Gs α hypofunction is defined as requiring a significantly higher IC₅₀ value.

Functional platelet Gs pathway test

Platelet aggregation-inhibition test was performed as described.³¹⁻³⁴ Samples were processed within 3 hours after blood drawing. Different concentrations of a Gs agonist being prostaglandin E₁ (PGE₁, Prostin®; 0-1 µg/ml; Pfizer Inc., NY, USA) or the stable prostacyclin analogue Iloprost (Ilomedine® 0-5 ng/ml; Bayer Schering Pharma AG, Berlin, Germany) were added one minute prior to induction of aggregation with collagen (2 µg/ml). The 50% inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) was evaluated for each Gs agonist from the patient's response curve and compared to the IC₅₀ for the same agonist on platelets of a control person, performed simultaneously.

Genetic analysis of GNAS

DNA was extracted from leukocytes from all patients studied. Exons 1-13 of *GNAS* were amplified and sequenced using conditions previously described.²² The presence of STX16 deletions was investigated as described.^{22,35-37} To rule out the presence of other deletions in the upstream *GNAS* region we performed SNP genotyping by PCR and direct sequencing of six polymorphic sites within the NESP55 region (rs 1800900, rs 1800901, rs 1800902, rs 1800903, rs 1800904, and rs 1800905) and of a known polymorphic pentanucleotide repeat within the exon A/B region.³⁸

GNAS, IGF2/ICR1_H19, SNURF and GRB10 methylation analysis

Genomic DNA (1ug) was used for bisulfite treatment with the MethylDetector™ bisulfite modification kit (Active Motif, Carlsbad CA) as described.¹⁹

NESP, XL, Exon A/B and SNURF methylation was studied via Sequenom EpiTYPER technology using primers and conditions already reported.¹⁹ New amplicons to study IGF2, ICR1 of H19 and GRB10 regions were designed using the Sequenom EpiDesigner software. Primers and amplicons characteristics are reported in **Tables 2 and 3**. All PCR amplifications were performed in triplicate. When the triplicate measurements had a SD equal to or greater than 0.10, all data for the sample involved were discarded (removing 8% of measurements). Sequenom peaks with reference intensity above 2, overlapping and duplicate units were excluded from the analysis.

Table 2. Primers used in the Sequenom study to amplify IGF2, ICR1/H19 and GRB10 regions

primer's name	nucleotide sequence
IGF2_F	5`-aggaagagagGTTGGAGGGTTTTAAAGTGGGG-3`
IGF2_R	5`-cagtaatacgactcactatagggagaaggctCAACTCAAATCCTACCTACATAA-3`
ICR1/H19_4_F	5`-aggaagagagTAGTTTAAGTTTTTTTTGGATGGGG-3`
ICR1/H19_4_R	5`-cagtaatacgactcactatagggagaaggctAAAACAACAATAACACTCCCAACTC-3`
ICR1/H19_14_F	5`-aggaagagagTTTGGTAGGTTTAAGAGTTTAGGGG-3`
ICR1/H19_14_R	5`-cagtaatacgactcactatagggagaaggctAAAACCCTACAAAAAAATCTCACC-3`
GRB10_F	5`-aggaagagagGTTTAAATGGGATTTTATTTGTTT-3`
GRB10_R	5`-cagtaatacgactcactatagggagaaggctAATCCCTAATTCTCATAACAACCCT-3`

Table 3: Characteristics of IGF2, ICR1/H19 and GRB10 amplicons used in the Sequenom study

name amplicon	chromosome	start*	end*	size (bp)	theoretical number of CpGs per amplicon	effective number of GpCs studied via the Sequenom EpiTYPER
IGF2	11	2107419	2107915	496	45	30
ICR1/H19_4	11	1977707	1978166	459	19	15
ICR1/H19_14	11	1978989	1979398	409	17	10
GRB10	7	50818156	50818535	379	20	18

* Nucleotide positions according to the March 2006 human reference sequence (NCBI Build 36/hg18.1) produced by the International Human Genome Sequencing Consortium.

Statistical analysis

Average of CpGs methylation for each amplicon was calculated for both controls and patients samples. Statistical analysis was performed using PRISM 5.0a software. Two-tailed unpaired T-test with Welch's correction ($p < 0.05$) was used to study group methylation differences between PPHP patients and healthy controls for all the imprinting control regions studied.

A more individual statistical approach was then performed comparing each patient's Sequenom CpG value or amplicon average with the distribution of values of the same variable measured in a group of healthy controls ($n=41$ for NESP, $n=48$ for XL and GRB10, $n=47$ for Exon A/B, $n=45$ for IGF2, $n=33$ for ICR1_H19, $n=35$ for SNURF) (Z-test, $P < 0.05$). Values with a Z-score ≤ -2 and $\geq +2$ were considered significantly hypo- or hypermethylated, respectively. Normality test was assessed with SPSS 12.5 software to study the control population values distribution.

Validation of Sequenom data via methylation specific digestion

NESP, XL, Exon A/B amplicons were PCR amplified and further digested with the SsiI (Fermentas, Burlington, Canada) enzyme as described.¹⁹

Results

Platelet Gs function

We studied platelet Gs activity in 16 PPHP patients and 1 POH patient with variable AHO features as reported in **Table 1**. For patients 1 to 4 platelet testing could not be performed since only a DNA sample was available for further analysis.

Genetic analysis of GNAS

Since patients were clinically diagnosed with PPHP (1 with POH) and most had platelet Gs hypofunction, *GNAS* screening for inactivation mutations was performed. No *GNAS* coding mutations were found in any of the PPHP patients. All patients were heterozygous for at least one of the studied *GNAS* region SNPs, excluding small chromosomal deletions within the *GNAS* cluster (data not shown).

Study of GNAS methylation

GNAS methylation was screened for NESP, XL and ExonA/B using the Sequenom EpiTYPER as we previously optimized for PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia cases.¹⁹ We could observe a significant hypermethylation in the XL region in PPHP patients vs controls (36 ± 3 vs. $29\pm 3\%$ (mean $\pm$ SD); T-test, $p<0.001$; Figure 1). Interestingly, this is the opposite pattern of the epigenetic defect described for PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia patients having pronounced XL hypomethylation.¹⁹ Overall methylation that includes all studied CpGs in the amplicons for NESP and ExonA/B did not show any significant difference between patients and controls (**Figure 1**) though some patients (patient 1, 2 and 3 for NESP and patient 3 and 5 for ExonA/B) showed a significant difference in methylation (**Figure 2A**). However, studying single CpGs within these amplicons showed significant hyper- (red) or hypo- (green) methylation (Z-test, $p<0.05$) for both the NESP and ExonA/B amplicons and for almost all patients (**Figure 2A**). Based on the analysis of the single CpGs in NESP and ExonA/B (not for XL), some patients seem to cluster in subgroups but these clusters did not seem to correlate further with clinical severity of PPHP phenotype.

Study of IGF2 and H19 ICR1 methylation

We additionally studied 30 CpGs in the DMR1 of IGF2 and 25 CpGs in the ICR1 of the H19 locus. Surprisingly, we could observe significant hypermethylation of the IGF2 locus in PPHP patients vs. controls (20 ± 10 vs. $14\pm 7\%$; T-test, $p<0.05$; **Figure 1**). The overall CpG methylation for the H19 amplicon was not significantly different for patients and controls (35 ± 8 vs. $35\pm 5\%$), though a significant hypermethylation was seen for patients 2 and 4 (**Figure 2B**). For the analysis of single CpGs within the IGF2 region, we could observe a significant hypermethylation in 14 out of 17 PPHP patients at specific CpGs (**Figure 2B**) (Z-test, $p<0.05$). For the H19 region also some specific CpGs show significant differences in methylation but only for a few patients and clustering within patients seems not be present.

Figure 1. *GNAS*, *IGF2/H19*, *SNURF* and *GRB10* methylation in PPHP vs. *crls*

* vs. *crls*, $p < 0.05$, ** vs. *crls*, $p < 0.001$, unpaired T-test

Study of SNURF methylation

The amplicon for *SNURF* studies 18 CpGs and a significant hypomethylation in the *SNURF* region was found for PPHP patients vs. controls (23 ± 6 vs. $32 \pm 6\%$; T-test, $p < 0.001$; **Figure 1**). Remarkably, single CpG analysis showed both significant hyper (CpG7_8) and hypo (CpG14_16, CpG25) methylation (**Figure 2B**) within the same amplicon and for almost all patients.

Study of GRB10 methylation

The amplicon for the *GRB10* region studies 18 CpGs and was not significantly different between patients and controls (37 ± 7 vs. $34 \pm 6\%$; **Figure 1**). Interestingly, the

overall methylation for patients 14 and 15 showed a significant GRB10 hypermethylation of 56 and 50%, respectively, vs. $35 \pm 6\%$ for controls; Z-test, $p < 0.05$) (Figure 2B). The analysis of single CpGs showed some significant differences for some patients with both hyper and hypomethylated sites (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. *GNAS* (A), *IGF2/H19*, *SNURF* and *GRB10* (B) methylation in PPHP patients via Sequenom EpiTYPER

A

Discussion

The human *GNAS* cluster contains three differentially methylated regions: NESP, XL and exon A/B.¹⁹ Patients who develop PHP-Ib usually present with exon A/B hypomethylation.^{14,39-41} In these familial PHP-Ib cases the latter appears to be caused by maternally inherited deletions affecting either the STX16^{35,42} or the NESP55/NESPAS regions.^{11,43} Broader *GNAS* imprinting defects involving the three differentially methylated *GNAS* regions are observed in sporadic PHP-Ib cases with NESP55 hypermethylation versus XL and exon A/B hypomethylation.^{19,40,43-45} In both familial and sporadic PHP-Ib cases, exon A/B hypomethylation is thought to interfere with the normal G α expression in the proximal renal tubules and therefore to be responsible for the PTH resistance in these patients though this remains a hypothesis.⁴⁶ Recently, a similar broad epigenetic *GNAS* defect was described for some PHP-Ia cases without *GNAS* coding mutations.^{15,16,18,19} These patients had PTH resistance but also an AHO phenotype implicating that *GNAS* methylation defects could also result in AHO features. Therefore, we hypothesize that PPHP patients without coding *GNAS* mutations could also have *GNAS* methylation abnormalities.

We studied *GNAS* methylation in 16 patients with clinical diagnosis of PPHP and 1 POH patient without *GNAS* mutations but having platelet Gs hypofunction and an AHO phenotype that mainly involves short stature and brachydactyly or clinodactyly. *GNAS* methylation was quantified for the three differentially methylated regions using the Sequenom EpiTYPER as we previously did for PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia cases.¹⁹ Grouped analysis showed a significant hypermethylation for the XL amplicon in PPHP patients versus controls (36% vs 29%; $p < 0.001$) but overall methylation for the NESP and ExonA/B regions was not significantly different between patients and controls, except for significant hypermethylation in patients 1, 2 and 3 for NESP and patients 3 and 5 for ExonA/B. The same trend for hypermethylation in NESP and ExonA/B is also visible when analyzing separate CpGs for at least the first 10 patients while the other 7 patients show a weak trend towards hypomethylation of NESP and ExonA/B. This epigenetic defect (with hypermethylation of NESP, XL and ExonA/B) is different from the imprinting pattern observed in PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia patients (having NESP hyper versus XL and Exon A/B hypomethylation). However, the main defect in PPHP is the significant XL hypermethylation that could be linked to the short stature

phenotype in the patients who did not present with intrauterine growth retardation. Interestingly, it is known that the main phenotype for XL deficient mice is the regulation of postnatal growth.⁴⁷ In addition, the platelet Gs hypofunction in the PPHP patients could also be due to loss of XL α s expression since we have previously shown evidence that the XL α s protein can regulate platelet Gs activity.^{48,49} Others have also shown a role for XL α s in the stimulation of cAMP after stimulation of Gs-coupled receptors.⁵⁰⁻⁵²

Some typical AHO features are also present in patients with other imprinting syndromes such as for the growth and neurodevelopmental diseases Silver-Russel/Beckwith-Wiedemann and Prader-Willi/Angelman syndromes. We have also studied the methylation of other imprinted genes such as IGF2, H19, SNURF and GRB10 in the PPHP patients. Surprisingly, we could observe significant hypermethylation for IGF2 (20 vs 10%; $P < 0.05$) and hypomethylation (23 vs 32; $P < 0.001$) for SNURF. H19 and GRB10 showed no overall difference between patients and controls. IGF2 expression is reported to affect mouse embryo development. Mice knockout models indicate that loss of paternal IGF2 causes Intra Uterine Growth Restriction (IUGR)⁵³ (model for Silver-Russel syndrome), whereas experimental overexpression of the same allele results in hypertrophic mice that resemble Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome.⁵⁴ We observed a significant hypermethylation of the IGF2 amplicon that was designed for the region chr11:2107419-2107915 (NCBI b36.1) including both promoter and first exons of IGF2 and its antisense transcript PEG8. The ICR1 of H19 (implicated in Silver-Russel and Beckwith-Wiedemann) was not significantly different in the PPHP patients except for patients 2 and 4 showing significant H19 hypermethylation which is the opposite pattern described for Silver-Russel syndrome. These findings could further support the short stature phenotype in our patients as a result of decreased expression of IGF2. A role for IGF2 in regulation of platelet function has not been assigned to our knowledge.

Some Prader-Willi syndrome patients show hypermethylation at SNURF/SNRPN locus, while our PPHP patients displayed a significant hypomethylation compared to normal controls. Interestingly, though Prader-Willi patients have hypotonia and failure to thrive at birth (as XL-*GNAS* deficient mice), they present with obesity later

in life. Our PPHP patients did not show obesity but growth failure that could be the result of the opposite imprinting pattern for SNURF compared to Prader-Willi syndrome. The SNURF/SNRPN region seems not be involved in the neurobehavior disease Angelman syndrome.

GRB10 DMR was only significantly hypermethylated in 2 of our PPHP patients which show in addition gain of methylation at *GNAS* DMRs. GRB10 hypomethylation as part of a wider loss of methylation defect has been recently reported in a patient with growth restriction.⁵⁵

IGF2 and GRB10 together with *GNAS* have been described to be part of an imprinted genes network that regulate embryonic growth and differentiation dependent on Zac-1 regulation.²⁶ At this moment it is not clear how these interactions function exactly. But there are some recent other studies that showed defects in multiple imprinting genes in some developmental diseases.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁸ Especially for *GNAS* the epigenotype-phenotype relation seems very complex as the same methylation defect was found for PHP-Ib (with PTH resistance) and PHP-Ia (with PTH resistance and AHO) cases. We here expand the spectrum with PPHP (only AHO) and epigenetic defect in *GNAS*, IGF2 and SNURF. In addition, we also report the first epigenetic defect in a patient with POH, a phenotype that was recently included in the phenotypic spectrum of *GNAS* paternally inherited inactivation mutations.¹³ This patient (number 5) had no *GNAS* coding mutations but presents with a significant overall *GNAS* hypermethylation (for XL, NESP and ExonA/B), while the other imprinting regions are about normal.

In conclusion we studied *GNAS*, IGF2/H19, SNURF and GRB10 methylation in a group of PPHP patients with Gs hypofunction but no *GNAS* coding mutations. We could broaden the spectrum of (epi)genetic defects associated with an AHO phenotype by identifying an epigenetic defect in XL, IGF2 and SNURF in PPHP patients. More studies on multiple imprinting control regions in more PPHP patients are warranted to further investigate the combination of epigenetic defects in relation to phenotypes.

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Chapter 10

Neural tube defects and epigenetic control by DNA methylation - is there a link?

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In preparation

Abstract

Neural Tube Defects (NTDs) represent a common group of severe congenital malformations that result from failure of neural tube closure during early embryogenesis. The aetiology is very complex involving environmental and genetic factors but the exact underlying molecular and pathogenic mechanisms still remain poorly understood. Genetic studies in NTDs have focused mainly on folate-related genes based on the finding that perinatal folic acid supplementation reduces the risk of NTDs by 60%. The candidate gene approach, investigating genes involved in neurulation, has failed to identify major causative genes for NTDs. Since our preliminary studies in some Spina Bifida patients with platelet Gs hypofunction revealed epigenetic abnormalities in Exon A/B of the *GNAS* cluster, we hypothesized that DNA methylation abnormalities in multiple genes could be involved in NTDs. Therefore, we used a genome-wide approach to study methylation using the Illumina Human 27K BeadChip in 6 Spina Bifida patients and 4 controls. Significant hypermethylation was found for CpGs associated with *ZNF718*, *KCNQ1*, *GSTT1*, *TP53INP1*, *MRI1* and *ACOT11* while CpGs within *FLJ45964* were hypomethylated. *ZNF718*, *GSTT1* and *ACOT11* hypomethylation was further studied in 101 SB patients using the Sequenom EpiTYPER for data replication. *ACOT11* depletion in zebrafish embryos further resulted in a neurulation defect. In conclusion, we here report the first epigenetic study in SB cases that combines genome-scale and locus-specific mass spectrometry analysis to quantify DNA methylation. Multiple loci of altered DNA methylation seem to be involved in neural tube closure. Additional epigenetic and functional genomic studies are needed to strengthen these preliminary findings.

Introduction

Neural Tube Defects (NTDs) are the second most common human birth defect, with an overall prevalence of around 0.5–2/1,000 pregnancies and frequently result in infant mortality or major health problems in surviving children.¹ They result from perturbation in the neurulation process. Spinal presentations of NTDs are the result of closure failure of the posterior neuropore. They include open spina bifida forms such as myelomeningocele and meningocele, where the defects in the vertebral arches are associated with the presence of the open neural folds. In addition myelomeningocele is often associated with other complications such as hydrocephalus and Arnold-Chiari type II malformation. A milder form of spinal malformations is represented by spina bifida occulta, where the outer part of some vertebrae is not completely closed, but the skin is often normal and in most cases this condition is asymptomatic. In general the clinical severity of spina bifida is affected by the axial level at which closure fails but patients frequently suffer from paralysis of the legs, as well as from bowel and bladder dysfunction. A number of evidences suggest an interaction between both genetic and environmental factors as possible etiology for NTDs.²⁻⁴ The most robust genetic risk factor so far reported for NTDs is the 677C>T SNP in 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR)⁵ which is associated with elevated homocysteine levels.⁶ However, some NTD cases were shown to be not folate-preventable⁷ and it has been shown that maternal folate levels in most affected pregnancies fall within the “normal” range.⁸

However, there are more evidences suggesting the role of genetics as predisposing factor for NTDs. High recurrence risk for siblings of affected individuals and association of NTDs with specific chromosomal anomalies has been reported.⁹⁻¹¹ In addition, more than 200 different mouse genetic models have been described to have NTDs.^{12,13} However, of those 200 genes only few have been confirmed to be involved in human NTDs.⁴ Some studies have focused on the human orthologous of those genes that cause NTDs in mice as possible causative factors for human NTDs. However, very few consistent findings originated from this candidate gene approach, except for a potential role for the non-canonical Wnt pathway ‘Planar Cell Polarity’ (PCP).¹⁴ Mutations in the PCP gene VANG1 were identified in few patients with NTDs¹⁵ and were next characterized as loss of function variants in VANG2 depleted

zebrafish.¹⁶ A case-control study was performed to evaluate the role of several key Wnt signaling genes in NTDs but none of the 172 evaluated SNPs in these Wnt regulatory genes showed an association with SB.¹⁷ Apart from candidate-gene studies, the conventional gene hunting strategies such as positional cloning and linkage mapping were not applicable to study NTDs because of the paucity of large families with multiple affected individuals. It has been suggested to focus on larger patient cohorts using high-throughput genomic technologies such as detection of CNVs or GWAS to identify novel regulatory genes for NTDs.^{4,14}

The involvement of epigenetics in NTDs has recently been suggested based on a theoretical hypothesis.¹⁸ Some evidence for a role of histone positioning in NTDs comes from studies that showed that valproate (VPA) that is widely used as anticonvulsant agent is associated with 1-2% incidence of NTDs and 10 to 20-fold increased risk for lumbosacral meningomyelocele when taken during the first trimester of pregnancy¹⁹⁻²² It is suggested that its potent histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitory activity could affect neurulation as also shown in zebrafish.²³ Some literature suggests in particular a specific role for DNA methylation in the neurulation process and in the development of NTDs. First of all, folates are internal to the intracellular one-carbon metabolism (**figure 6, chapter 2**) that produces pyrimidines and purines for DNA synthesis and s-adenosyl methionine,²⁴ the universal methyl group donor for all macromolecules, including DNA. Therefore, cell proliferation that depends on DNA synthesis and stimulation of DNA methylation are likely effects of folate supplementation. Secondly, epidemiological studies are suggestive for a link between an impaired methylation cycle and human NTDs, since an association was found with elevated homocysteine and sub-optimal levels of folate in maternal blood.^{25,26} Few small-scale studies focused on fetal DNA methylation demonstrated an inverse correlation between LINE-1 DNA methylation and homocysteine levels.^{27,28} In addition, experimental evidence from model systems also supports the hypothesis that abnormal methylation contributes to NTDs. Mice deficient for DNA methyltransferase 3A (DNMT3A) or treated with methyl cycle inhibitors have cranial NTDs.^{29,30}

Preceding study

The complete coding region of *GNAS* (including NESP, XL and ExonA/B) was sequenced for a SB patient with pronounced brachydactyly (short metacarpals IV), short stature, mental retardation (**table 3 of chapter 2**) and platelet Gs hypofunction comparable to defects observed in AHO patients.³¹ A unique combination of nucleotide substitutions in exon 7 and exon 13 on the same allele of the *GNAS* gene that was previously shown to be associated with three *GNAS* splice variants and reduced Gs protein levels³² has been detected in this SB patient. The incidence of these combined substitutions in a series of sporadic SB patients is 6.09 % (5/82). The 4 other SB patients with these *GNAS* variants also had AHO features and platelet Gs hypofunction (**table 3 of chapter 2**). We tested unrelated controls and found an incidence in 2/397 without evidence of spinal closure defects (0.5% versus 6,09%, $p=0.0021$). We here hypothesized that *GNAS* methylation abnormalities could also have a causative role in the pathogenesis of NTDs.

Subjects and Methods

Subjects

101 sporadic SB patients were selected with various spinal NTDs including myelomeningocele with hydrocephalus and Arnold-Chiari type II malformation (n=87), meningocele (n=3) and spina bifida occulta (n=11). Most of the patients also are non-autonomous ambulators and suffer from incontinence.

GNAS Methylation analysis by PCR amplification of bisulfite treated DNA and methylation-sensitive restriction digestion

The bisulfite reaction was carried out on 500 ng of gDNA with the MethylDetector bisulfite modification kit (Active Motif, Carlsbad, CA). A conversion reaction was performed in a 140 μ L mixture containing 13 μ L of gDNA, 7 μ L of hydroquinone, and 120 μ L of conversion buffer, as described by the manufacturer. DNA was denatured with an initial melt at 94°C for 3 min, and then a conversion at 50° C for 9 h was performed in a PTC-200 Peltier Thermal Cycler (MJ Research, Reno, NV). Control nested PCRs were performed as described in the kit. A nested PCR was performed to amplify the exon A/B region using 5 microl bisulfite-treated gDNA, 0.5 microM primers, 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 1X buffer (20 mM Tris (pH 8.4), 50 mM KCl), and 0.2

microl (5 U/microl) Taq DNA polymerase (Invitrogen) as described.³¹ Amplified PCR products were further digested with a restriction enzyme that only recognizes the nonconverted (methylated) DNA sequence, being HinfI (Fermentas) for exon A/B. Digested PCR fragments were separated on a 2% agarose gel.

Infinium 27K methylation assay

For the discovery round, the HumanMethylation27K BeadChip, using Infinium technology³³ for genome-wide DNA methylation screening was used.³⁴ Genomic DNA (1 µg) was bisulfite converted using the MethylDetector Kit (Active Motif). The following modifications to the protocol were made to optimize the bisulfite conversion for subsequent whole-genome amplification: i. bisulfite DNA elution was performed in a final volume of 15 µL and ii. the conversion reaction mixture was incubated at (95°C for 30sec, 50°C for 1h) x 16 cycles. Bisulfite-treated DNA was applied to BeadChips (Illumina). This microarray platform relies on the hybridization between microarray probes (50-mer oligonucleotides) and sodium bisulfite-modified genomic input DNA. Sodium bisulfite converts unmethylated cytosine to uracil but methylated cytosine is protected and remains a cytosine. There are two probes for each CpG site, one is specific for the methylated CpG and the other is for the unmethylated CpG. The two probes differ only at the 3'-end nucleotide, which hybridizes to the target CpG and allows the probes to distinguish between the methylated and the unmethylated target sequence. Only when the end nucleotide of the probe hybridizes to the corresponding type of CpG (methylated or unmethylated) can single-base extension using DNP- and Biotin-labeled ddNTPs occur and release the fluorescent signal for detection. After extension, the array is fluorescently stained and scanned, and the intensities of the nonmethylated and methylated bead types are measured. DNA methylation values, described as “beta values”, are recorded for each locus in each sample and represent the ratio of the intensity of the methylated bead type to the combined locus intensity.

Sequenom EpiTYPER analysis

Sequenom EpiTYPER technology was used for replication experiments. DNA bisulfite conversion was performed with MethylDetector kit. Bisulfite-specific primers for the replication of the findings in the 27K study are reported in **table 2**. FLJ90036, ACOT11 and GSTT1 PCR products were treated according to the standard protocol by

SAP treatment and T-cleavage reaction. The samples were then cleaned by Resin and were dispensed to a 384 SpectroCHIP by Nanodispenser. The chip was read by a Bruker Autoflex Mass Spectrometer System. Data were collected with the use of SpectroACQUIRE v3.3.1.3 software and visualized with MassARRAY EpiTYPER v1.0 software.

Statistical analysis to identify differentially methylated genes in NTD patients

The microarray data were analyzed using the BeadStudio (Methylation Module v3.2) software provided by Illumina. We used two criteria to classify a CpG site as differentially methylated in each of the NTD patient compared to the four controls used in the study: i. an average Beta value below the cut-off for hypomethylation and above the cut-off for hypermethylation. Cut-offs for hypomethylation and hypermethylation for each CpG were calculated as the mean of average Beta values in the four controls $\pm$ three times the standard deviation, respectively (**Table 3**) and ii. an absolute difference of average Beta values above 0.2. The method was adapted from Martin-Subero et al.³⁵

Table 2. Primers used in the replication study by Sequenom EpiTYPER

primers' name	primers' nucleotide sequence
FLJ90036_F	5`-AGGAAGAGAGAGAGTTATAGAGGTTGAGGTTGTGG-3
FLJ90036_R	5`-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTACCTACCTCAAATACCAAAAACC-3
ACOT11_23_F	5`-AGGAAGAGAGTTTGGGTGTTTGTAGTTTTTGTAGTTTTT-3
ACOT11_23_R	5`-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTCAACCCCCTCCCTAAAAATAAT-3
GSTT1_4_F	5`-AGGAAGAGAGAGTAATGGTTTTAGGAAGAAGGTGG-3
GSTT1_4_R	5`-CAGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGGCTATCTCTTAACCACCCACCCTAA-3

Table 3. Raw DNA methylation data and analysis to identify differentially methylated genes in NTD patients. Average Beta values range from 0 for completely unmethylated to 1 for complete methylated DNA.

SYMBOL	TargetID	cr1	cr2	cr3	cr4	Mean	SD	Cut-off hypomethylation	Cut-off hypermethylation	DS	VN	DP	KM	BJ	SM
FLJ90036	cg12717203	0,083	0,133	0,104	0,068	0,097	0,028	0,012	0,182	0,514	0,407	0,329	0,405	0,117	0,494
FLJ90036	cg15792688	0,073	0,132	0,081	0,071	0,089	0,029	0,002	0,176	0,378	0,203	0,301	0,204	0,097	0,278
ACOT11	cg21448423	0,282	0,345	0,256	0,394	0,319	0,063	0,132	0,507	0,513	0,512	0,547	0,508	0,620	0,433
KCNQ1	cg17820828	0,458	0,469	0,523	0,382	0,458	0,058	0,284	0,632	0,751	0,588	0,625	0,748	0,660	0,519
GSTT1	cg24330042	0,043	0,055	0,071	0,053	0,055	0,012	0,021	0,090	0,054	0,034	0,421	0,049	0,428	0,404
TP53INP1	cg18059933	0,268	0,192	0,268	0,292	0,255	0,043	0,125	0,386	0,203	0,364	0,473	0,184	0,204	0,517
MGC3207	cg16474696	0,056	0,090	0,181	0,058	0,096	0,059	-0,080	0,273	0,347	0,097	0,425	0,555	0,290	0,258
FLJ45964	cg17977362	0,859	0,896	0,899	0,900	0,888	0,020	0,829	0,948	0,910	0,920	0,448	0,489	0,924	0,921

Cells labeled in green indicate CpGs hypomethylated whereas cells labeled in red point to CpGs hypermethylated vs. controls, respectively.

Statistical analysis to study differential methylation in NTD patients for the amplicons ACOT11, GSTT1, FLJ90036

The Z-test was calculated as described.³⁶ Both single CpG and amplicon averages were taken in account to determine differential methylation in the ACOT11, GSTT1 and FLJ90036 regions for the total NTD cases studied. Unpaired T-test was additionally applied to study group differences with a $p < 0.05$ of significance using Prism 5.0a software.

Zebrafish and microinjection of an ACOT11-specific morpholino

Wild-type AB zebrafish embryos were injected at the 1-cell stage with a start codon blocking morpholino (MO): 0.6, 0.8 and 1 mM ATG ACOT11a MO (5'-TTAGCCTGGACTCTAATGATGCCAT-3'). Off-target effects were assessed by co-analyzing injections with a standard control MO or buffer injected embryos. The ACOT11a MO was designed by Gene-Tools LLC (Philomath,OR). Embryos were life-screened at 1, 2, 3 and 6 days post fertilization (dpf) using a Zeiss Lumar V12 and images were captured with a Zeiss AxioCam MRc camera using AxioVision software (Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany). All animal protocols were approved by the Ethical Committee of the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven.

Whole-Mount In Situ Hybridization (WISH) of zebrafish

Developmental staging of injected zebrafish were determined by somite number and embryos were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde. Assays for RNA expression using WISH were performed as described³⁷ using a Pax2a and MyoD probe. Embryos were visualized with a Zeiss Lumar V12 or a Zeiss Axiovert 100M microscope and images were captured with a Zeiss AxioCam MRcamera using AxioVision software.

Results

GNAS exon A/B-specific methylation analysis

We have studied a total of 77 patients for exonA/B methylation via bisulfite-treated DNA amplification and methylation-specific digestion with *Hinf I*. We have found an abnormal exon A/B methylation in 20% of the patients: 20 patients presented with hypermethylation while 5 other patients displayed hypomethylation (**figure 4**).

Figure 4. Exon A/B methylation patterns observed in SB patients

Exon A/B methylation analysis by PCR and restriction digestion (*Hinf I*) of bisulfite-treated DNA in Spina Bifida patients (**a, b, c, d, e**) and healthy controls (**ctrl**) showing ExonA/B hypermethylation (a, b, d and e) or hypomethylation (c) of the same amplicon.

Genome-wide methylation analysis using the 27K BeadChip array

Six patients were selected with an abnormal exon A/B methylation and further studied together with 4 controls (2 females) using the 27K human methylation Bead chip array. This chip interrogates 27,578 CpGs covering more than 14,000 RefSeq genes. These CpGs map to the promoter regions of genes with an average coverage of 2 CpGs per gene and more extensive coverage (3–20 CpGs) for cancer-related and imprinted genes.³⁸ Two independent experiments were performed for all the samples studied (bisulfite treatment included). The mean coefficient of determination (R^2) from the technical replicates from all samples was 0.975, ranging from 0.955 to 0.993. Controls coefficient of determination is reported as an example in **figure 5**. Beta values were calculated and used for further analysis. All samples had at least 26,608 CpGs with detection p-value below 0.05. Detection p value provided by BeadStudio is a measure of signal quality. In addition, all samples had a bisulfite conversion control (BCC) value of at least 3704. The BCC value provided by BeadStudio is a measure of bisulfite conversion quality. All samples were considered of high quality. For microarray precision analysis, the samples were subjected to quality control of similar stringency.

Figure 5. Coefficient of determination R^2 for control samples ($R^2=0.9931$)

GNAS CpGs analysis in healthy controls

The 27K BeadChip allows quantification of methylation for 30 CpGs localized in the *GNAS* cluster. We could observe variation in control methylation values among different CpGs, with some being almost fully methylated (cg01565981) and others completely unmethylated (cg06044900, cg09598225 and cg22885821) (**figure 6**). Surprisingly, 2 out of these 4 outliers (cg09598225 and cg22885821) are localized in the ExonA/B DMR. This suggests the relevance of applying additional methodologies that allow quantification of additional CpGs such as possible with the Sequenom EpiTYPER. In fact, some CpGs might be not representative for the methylation pattern of the complete locus or might be not relevant for disease. However, most of the *GNAS* CpGs, showed methylation values ranging from 30 to 70% (**figure 6**).

the FLJ45964 displayed hypomethylation (**table 3 and figure 8**). Apart from the KCNQ1 locus, no other imprinted region was commonly involved in the methylation defect. Differential methylation was also observed for 60 other genes (23 hypo- and 37 hypermethylated) but this only for a single SB patient. Variability of the epigenotypes of the 6 SB patients studied was not associated to any specific variability in the phenotype.

Table 4. Localization and transcription start site coordinates of the differentially methylated CpGs in at least 2 out of 6 SB cases.

CpG number	Gene Symbol	Chromosome	Map info	TSS_Coordinate
cg15792688	FLJ90036	4	114693	114402
cg12717203	FLJ90036	4	114342	114402
cg21448423	ACOT11	1	54786544	54786489
cg17820828	KCNQ1	11	2769874	/
cg24330042	GSTT1	22	22714159	22714231
cg18059933	TP53INP1	8	96031639	96030767
cg16474696	MGC3207	19	13736014	13736346
cg17977362	FLJ45964	2	240165186	240164932

Heatmap representation of 27K BeadChip methylation in 6 SB cases.

DNA methylation of CpG units of the differentially methylated genes in SB vs. controls. DNA methylation values are depicted by a pseudocolor scale as indicated in the legend. Methylation increases from green (nonmethylated) to red (methylated).

Replication study with Sequenom EpiTYPER

We replicated the genome-wide methylation findings using the Sequenom EpiTYPER, which allows rapid quantitative screening of methylation for multiple CpGs in a large numbers of samples. Three amplicons were designed to amplify the region of ZNF718, ACOT11 and GSTT1 using the Epidesigner software from Sequenom (<http://www.epidesigner.com/>). Localization of the amplicons and the studied 27K BeadChip CpGs within these loci are reported in **table 5**. The Sequenom will analyze a total of 7 CpGs in the ZNF718, 14 CpGs in the ACOT11 and 17 CpGs in the GSTT1 amplicons. We could observe significant hypermethylation in at least one of the CpGs studied in 33, 41 and 25% of the SB cases (n=101) for ZNF718, ACOT11 and GSTT1, respectively. Unpaired t-test analysis was performed to study the significance of preferential CpGs for SB cases vs control subjects ($p < 0.05$, **figure 9**).

Table 5. Localization and characteristics of the FLJ90036, ACOT11 and GSTT1 Sequenom amplicons

name amplicon	chr	start*	end*	size (bp)	theoretical number of CpGs per amplicon	effective number of GpCs studied via the Sequenom EpiTYPER	localization of CpGs in the Illumina array
FLJ90036	4	114192	114492	300	14	7	114342
ACOT11_23	1	54786170	54786657	488	19	14	54785544
GSTT1_4	22	22714012	22714467	455	27	17	22714159

* Nucleotide positions according to the March 2006 human reference sequence (NCBI Build 36/hg18.1) produced by the International Human Genome Sequencing Consortium.

Figure 9. Differential methylation in NTDs for ACOT11, GSTT1 and ZNF718

The depicted CpGs in ACOT11, ZNF718 and GSTT1 showed hypermethylation in NTDs cases compared to controls. ** Vs. controls (Ctrls), $p < 0.05$, Unpaired T-test.

Functional characterization of ACOT11 in zebrafish neurulation

ACOT11 depletion in zebrafish embryos was done with an ATG MO in different concentrations (0.6, 0.8 and 1 mM). Concentrations of 1 mM MO were cytotoxic, leading to a rapid developmental arrest. Malformation of the tail could only be observed at 48 hpf with 0.8 mM MO (**figure 11a**). Pax2a staining for neurons adjacent to the neural tube in ACOT11 MO deleted and control embryos at 24 hpf showed an abnormal staining for the ACOT11 deficient embryos (**figure 11b and c**). An abnormal neurulation phenotype became even more obvious at 72 hpf (**figure 11d and e**). At least 80% of the embryos present with shorter A/P axes as well as bent or crooked tails. Some had eye defects and a disrupted or complete lack of pigmentation. Most of them did not develop one or both the fins and swimming activity was severely impaired leading to immobility or swimming in circles. At 6 dpf, ACOT11 depleted embryos remained viable but the tail abnormalities were still visible (**figure 11f and g**).

Figure 11. Phenotypic analysis of ACOT11a depleted Zebrafish embryos

(a) ACOT11a injected embryo at 48 hpf showing a deformed tail; (b & c) WISH with Pax2a probe in ACOT11a injected (b) and buffer-injected (c) embryos at 24 hpf; (d & e) buffer-injected (d) and ACOT11a injected with curled and nicked tails (e) embryos at 72 hpf; (f & g) buffer-injected (f) and ACOT11a injected (g) embryos at 6 dpf.

Discussion

From a preliminary study previously conducted in the lab, platelet Gs hypofunction was detected in 5 SB patients with also some AHO features (**table 3 chapter 2**) and presenting with a unique combination of SNPs in the coding sequence of GNAS. Functional evidence for Gs signalling to be involved in the pathogenesis of NTDs comes from the observation that protein kinase A deficient mice develop NTDs.³⁹ We therefore hypothesized that also GNAS methylation could play a role in SB. Indeed, we could observe in 20% of 77 SB patients an abnormal exon A/B methylation but with both hyper- or hypomethylation in the same amplicon. To investigate whether GNAS methylation changes are specific or just part of an overall DNA methylation defect, we have studied DNA methylation in SB cases using a genome-scale methylation quantification approach. A general methylation defect in SB is further supported by the evidence that folic acid supplementation, which may alter genome methylation, reduces the risk of developing NTDs.

So far the only evidence for a link between one-carbon metabolites and fetal DNA methylation originate from few small-scale studies that used cord blood to determine these parameters. An inverse relation was detected between DNA methylation of LINE-1 sequences and homocysteine levels.^{27,28} Wang et al very

recently examined LINE-1 methylation in fetal neural tissues showing lower LINE-1 methylation levels in tissues from cranial NTDs compared to controls in association with a significant decrease in maternal plasma vitamin B-12 relative to controls⁴⁰. However, a caveat associated with analyses of LINE-1 elements as a surrogate for genome-wide methylation is that changes in these repetitive elements may differ from the rest of the genome. The latter has been even recognized by Yang and colleagues, who first described the advantage of analyzing these repetitive elements.⁴¹ Our genome-scale approach revealed both hyper- (43 genes) and hypomethylated (24 genes) CpGs in SB patients versus controls. Hypomethylation of LINE-1 sequences might be associated to more gene-specific hypermethylation as this is also described in tumor cells⁴². From the genome-wide analysis it appears that NTDs are the result of a general methylation defect that involves many loci, some of them being possibly more important than others in the aetiology of the phenotype. Whether methylation abnormalities are chromosome-specific still remains to be elucidated, although some specific regions of the genome seem to be more involved than others such as 1p31-36, 19p13, 19q13 and 12q13-24.

The genome-wide methylation analysis also revealed the presence of common differentially methylated CpGs in the SB cases as 6 and 1 CpGs were hypermethylated and hypomethylated, respectively, in at least 2 out of 6 patients. The ZNF718 (FLJ90036) gene was hypermethylated in even 5 out of 6 SB patients. ZNF718 is an unknown gene with no defined function in human or mouse. The potassium voltage-gated channel, KQT-like subfamily, member 1 (KCNQ1, MIM: 607542) is the only imprinted gene found to be hypermethylated in 3 out of 6 SB patients. This gene exhibits tissue-specific imprinting, with preferential expression from the maternal allele in some tissues and biallelic expression in others. It is located in the chromosome 11 region that is associated with Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome. However, it is important to note that protein expression studies in mouse have shown that KCNQ1 is expressed in all nervous and sensory organs, including the spinal cord.⁴³ Glutathione S-transferase (GST) theta 1 (GSTT1; MIM: 600436) is a member of a superfamily of proteins that catalyze the conjugation of reduced glutathione to a variety of electrophilic and hydrophobic compounds. The gene has been associated to a number of cancer conditions, and interestingly its expression

has been proven in human embryonic craniofacial tissues during the relevant developmental interval.⁴⁴ The methylthioribose-1-phosphate isomerase (MRI1) homolog is located on chromosome 19p13.2, and it is described to be involved in the eukaryotic methionine salvage pathway,⁴⁵ being particularly relevant then for the folate metabolism.

Acyl-CoA thioesterase 11 (ACOT11; MIM: 606803) encodes a member of the acyl-CoA thioesterase family which catalyses the conversion of activated fatty acids to the corresponding non-esterified fatty acid and coenzyme A.⁴⁶ This gene was hypermethylated in 5 SB patients using the 27K BeadChip and hypermethylated in 41% of the 101 patients studied in the replication experiments. We evaluated the morphological changes in Zebrafish embryos after MO-induced depletion of the ortholog gene ACOT11a. The phenotype we could observe is highly comparable to the one induced by valproate,²³ which is known as teratogenic agent causing defects of the neural tube closure. More studies are needed to better characterize the function of ACOT11 in zebrafish neurulation.

In conclusion we have shown a possible link between methylation defects and aetiology of NTDs by a unique combination of genome-wide (discovery round via 27K BeadChip) and gene-specific (replication studies via Sequenom) methylation analysis. Our data further support the use of zebrafish embryos for the functional screening of candidate genes in their role on neurulation as hyper- or hypomethylation of genes can be studied via MO technology or mRNA overexpression, respectively. This chapter is a preliminary study that requires further DNA methylation assays and a further functional characterisation in zebrafish.

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Chapter 11

Concluding discussion

GNAS is the most complex imprinted gene described to date and includes a transcript that codes for Gs as main regulator of cAMP formation. Its role in human development has become more and more evident in the last years especially since (epi)genetic technologies have improved. This thesis attempted to expand the current knowledge about *GNAS* involvement in human diseases, with particular attention to classical *GNAS*-related phenotypes such (a)specific PHP-Ib cases and some PHP-Ia and PPHP cases without coding *GNAS* variants. In addition, our focus was drawn to the role of *GNAS* in patients with spina bifida and an AHO phenotype. For most of these patients described in my thesis, an abnormal platelet Gs function was identified.

***GNAS*: a complex gene cluster associated with different phenotypes due to genetic and epigenetic defects**

The term pseudohypoparathyroidism encompasses a heterogeneous group of rare endocrine disorders, all characterized by end-organ resistance to the action of PTH (reviewed in^{56,219,220}). Those include PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib, that were classically distinguishable by the presence or absence of AHO features, respectively. Recent studies performed by our group^{80,126} and others^{132-134,141,221} have shown that both clinical conditions show overlapping features in functional Gs assays and epigenetic *GNAS* defects. PHP-Ib cases were originally defined as the only *GNAS* imprinting disorder with the sporadic PHP-Ib cases having NESP hypermethylation versus XL and ExonA/B hypomethylation and the familial PHP-Ib cases with hypomethylation of ExonA/B-only.^{80,121,122,222} Our novel quantitative approach using the Sequenom EpiTYPER mass spectrometry technology resulted in the detection of mild NESP hypo- and XL hypermethylation in addition to exon A/B hypomethylation for familial PHP-Ib cases¹²⁶ (**chapter 6**) which we did not detect before using the classical DNA methylation screening methodology.⁸⁰ In accordance with the current literature,^{132-134,221,223,224} we were also able to identify two additional PHP-Ia cases with a broad epigenetic *GNAS* defect¹²⁶. These data, in combination with the cases reported by others, suggest that PHP-Ia and PHP-Ib are extreme phenotypes of a single heterogenous (epi)genetic *GNAS* disorder. In addition, we could even expand this clinical entity further as a broad epigenetic *GNAS* defect was also detected in 3

unrelated patients with hypoparathyroidism, characterized by low calcium, high phosphate and low intact PTH levels (**chapter 7**).

In conclusion, the current clinical and functional classification does not reflect the molecular basis of PHP. Methylation changes at the *GNAS* locus have been identified in patients with PHP-Ia, PHP-Ib and now also hypoparathyroidism. A new nomenclature and classification is recommended to allow for better diagnostic procedures and therapeutic approaches to PHP. An European initiative (EUROPHPNET) was started to collect all PHP patients with epigenetic *GNAS* defects and this will bring novel insights in this complex pathology and a better classification of *GNAS* pathology.

No evidence for GNAS CNVs in PPHP patients

We studied *GNAS* CNVs in 256 patients with variable AHO features, some of them having also an abnormal platelet Gs function (**chapter 8**). No abnormal CNVs were detected in our patients using the MAQ Array as a sensitive high-throughput system to identify small CNVs in the *GNAS* locus and its surrounding regions. This suggests that classical genetic sequencing studies and methylation screening are needed to further diagnose and characterize these PPHP patients.

PPHP with platelet Gs hypofunction due to epigenetic defects in multiple imprinting genes

In this thesis, we have expanded the knowledge on *GNAS*-related pathology by focusing on PPHP patients. PPHP is characterized by AHO features that show high variability in their clinical phenotypic expression and therefore, it is difficult to correctly diagnose this disease. The low mutation detection rate for *GNAS* coding defects in PPHP cases (20-30%) can be due to misdiagnosis and/or to the fact that epigenetic and not genetic *GNAS* defects are causative. Since AHO features are also present in PHP-Ia cases with a *GNAS* epigenetic defect, the later possibility is perfectly feasible. Therefore, we studied 16 PPHP and 1 POH patients with platelet Gs hypofunction but no *GNAS* coding mutations by the Sequenom EpiTYPER for the 3 *GNAS* differentially methylated regions (NESP, XL and ExonA/B) to further investigate our hypothesis (**chapter 9**). However, since some other imprinting disorders share some typical AHO features, we designed Sequenom amplicons for IGF2, H19, SNURF and GRB10 to screen our patients. Interestingly, grouped analysis for all amplicons in

17 patients versus +/- 45 controls showed significant hypermethylation for XL (36 ± 3 vs. $29\pm 3\%$; T-test, $p<0.001$), hypermethylation for IGF2 (20 ± 10 vs. $14\pm 7\%$; T-test, $p<0.05$) and hypomethylation for SNURF (23 ± 6 vs. $32\pm 6\%$; T-test, $p<0.001$). The grouped analysis for other amplicons showed no significant differences. For the analysis of each amplicon for each patient separately, a significant abnormal methylation for these three amplicons was present in at least some patients but there was no obvious link between this epigenetic defect and their clinical phenotype. Also the separate CpG analysis for each amplicon for each patient versus the group of controls did show many significantly abnormal values but no obvious correlation with the phenotype. Further studies including more PPHP cases will have to bring novel insight in the epigenotype/phenotype correlation.

The involvement of different imprinting defects in multiple loci supports the idea that AHO features might be caused not only by a single epigenetic (*GNAS*) defect, but is rather the result of a more general imprinting error as it is described for other imprinting disorders.^{144,146,225} However, the specificity of the abnormal methylation patterns found, might also suggest that imprinting at multiple loci could be regulated through a common mechanism which should be specific for PPHP patients, and then different from other imprinting disorders. This would imply that there exist mutations in a trans-acting factor involved in establishing or maintaining methylation at multiple chromosomal loci.^{144,225-230} In fact all the imprinting mutations described so far for both IGF2 and SNURF/SNRPN, are the opposite than the ones described here for PPHP, and lead to rather different phenotypic manifestations: hypomethylation of IGF2 in 2 cases of Silver-Russel syndrome²³¹ and in a patient with clinodactily and short V finger in addition to the Silver-Russel phenotype¹⁴⁵ and gain of methylation at SNURF/SNRPN locus in Prader-Willi patients.²³² It still remains an open question whether PHP-Ib could also have multilocus imprinting abnormalities. So far only two reports have investigated DNA methylation in PHP-Ib patients for ICRs other than *GNAS*,^{126,233} in both studies no methylation defects apart from *GNAS* were reported.

Our studies also included a patient with clinical diagnosis of POH (patient 5). Progressive osseous heteroplasia is a rare syndrome, with fewer than 60 clinically-confirmed cases worldwide.²³⁴ POH was recently included in the phenotypic

spectrum of *GNAS* paternally inherited inactivation mutations.²³⁵ We here reported for the first time a *GNAS* methylation defect in POH with hypermethylation for NESP, XL and ExonA/B while the other imprinting genes were only mildly affected.

Neural tube defects and methylation abnormalities: is there a link?

Previous studies in our group have identified 5 patients with Spina Bifida and having some AHO features with platelet Gs hypofunction. Aberrant *GNAS* splicing was found in these patients due to a previously described combination of SNPs.⁸² This observation resulted in a preliminary study of *GNAS* methylation in 77 SB cases for the ExonA/B locus using the methylation-sensitive restriction digestion assay. Though 20% of the SB cases had abnormal ExonA/B methylation, there was no consistency as both hyper- and hypomethylation were detected. In addition, NTDs are not described in the typical *GNAS*-associated diseases. We therefore hypothesized that mild *GNAS* methylation changes are just part of a broader methylation defect in SB cases. The novel recent approach '27K BeadChip' from Illumina offers the possibility to study genome-wide methylation. **Chapter 10** reports the first methylation study conducted in SB patients using this 27K BeadChip and the validation of identified candidate loci with the Sequenom EpiTYPER. In addition we have used Zebrafish as model to validate the function of one of the identified candidate genes (*ACOT11*) in relation to neurulation and development.

So far, methylation studies in the field of NTDs have mainly focused on environmental factors as possible determinants of epigenetic changes. Indeed an association was found with elevated homocysteine and sub-optimal levels of folate in maternal blood,^{168,171} and very recently Wang et al.²³⁶ have found lower LINE-1 methylation levels in fetal neural tissues of NTDs compared to controls in association with a significant decrease in maternal plasma vitamin B-12 relative to controls. This is not in contrast with our results, since we have focused on gene-specific methylation analysis and it has been shown in cancer cells that a combination of LINE-1 hypomethylation and gene-specific hypermethylation is possible.²³⁷ In addition, we assume that the patients we have studied, escaped the folate preventive effect, since they develop spina bifida while their mothers had a normal

folic acid diet intake. This suggests that the genes identified might be the most relevant in the aetiology.

The study reported in **chapter 10** was a proof-of-principle study that seems very promising but definitely deserves further investigation. Future studies will include more patients in the genome-wide methylation detection approach to increase the power for the detection of possible candidate genes that needs to be confirmed by the Sequenom EpiTYPER. The study of ACOT11a in zebrafish will also be used to study the effects of hypermethylated genes (via MO technology) and hypomethylated genes (via mRNA overexpression).

The main conclusion of this thesis is that we were able to expand *GNAS*-related pathology further by both genetic and epigenetic studies using novel technology, highlighting the extreme complexity of this fascinating and still far from completely understood imprinted gene cluster.

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Scientific summary

The *GNAS* cluster, located on chromosome 20q13 gives rise to several transcripts, antisense transcripts and noncoding RNAs, including transcription of the gene for the stimulatory G-protein alpha subunit ($G\alpha_s$), which interacts with adenylyl cyclase to generate cAMP. It comprises four alternative first exons and promoters that splice onto exon 2 of the classical *GNAS* gene, and that are all located in three differentially methylated regions (DMRs) namely NESP, XL and ExonA/B. The phenotypes resulting from genetic and epigenetic abnormalities of the *GNAS* region include Albright Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO), pseudohypoparathyroidism types Ia (PHP-Ia) and Ib (PHP-Ib), and pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism (PPHP). PHP-Ia and PPHP are caused by inactivating *GNAS* mutations, while PHP-Ib results from epigenetic *GNAS* mutations. All different aspects of epigenetics and with a focus on DNA methylation and the imprinted *GNAS* cluster are reviewed in **chapters 1 and 3**.

Our research group developed a reproducible and reliable platelet-based functional Gs test, termed “platelet aggregation-inhibition test” which is based upon inhibition of platelet aggregation by cAMP after Gs stimulation. Via this test 270 patients with AHO features were screened and further classified in Gs hypo- (24%), hyper- (15%) or normal function. My PhD project will mainly focus on the finding of new (epi)genetic causes associated with an AHO phenotype and/or having PTH resistance in combination with a defective platelet Gs signaling pathway. In **chapters 5 to 7**, we have described the set up and validation of methodologies to study methylation in the different *GNAS* DMRs. **chapter 5** reports an easy screening method to detect pronounced *GNAS* methylation abnormalities such as for PHP-Ib patients. **Chapters 6 and 7** fully describe the optimization and validation of a quantitative methodology (Sequenom EpiTYPER mass-array) that allows the simultaneously study of different CpGs on large samples sets. The technique was validated in PHP-Ib and PHP-Ia cases to quantify their *GNAS* methylation defect (**chapter 6**) and was further used to expand the *GNAS*-related pathology with patients having hypoparathyroidism characterized by low calcium, high phosphate and low intact PTH levels, thus not presenting with PTH resistance but still having *GNAS* DNA methylation abnormalities (**chapter 7**). **Chapter 8** reports the first study of *GNAS* Copy Number Variants (CNVs)

that showed no evidence for CNVs in AHO patients with or without abnormal Gs platelet function. PPHP patients with Gs hypofunction but no *GNAS* coding mutation were investigated for imprinting defects in **chapter 9**. Since AHO features are shared characteristics also with other imprinting disorders, we have also studied other imprinting genes such as IGF2/H19, SNURF and GRB10. We found that PPHP patients have XL and IGF2 hypermethylation in combination with SNURF hypomethylation.

Since Gs hypofunction was also found in platelets from 5 spina bifida patients with Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy carrying a peculiar *GNAS* splice mutation, 96 other spina bifida cases were included for further (epi-)genetic *GNAS* studies (**chapter 10**). Identification of abnormal ExonA/B methylation in 20% of 77 patients was the basis for further methylation studies in SB patients. Evidence exists for a possible role for methylation in the aetiology of NTDs (**chapter 2** for review on NTDs). We have studied for the first time DNA methylation in SB cases at genomic-scale level using the human 27K BeadChip array from Illumina that includes more than 27.000 CpGs. CpGs in ZNF718, KCNQ1, GSTT1, TP53INP1, MRI1 and ACOT11 were significantly hypermethylated, while the FL45964 CpGs were hypomethylated in SB patients. The genome-wide findings were replicated with the Sequenom EpiTYPER and confirmed on a total of 101 SB patients for ACOT11, GSTT1 and ZNF718. The zebrafish ortholog ACOT11a gene was depleted in zebrafish embryos and life-screening experiments revealed a phenotype of neurulation defects but this deserves further characterization. Further studies on larger patients sets are needed to better characterize these preliminary findings.

In conclusion, we have expanded human *GNAS*-related pathology by both genetic and epigenetic studies revealing a potential relevant role of this gene in the aetiology of different pathological phenotypes, once again highlighting the extreme complexity of this fascinating, and still not completely known, imprinted gene cluster.

Samenvatting

De *GNAS* cluster bevindt zich op chromosoom 20q13 en resulteert in verschillende transcripten, antisense transcripten en niet coderende RNA's, inclusief het 'stimulatory G-protein alpha subunit ($G\alpha$) gen, dat interageert met adenylyl cyclase om vervolgens cAMP te genereren. Het omvat vier alternatieve eerste exonen en promotors, die zich allen bevinden in drie differentieel gemethyleerde gebieden (DMRs genaamd): NESP, XL en Exon A/B. De verschillende fenotypes als gevolg van genetische of epigenetische mutaties in deze *GNAS* regio omvatten Albright Hereditary Osteodystrophy (AHO), pseudohypoparathyroidie type Ia (PHP-Ia) en Ib (PHP-Ib) en pseudopseudohypoparathyroidie (PPHP). PHP-Ia and PPHP worden veroorzaakt door inactiverende *GNAS* mutaties terwijl PHP-Ib het resultaat is van epigenetische *GNAS* mutaties. Alle verschillende aspecten van epigenetica met een focus op DNA methylatie alsook de (epi)genetica en pathologie van de *GNAS* cluster worden besproken in de verschillende hoofdstukken van de literatuurstudie.

Onze onderzoeksgroep heeft een reproduceerbare en betrouwbare Gs test in bloedplaatjes ontwikkeld, genaamd de "bloedplaatjesaggregatie-inhibitie test", die gebaseerd is op de inhibitie van plaatjesaggregatie door cAMP na Gs receptor stimulatie. Aan de hand van deze test zijn 270 patiënten met een AHO fenotype gescreend en konden zij verder ingedeeld worden in drie groepen zijnde met een Gs hypo-(24%), hyper-(15%), of een Gs normale functie. Mijn doctoraatsproject zal hoofdzakelijk gericht zijn op het zoeken naar nieuwe (epi)genetische oorzaken die geassocieerd zijn met een AHO fenotype en/of een parathormoon resistentie en dit in combinatie met een verstoorde bloedplaatjes Gs signalisatie. Hoofdstukken 5 en 7 rapporteren over het ontwerp en de validatie van een nieuwe methoden om de methylatie in verschillende DMRs te bestuderen. Hoofdstuk 5 beschrijft een eenvoudige screeningsmethode om uitgesproken afwijkingen in *GNAS* methylatie te detecteren PHP-Ib patiënten. Hoofdstukken 6 en 7 beschrijven de optimalisatie en validatie van een kwantitatieve methodologie (Sequenom EpiTYPER mass-array) die het toelaat om gelijktijdig verschillende CpGs te bestuderen in een groot aantal DNA stalen. Deze techniek werd gevalideerd in verschillende PHP-Ib en PHP-Ia cassusen om

de defecten in *GNAS* methylatie te kwantificeren. De methode werd verder eveneens toegepast in andere *GNAS*-gerelateerde pathologiën zoals voor patiënten met hypoparathyroidie, een aandoening gekarakteriseerd door respectievelijk lage calcium, hoge fosfaat en lage intacte PTH waarde, maar zonder de aanwezigheid van PTH resistentie, niettegenstaande dat zij analoge afwijkingen vertonen in *GNAS* DNA methylatie als beschreven voor PHP-Ib (hoofdstuk 7). Hoofdstuk 8 rapporteert de eerste studie van die nagaat of er “Copy Number Variants” (CNVs) voorkomen in *GNAS* bij AHO patiënten met of zonder abnormale Gs plaatjesfunctie maar CNVs lijken geen oorzaak te zijn van deze pathologie. PPHP patiënten met een Gs hypofunctie maar zonder een coderende *GNAS* mutatie werden onderzocht voor imprinting defecten in hoofdstuk 9. Aangezien AHO kenmerken gelijkaardige karakteristieken vertonen met andere imprinting aandoeningen, hebben we ook andere imprinting genen zoals IGF2/H19, SNURF en GBR10 bestudeerd. We vonden dat PPHP patiënten een XL en IGF2 hypermethylatie hadden en dit in combinatie met een SNURF hypomethylatie.

Aangezien Gs hypofunctie ook werd teruggevonden in de bloedplaatjes van 5 spina bifida patiënten met AHO kenmerken en zij tevens drager zijn van een welbepaalde *GNAS* splice mutatie, werden er 96 andere spina bifida patiënten nagekeken op (epi)genetische *GNAS* afwijkingen (hoofdstuk 11). De identificatie van een afwijkende ExonA/B methylatie in 20% van de 77 patiënten, vormde de basis voor een verdergaande methylatie studie in SB patiënten. Er werd bewijs gevonden voor een mogelijke rol met betrekking tot methylatie in the etiologie van “neural tube defects” (NTD). We hebben als eersten de DNA methylatie in SB casussen op genoomwijd niveau bestudeerd door gebruik te maken van de ‘27K BeadChip array’ van Illumina die de methylatie status na gaat van meer dan 27.000 CpGs. De CpGs geassocieerd met ZNF718, KCNQ1, GSTT1, TP53INP1, MRI1 and ACOT11 toonden een significante hypermethylatie aan in SB patiënten en dit in tegenstelling tot hypogemethyleerde FL45964 CpGs. De methylatie defecten voor voor ACOT11, GSTT1 en ZNF718 werden gerepliceerd met de ‘Sequenom EpiTYPER’ bij 101 SB patiënten. Het zebavis ACOT11a ortoloog werd onderdrukt in zebavis embryo’s en life-screening experimenten toonde een fenotype met neurulatie-defecten aan,

hetgeen verder gekarakteriseerd dient te worden in de toekomst. Verdere studies om deze preliminaire resultaten beter te onderbouwen zijn vereist.

In conclusie hebben we humaan gerelateerde *GNAS* pathologiën verder uitgediept met genetische en epigenetische studies die een mogelijk relevante rol van *GNAS* in the etiologie van verschillende pathologische condities onthult. Dit beklemtoont weerom de extreme complexiteit van deze fascinerende en tot op heden niet volledig ontrafelde imprintings gen cluster.

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SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

1. **Izzi B**, Labarque V, Francoise I, Thys C, Wittevrongel C, Devriendt K, de Zegher F, Legius E, Van den Bruel A, D'Hooge M, Lambrechts D, Van Geet C, Freson K. Imprinting defect in patients with Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy and platelet Gs hypofunction. *In preparation*.
2. **Izzi B**, de Zegher F, Francois I, del Favero J, Goossens D, Wittevrongel C, Thys C, Van Geet C, Freson K. No evidence for *GNAS* Copy Number Variants in patients with features of Albright's Hereditary Osteodystrophy and abnormal platelet Gs activity. *In revision J Hum Gen*.
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9. **Izzi B**, Decallonne B, Devriendt K, Bouillon R, Vanderschueren D, Levtchenko E, de Zegher F, Van den Bruel A, Lambrechts D, Van Geet C, Freson K. A new approach to imprinting mutation detection in GNAS by Sequenom EpiTYPER system. *Clin Chim Acta*. 2010 Dec 14;411(23-24):2033-9
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15. Freson K, **Izzi B**, Jaeken J, Van Helvoirt M, Thys C, Wittevrongel C, de Zegher F, Van Geet C. Compound heterozygous mutations in the GNAS gene of a boy with morbid obesity, thyroid-stimulating hormone resistance, pseudohypoparathyroidism, and a prothrombotic state. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2008 Dec;93(12):4844-9.
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17. **Izzi B**, Pampuch A, Costanzo S, Vohnout B, Iacoviello L, Cerletti C, de Gaetano G. Determinants of platelet conjugate formation with polymorphonuclear leukocytes or monocytes in whole blood. *Thromb Haemost*. 2007

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Abstracts

1. 21st Meeting of the Belgian Endocrine Society. Leuven, Belgium. 19 November 2011
Oral presentation: GNAS methylation abnormalities identified in hypoparathyroidism patients: expanding the GNAS-related pathology. **Izzi B**, Decallonne B, Lambrechts D, Van Geet C, Vanderschueren D, Freson K.
2. Netsim/Bloodomics Workshop 2011, IJsselmeer, The Netherlands 31 May-3 June 2011.
Oral presentation: From Genome-Wide to individual CpG methylation analysis: Illumina and Sequenom EpiTYPER application for the identification of epigenetic abnormalities in Neural Tube Defects. **Izzi B**, Thys C, Louwette S, Lambrechts D, Van Geet C, Freson K.
3. European Conference of Human Genetics 2011, Amsterdam, the Netherlands, 28 – 31 May, 2011.
Poster presentation: GNAS NESP and XL hypermethylation in pseudopseudohypoparathyroidism patients. **Izzi B**, Devriendt K, Lambrechts D, Van Geet C, Freson F.
4. Epigenetics World Congress, Berlin, Germany, 17-18 September 2009.
Poster presentation: Mass-spectrometric analysis of GNAS methylation in Pseudohypoparathyroidism type Ib patients reveals overall methylation defects also for the familial cases. **Izzi B**, Claes B, Lambrechts D, Van Geet C, Freson K.
5. XXII Congress of the International Society on Thrombosis and Haemostasis, Boston, USA, 11-16 July, 2009.
Poster presentation: Possible role of GNAS imprinting in a prothrombotic phenotype: NESP55 hypermethylation in CVA at young age. **Izzi B**, Bouillon R, Devriendt K, Van Geet C, Freson K.
6. I International Workshop on cAMP Signaling Phosphodiesterases: From Genetics to Function & Human Diseases, Bethesda, MD, 8-9/06/2009
Abstract presentation: GNAS pathology and blood platelet function. **Izzi B**, Van Geet C, Freson K.

7. V LINAT meeting , OMRF, Oklahoma, 30/05-1/06/2008.
Poster presentation: Determinants of platelet aggregate formation with polymorphonuclear leukocytes or monocytes in human whole blood. **Izzi B**, Pampuch A, Costanzo S, Vohnout B, Iacoviello L, Donati MB, Cerletti C, de Gaetano G.
8. XXV Italian Conference on Cytometry, Roma, Italy, 3-6/10/2007.
Poster presentation: Platelet-leukocyte conjugates in persistent atrial fibrillation (AF). Alberti S, Pampuch A, **Izzi B**, Tamburrelli C, Angeloni G, de Gaetano G, Cerletti C.
9. XXI Congress of the International Society on Thrombosis and Haemostasis, Geneva, Switzerland, 6-12 July, 2007.
Poster presentation: Determinants of platelet aggregate formation with either polymorphonuclear leukocytes or monocytes in human whole blood. Pampuch A, **Izzi B**, Costanzo S, Vohnout B, Iacoviello L, Donati MB, Cerletti C, de Gaetano G. (J Thromb Haemost 2007; 5, suppl 2: P-M-426.)
Poster presentation: Platelet but not leukocyte activation is a prerequisite for platelet-leukocyte interaction in human whole blood. **Izzi B**, Pampuch A, de Gaetano G, Cerletti C. J (Thromb Haemost 2007; 5, suppl 2: P-M-423.)
10. XIX Congress of the Italian Society for the Study on Thrombosis and Haemostasis (SISSET), Milano, Italy, 14-17/9/2006.
Poster presentation: Platelet P-selectin expression, Platelet-PMN and Platelet-monocyte aggregate formation upon stimulation, are positively correlated in a general population. **Izzi B**, Pampuch A, Costanzo S, Vohnout B, Iacoviello L, Donati MB, Cerletti C, de Gaetano G. (Haematologica/The haematology journal 2006, 91 suppl. 2:98)

Scientific Awards

Belgian Endocrine Society Young Investigator Award 2011

